

UNIVERSITÉ DE GENÈVE
Département de médecine génétique et développement

FACULTÉ DE MÉDECINE
Professeur Evgeny M. Zdobnov

UNIVERSITÉ DU MICHIGAN
Département d'écologie et de biologie évolutive

FACULTÉ D'ÉCOLOGIE ET ÉVOLUTION
As. Professeur Melissa Duhaime

Microbial life in a Proterozoic Ocean analogue (Meromictic Lake Cadagno)

THÈSE

présentée à la Faculté de médecine et science de l'Université de Genève pour obtenir le grade
de Docteur ès sciences en Sciences de la vie mention Ecologie et évolution

Par

Jaspreet Singh Saini

de

Delhi (Inde)

Thèse N°151

GENÈVE

Atelier d'impression ReproMail

2022

Abstract

Meromictic Lake Cadagno contains a persistent microbial bloom and resembles the conditions of the Proterozoic Ocean because of oxic-anoxic transition along with sulphide-rich water. Lake Cadagno is permanently stratified into mixolimnion (oxic), chemocline (oxic-anoxic), and monimolimnion (anoxic). The microbial community of Lake Cadagno has been extensively studied for at least 25 years; contrastingly, a collective picture of nutrient biogeochemical cycling modulation by microbial eukaryotes, bacteria, and viruses was still missing. The work extends the understanding of the Lake Cadagno microbial loop and provides the first insights into the genomics of microbial eukaryotes and viruses from this ancient ocean model. This thesis presents a novel genome of a photosynthetic microbial eukaryote (referred to as *Chlorella cadagnis*) from the chemocline of Lake Cadagno, and their genomic machinery shows protein-coding genes involved in carbon, sulphur, and nitrogen metabolism. These findings reveal how microbial eukaryotes might thrive in a harsh (low light, O₂) chemocline environment. Furthermore, the work also presents that phycocyanin and phycobilins signals used for the detection of cyanobacteria in Lake Cadagno likely originated from chloroplasts of microbial eukaryotes like *Cryptomonas*. Finally, this thesis also brings the first report on the viral ecology of Lake Cadagno and potentially reveals how viruses might modulate oxygenic and anoxygenic photosynthesis in the chemocline of the ancient oceans.

Résumé

Le lac méromictique Cadagno contient une efflorescence microbienne persistante et ressemble aux conditions de l'océan protérozoïque en raison de la transition oxique-anoxique et d'une eau riche en sulfures. Le lac Cadagno est stratifié en permanence en mixolimnion (oxique), chemocline (oxique-anoxique), et monimolimnion (anoxique). La communauté microbienne du lac Cadagno a fait l'objet d'études approfondies pendant au moins 25 ans ; par contre, il manquait encore une image collective de la modulation du cycle biogéochimique des nutriments par les eucaryotes microbiens, les bactéries et les virus. Ce travail élargit la compréhension de la boucle microbienne du lac Cadagno et fournit les premières informations sur la génomique des eucaryotes microbiens et des virus de cet ancien modèle océanique. Cette thèse présente un nouveau génome d'un eucaryote microbien photosynthétique (appelé *Chlorella cadagnis*) provenant de la chimiocline du lac Cadagno, et sa machinerie génomique montre des gènes codant pour des protéines impliquées dans le métabolisme du carbone, du soufre et de l'azote. Ces résultats révèlent comment les eucaryotes microbiens peuvent prospérer dans un environnement chimiocline difficile (faible lumière, O₂). En outre, le travail présente également que les signaux de phycocyanine et de phycobilines utilisés pour la détection des cyanobactéries dans le lac Cadagno proviennent probablement de chloroplastes d'eucaryotes microbiens comme *Cryptomonas*. Enfin, cette thèse apporte également le premier rapport sur l'écologie virale du Lac Cadagno et révèle potentiellement comment les virus pourraient moduler la photosynthèse oxygénique et anoxygénique dans la chimiocline des anciens océans.

Acknowledgements

This thesis is dedicated to my family: my mother, father, brother and my love.

First and foremost, I would like to thank Dr Christel Hassler and the Swiss Confederation for supporting my application for the excellent scholarship to start this PhD at the University of Geneva. Without them, I would not be here. My sincere gratitude to Schmidheiny Foundation for providing additional final year support to finish this journey.

I am grateful to Prof. Evgeny Zdobnov for welcoming me and offering a smooth transition to the EZ lab and providing all the necessary resources. From Evgeny, one of the most special things I felt was the freedom and confidence to lead this project. Also, many thanks to Dr Mose Manni for teaching and welcoming me to the field of eukaryotic metagenomics and without his continuous support, this journey would not have been possible.

“We need to learn on how to learn”. A well said quote from Dr Melissa Duhaime always inspired me. She acted as a pillar to this PhD from the beginning to the end and taught me the first essential steps of scientific manuscript writing. Words would not be enough to describe her contribution, I thank Melissa for being my mentor and offering the support I needed.

I want to share my gratitude with EZ Lab and Duhaime Lab, and without their contribution, this journey wouldn't have been possible. Also, many thanks to Alpine Biology Center, Dr Nicolla Storelli and the Lake Cadagno team for assisting me with everything I requested. I also would like to acknowledge the great community of Anvio for troubleshooting my metagenomics queries and for offering support promptly.

In the end, I thank the jury, Dr. Jasmin Berg, and Dr. Nicola Storelli for providing me with constructive feedback for improvement of this manuscript.

Table of contents

Microbial life in a Proterozoic Ocean analogue (Meromictic Lake Cadagno)	1
Abstract	2
Table of contents	4
Glossary	7
1. Introduction	9
1.1 Meromictic lakes stratified aquatic systems	9
1.2 Microbial communities and Proterozoic Oceans	9
1.3 Why Metagenomics?	10
2. Aims	12
3. Chapters	13
3.1. Chapter I: Bacterial, phytoplankton and viral distributions and their biogeochemical contexts in meromictic Lake Cadagno offer insights into the Proterozoic Ocean microbial loop	14
Correspondent footnote	14
Abstract	15
Introduction	16
Results	18
Position of Mixolimnion, Chemocline, and Monimolimnion	18
Microbial production at the oxic/anoxic interface	19
Prokaryote- and Virus-like particle abundances and trends	22
Bacterial community composition through the mixolimnion, chemocline, and monimolimnion	23
Phytoplankton in the mixolimnion, chemocline, and monimolimnion	26
Prokaryotic genotypic and phenotypic diversity trends	29
Discussion	31
Eukaryotic algae associated with oxygenic phototrophy in the mixolimnion	31
Revisiting the microbial linkages between in situ oxygen production and anoxygenic processes in the chemocline	32
Nutrient remineralization through secondary production contributes to chemocline biomass	35
Potential for the role of viruses in modulating microbial activity and nutrient cycling	35

Conclusion	37
Methodology	38
Water-sample collection and physicochemical profiling	38
Chemical parameters	39
Dissolved compounds	39
Particulate compounds	39
Biological parameters	40
Primary production	40
Maximum quantum yield	40
Flow-cytometry (FCM)	41
Phenotypic alpha diversity of PLP (Prokaryotic-like-particles)	42
Secondary production	43
Statistical Analyses	44
Illumina MiSeq 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequence analyses	44
16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing	44
Microbial community analysis	45
Chloroplast 16S rRNA gene phylogeny	45
Data Availability	46
Acknowledgements	46
Supplementary Materials	46
3.2. Chapter II: A near-complete genome of microbial eukaryote <i>Chlorella</i> from high alpine lake reveals an enhanced CO ₂ concentrating mechanism equipped with sulfur and nitrogen metabolism	56
Abstract	56
Introduction	57
Results and Discussion	58
Microbial eukaryotes understudied members of chemocline microbial communities	60
A newly-discovered high-quality eukaryotic genome belongs to a novel species of <i>Chlorella</i>	64
Genomic evidence of <i>Chlorella</i> and <i>Cryptomonas</i> chloroplasts contributing to chlorophyll-a while phycobiliproteins specific to <i>Cryptomonas</i>	66
Integrated carbon, and nitrogen metabolism aiding <i>Chlorella</i> to thrive chemocline of Lake Cadagno	68
Conclusion	72
Materials and Methods	72
Sample collection and DNA extraction for metagenomics	72
Assembly, Mapping, and Binning	73

Taxonomic classification, quality assessment and visualization of eukaryotic MAG	73
Organelle hunting and chloroplast phylogenomics	74
Functional annotations of nuclear and chloroplast genomes	75
Comparative phylogenomics and quality assessment of Chlorellaceae genomes	75
3.3. Into the viral ecology of Lake Cadagno	78
Introduction	78
Results	79
Detecting viruses of microbial eukaryotes and prokaryotes in meromictic Lake Cadagno	79
Methodology	82
Main discussion	84
Lake Cadagno provided a better understanding of the Proterozoic Ocean microbial loop	84
A paradox of microbial abundances and biomass of chemocline	84
Cyanobacterial bloom led to the discovery of eukaryotic algal genomes in the chemocline	85
Viruses may facilitate biomass production in the chemocline, but how?	87
References	90

Glossary

Assembly:	Collection of contigs (DNA sequences)
Amplicon:	A small segment of DNA
BAM:	Binary alignment map
Binning:	A process of obtaining microbial genomes
Biogeochemical:	Transformation of chemical elements by organisms in the environment
Chemocline:	Oxic-anoxic boundary in aquatic systems
Contigs:	Stretches of DNA sequences
Coverage:	Average number of times a genome is sequenced
DCM:	Deep Chlorophyll Max
FCS:	Flow-cytometry machine for counting cells and virus-like-particles
GSB:	Green sulfur bacteria
Libraries:	Total genomic DNA
MAG:	Metagenome-Assembled Genome
Mapping:	Aligning the raw sequences on reference genomes.
Metagenomics:	Study of genetic material collected from the environment
Meromictic:	A term used to describe stratified lakes
Microbe:	A microscopic life and prospectively including viruses
Mixolimnion:	Oxic zone of meromictic lake
Monimolimnion:	Anoxic zone of meromictic lake
NCLDV:	Nucleocytoplasmic large DNA virus
Phage:	Bacteriophages; viruses infecting bacteria
Phytoplankton:	Photosynthetic oxygenic microbes
Proterozoic era:	2.5 billion to 542 million years ago
Reads:	Raw DNA sequences
Scaffolds:	Portion of genome sequences including contigs and gaps
16S rRNA:	A gene used to identify bacterial communities
PCR:	Polymerase chain reaction (PCR)
PLP:	Prokaryotic-like-particles
VLP:	Virus-like-particles

1. Introduction

1.1 Meromictic lakes stratified aquatic systems

The term *meromictic* in limnology refers to the lakes which do not undergo complete seasonal mixing. Depending upon the type of mixing, Meromictic lakes are broadly categorised into ectogenic, crenogenic, and biogenic¹. Ectogenic meromictic lakes result from the mixture of seawater and freshwater and usually occur near coastal areas, for example, Nitinat and Sakinaw Lakes in British Columbia¹. Some meromictic lakes, like Hall Lake, are biogenic because of organic matter deposition². In contrast, meromixis occurs when an external inflow of low-density freshwater mixes with the high-density groundwater is called crenogenic. A typical example of the latter is Lake Cadagno³. The upper oxic and lower anoxic part of meromictic lakes is called mixolimnion and monimolimnion respectively, while the region between the oxic and anoxic boundaries is called the chemocline. The chemocline of some meromictic lakes, e.g Fayetteville Green Lake⁴, Ace Lake⁵, and Lake Shunet⁶, is characterised by a turbidity peak composed of phototrophic sulphur bacteria.

1.2 Significance of microbial communities of Proterozoic Oceans

Billions of years of evolution have resulted in the emergence of microbial life, including archaea, bacteria, eukaryotes⁷ and viruses⁸. Chemoautotrophy⁹ and anoxygenic photosynthesis (as early as ~3.77 Gyr)¹⁰ may have been the earliest mode of primary production until cyanobacteria re-engineered the ecological dynamics during the Great Oxidation Event^{11,12}. This planetary transition between anoxic and oxic conditions is thought to have occurred in the Proterozoic Era (2.5 billion -541 million years ago)^{11,12}. The oxic-anoxic biogeochemical transition also coincides with the evolution of microbial eukaryotes roughly around 1.8 billion years ago¹³. This shows that anoxygenic-oxygenic shift and evolution of early microbial eukaryotes coincidentally occurred during the Proterozoic era. There may have also been a co-occurrence of anoxygenic and oxygenic photosynthesis, as proposed in the oxic-anoxic boundary (chemocline) of the Proterozoic Ocean¹⁴ (Model; Fig. 1). Maybe that's why microbial

life in Proterozoic Oceans has received much attention owing to its central role in Earth's biogeochemical cycling¹⁴⁻¹⁹. Although oxygenic and anoxygenic phototrophs rely on contrasting electron donors (H_2O and H_2S) for carbon fixation, our understanding of the overall microbial biogeochemical cycling in Proterozoic Oceans is arguably restricted to geochemical evidence and fossil records. Nutrient biogeochemical cycling in the Proterozoic Ocean might be important to understand the evolution of oxygenic and anoxygenic phototrophs and early microbial eukaryotes. Therefore, this project investigated the microbial communities of the Proterozoic Ocean model²⁰⁻²⁴.

Introduction, figure. 1: Proterozoic Ocean model inspired by *Johnston et al 2009* created with BioRender.com.

1.3 Origin of plastids and photosynthetic microbial eukaryotes

Oxygenic photosynthetic microbes like cyanobacteria likely originated in the archaean period ~2500-2700 Myr^{25,26}, which also gave rise to the origin of chloroplasts following GOE²⁶. The primary endosymbiosis between cyanobacteria and single cell eukaryotes²⁷ may have given rise to the first multicellularity and origin of photosynthetic microbial eukaryotes on Earth²⁸. The emergence of oxygenic phototrophs like cyanobacteria and photosynthetic microbial eukaryotes may have contributed to the aerobic conditions posed to be essential for evolution of early life on Earth²⁹. Chlorophytes are amongst the oldest photosynthetic microbial eukaryotes which date back to the Proterozoic era³⁰. But how did these photosynthetic microbial eukaryotes may have thrived in Proterozoic Oceans of early earth? Our knowledge remains limited.

Microbial eukaryotes in present earth are autotrophic³¹, heterotrophic³², and mixotrophic³³ and their characteristics have pivotal roles in microbial food webs including the carbon cycle^{34,35}. Microbial eukaryotes are often called "Protists"³⁶ and kingdom Protista is classified into several phylogenetic lineages called Amoebozoa, Archaeplastida, Rhizaria, Alveolates, Stramenopiles, Excavates, and Opisthokonts³⁵. Sometimes protists are categorised based on their size 1) Microplankton (20-200µm) 2) Picoplankton (2-20µm) 3) Nanoplankton (0.2-2µm). Typical examples of micro-planktons are ciliates, diatoms, foraminifera. Whereas coccolithophores and chlorophytes are good examples of nano and pico-planktons.

1.4 Bacterial realms engines of microbial food-webs

Amongst the total prokaryotic population ($4-6 \times 10^{30}$)³⁷, bacteria are by far the most numerous (1.3×10^{29}) life on our planet³⁸ and controls primary production of via oxygenic^{39,40} and anoxygenic photosynthesis^{41,42}. Besides carbon fixation, bacterial biogeochemical networks also modulate global iron⁴³, sulphur⁴⁴, nitrogen⁴⁵, and methane⁴⁶ cycles, hence regulating the earth's global biogeochemical cycling⁴⁵. Maybe because of their significance to the ecosystem, bacteria also contribute most to the global microbial biomass (70 Gt C) followed by fungi (12 Gt C), archaea (7 Gt C), protists (4 Gt C), and viruses (0.2 Gt C)⁴⁷. The bacterial presence also contributes to the microbial food webs through remineralization of organic matter and aids in energy flow via predation^{48,49}. Bacteria are also central to the microbial loop by serving as a prey

for larger organisms such as zooplankton, simultaneously also being predated by smaller biological entities such as viruses ⁵⁰.

1.5 The Ecological role of viruses

Viruses are ubiquitous on this planet and their numbers (10^{31}) exceed that of the stars in this observable universe ⁵¹. Viruses are major players in marine biogeochemical cycling ⁵², and are also found crucial for soil ⁵³ and freshwater aquatic ecosystems ^{54,55}. Most of these viruses infect the bacteria are called bacteriophages. However, viruses infecting eukaryotes are also emerging with their global presence ^{56,57}. Viruses manipulate their host mainly using lytic and lysogenic cycles and also contribute auxiliary metabolic genes (AMGs) necessary for the host's carbon, sulphur and nitrogen cycling ⁵⁸. Viral mediated lysis ruptures the bacterial cell and releases the dissolved organic carbon (DOC) and nutrients necessary for the functioning of microbial food webs in aquatic ecosystems ⁵⁰. The release of nutrients through viral lysis is also called Viral Shunting. Viruses also contribute to the formation of aggregates by producing sticky lysates resulting in the effective sinking of biomass from the surface of the ocean to the bottom in a process known as Viral Shuttling ⁵⁰.

Introduction, Figure 3: Viral shunting and shuttling within aquatic systems.

Source: Shunt or Shuttle (Alex J. Poulton, Nature Geoscience).

1.6 Metagenomics approach to investigate microbial communities

Metagenomics is an approach to assess microbial communities' taxonomic and functional metabolic potential. Metagenomics has empowered the planetary investigation of microbes in animal, ecological, and human health ^{59,60} and drastically expanded our knowledge of microbial diversity, owing to the ability to characterise uncultured microbes ⁷. These aspects of metagenomics have also led to our current understanding of the global diversity of viruses ^{56,57,61}. It has the potential to investigate all domains of microbial life, from small viruses to larger microbial eukaryotes; this potential may be why genomics has piqued the interest of other fields of big data generation, like astronomy and Twitter and YouTube analytics ⁶².

Introduction, Figure 3: Overview of Metagenomic Workflow created with BioRender.com

The metagenomic workflow is exquisitely described by ⁵⁹. Briefly, it includes 1-2) the collection and extraction of DNA from the sample 3) followed by long-read (ex: Oxford Nanopore, PacBio) and/or short-read (ex: Illumina) sequencing. 4) The sequenced data is called *reads*, which are preprocessed through quality control steps and 5) then assembled into *contigs*

using metagenomic assemblers like Meta-IDBA ⁶³, Megahit ⁶⁴, SPAdes ⁶⁵. The assembled contigs are referred *assembly*, 6) which is binned to Metagenomic Assembled Genomes (MAGs) by programs like CONCOCT ⁶⁶, MaxBin2 ⁶⁷, MetaBAT2 ⁶⁸, VizBin ⁶⁹. The process is often called *binning*. 7) These MAGs are quality assessed using BUSCO ⁷⁰ and CheckM ⁷¹ followed by their 7) taxonomic assignment using Genome Taxonomy Database Toolkit (GTDB-Tk) ⁷², and/or contigs annotation tools ⁷³. Fortunately, these metagenomic workflows are fully automated by the availability platforms like ATLAS ⁷⁴ and Anvio ⁷⁵.

1.5.1 Advantages and disadvantages of Metagenomics

Metagenomics has empowered the investigation into microbial community composition aiding the identification of genomic diversity of viruses ⁵⁷, bacteria ^{76,77}, and microbial eukaryotes ⁷⁸. Because of metagenomics, predicting genes ^{79,80} has made metabolic potential investigations possible ⁸¹. This gene and genome centric approach has driven drastic progress in the field of microbial ecology ⁸². Although the detection of genes and prediction of the metabolic potential is possible, metagenomics are still limited in functional aspects. It lacks the knowledge if a gene is expressed or unexpressed or active or inactive ⁸³. That's where metatranscriptomics serves as an alternative to assess the functional activity of microbes ⁸⁴. The cost of shotgun metagenomics is extremely high as compared to 16S sequencing ⁸⁵, which makes it inaccessible to scientific communities, especially from developing countries.

1.6 Other powerful methods for assessment of microbial communities

Abundance, diversity, and productivity are amongst the core parameters to assess the microbial communities in complex natural environments.

1.6.1 Abundance

The relative abundance of bacterial, and eukaryotic communities were assessed using 16S and 18S sequencing. 16S and 18S small stranded units of ribosomal ribonucleic acid (SSU rRNA) which belonged to 30S and 40S subunits of prokaryotic and eukaryotic ribosome where S stands for Svedberg unit. The 16S and 18S rRNA encoding for these ribosomal submits has been

widely used to assess prokaryotic and eukaryotic microbial community composition ⁸⁶, and is often restricted to relative abundance because of different amounts of gene copies per genome ⁸⁷ and is not a representation of absolute abundance.

Flow-cytometry is another cheap, quick, and reliable technique to assess microbial (archaea, protist, bacteria, archaea) abundance ⁸⁸⁻⁹⁰. One drawback is that flow-cytometry data takes the edge on the quantitative side as compared to 16S sequencing, which is an alternate qualitative assessment of microbial communities.

Fluorescent *in-situ* hybridisation (FISH) is another powerful technique to assess and identify known microorganisms inside microbial communities including archaea, bacteria, and eukaryotes in complex environmental samples ⁹¹. Some disadvantages include, difficulties with sample autofluorescence, the labour intensive task of designing and optimising probes ^{92, 92}, as well as the need to know the 16S sequence of the microorganism to be searched for.

1.6.2 Diversity

Introduction, Figure 4: Richness and evenness of Alpha diversity created with BioRender.com

The diversity of microbial communities are often described as alpha and beta diversity ⁹³. Alpha diversity shows the diversity of a community in a single sample and is often called species richness and evenness ⁹⁴. Species richness refers to the diversity of the sample (how many types)

while evenness explains how diversity is distributed within the sample (Intro, Figure 4A-B). Beta diversity is when diversity of multiple samples is compared with each other.

The phenotypic and genotypic diversity of prokaryotic communities can further be assessed using flow-cytometry and 16S sequencing data. With R built packages like flowDiv, and phenoflow, assessment of phenotypic diversity using flow-cytometry fingerprints is also possible ⁹⁵⁻⁹⁸. On the other hand, R based packages like phyloseq ⁹⁹, microbiome ¹⁰⁰ are specialised to assess genotypic alpha and beta diversity of microbial communities.

1.6.3 Productivity

Autotrophic and heterotrophic production by microbial communities in aquatic systems are called primary and secondary productivity. Phytoplankton are responsible for half of the global primary productivity via oxygenic photosynthesis ¹⁰¹. Contrasting to the oxygenic photosynthesis, chemoautotrophy and anoxygenic photosynthesis uses species like Fe (II) and H₂S in place of H₂O for primary production ¹⁰² and is more common in sulphide rich ecosystems like meromictic lakes ^{103,104}, peat bogs ¹⁰⁵. Organic matter produced by primary producers is decomposed into dissolved organic matter by heterotrophic bacteria via secondary productivity ¹⁰⁶. Thus, primary and secondary productivity are main pillars of microbial food webs especially in aquatic ecosystems. The primary and secondary productivity are usually measured with bulk methods, but can also be assessed by single cell methods like nanoSIMS ¹⁰⁷.

1.5 Meromictic Lake Cadagno, a Proterozoic Ocean analogue

The Great Oxidation Event, and the planetary anoxic-oxic transition occurred at the beginning of the Proterozoic Era¹². Multiple Proterozoic Ocean models proposed the chemocline (oxic-anoxic boundary) followed by sulphide-rich anoxic zone ^{14,108}. Similar euxinic conditions have been reported for meromictic Lake Cadagno²⁰⁻²⁴, which is 21 metres deep situated at 1921 m within the Swiss Alps ³. The permanently stratified water column is composed of three zones; 1) Mixolimnion (oxic) 2) Monimolimnion (anoxic), and 3) Chemocline (oxic-anoxic) boundary. The chemocline, situated at around 12.0 m of depth, harbours a dense bacterial layer composed mainly of purple (PSB) and green (GSB) sulphur bacteria ¹⁰⁹⁻¹¹³.

1.5.1 Biogeochemical cycles in Meromictic Lake Cadagno

At the turn of the century, a study by Camacho et al. [110] detailed the major phytoplankton species of the upper layer of Lake Cadagno, the mixolimnion. The study also showed the strong presence of CO₂ fixation in the zone of maximum turbidity of the chemocline, where oxygenic and anoxygenic photosynthesis were nearly equivalent. Also very interesting was the presence of CO₂ fixation in the absence of light at very high levels, again in the chemocline zone. At the upper edge of chemocline, phytoplankton are often indicated by the peak of Chl *a* and phycocyanin, while at the core the peak of turbidity is used as a proxy for purple and green sulphur bacteria. This contrasting presence of microbial guilds persisted for more than two decades. While phytoplankton leverages oxygen (H₂O) as electron donor in oxygenic photosynthesis, anoxygenic phototrophic sulfur bacteria uses sulfur (H₂S) for carbon fixation via anoxygenic photosynthesis.

Purple sulphur bacteria (PSB) *Chromatium okenii*, *Thiodictyon syntrophicum*, *Lamprocystis purpurea*, and Green sulphur bacteria (GSB) *Chlorobium Clathratiforme*, *Chlorobium phaeobacteroides* well studied anoxygenic phototrophs responsible for carbon fixation in the zone of chemocline^{3,104,109,113–126}. Amongst these phototrophic sulphur bacteria, *C. okenii* was once found to be least abundant but contributing around 40% of ammonia assimilation and 70% of carbon uptake in the chemocline¹⁰⁷. Recently it has been shown that *C. okenii* is responsible for most of the nitrogen fixed in the chemocline (about 80%) [24,120], while previously only GSBs were known to be able to fix nitrogen¹¹⁸. Maybe because of the versatile metabolism of CO₂ and N₂ fixation, *C. okenii* contributes most to the biomass of the prokaryotic population of the chemocline and likely because of unusually large size (8-10µm)^{24,113}. Under microaerophilic conditions, it has been shown that PSBs, such as *C. okenii* and *T. syntrophicum*, are able to fix CO₂ in the dark¹¹⁴. Apart from sulphide oxidizers and sulphate reducers, 16S rRNA sequences of iron oxidizers and reducers were also recovered, and photoferrotrophic iron oxidation contributed around 10% of total primary production in the chemocline¹²⁷.

Within the anoxic mixolimnion, the sinking biomass of the chemocline settles to the sediments, where microbial driven phosphorus recycling occurs, which may be an important

nutrient for the primary production of the chemocline²⁰. Especially near the sediments, archaea modulation of anaerobic methane oxidation also occurs¹²⁸. Thus overall resembling Lake Cadagno as a biogeochemical hub where each stratified zone ie. mixolimnion, chemocline, and monimolimnion provides a unique yet diverse ecological niche for functionality of microbes.

1.6 Gap of knowledge and aims

Within the chemocline, purple and green sulfur bacteria (*Chromatium*, *Thiodictyon*, *Lamprocystis*, *Chlorobium*) contribute to the peak in turbidity and carry out anoxygenic photo-and-chemosynthesis¹⁰⁴. Although the meromictic Lake Cadagno has been extensively studied for decades, the collective functioning of microbial communities (bacteria, eukaryotes, and viruses) in context of abundance, productivity, and diversity is still missing. Furthermore, *Chromatium okenii*, which dominates the microbial bloom of chemocline in biomass²⁴, also carries dark sulphide oxidation which was coupled to high oxygen consumption possibly produced by *in situ* oxygen production by diatoms and photosynthetic algae¹¹⁴. In contrast, no genomic report was available on the microbial eukaryotes of Lake Cadagno and what kind of metabolism they might use to thrive. Viral infections of prokaryotic and eukaryotic hosts modulate the carbon cycle globally^{50,129}. The presence of viruses might modulate the carbon cycle in the chemocline of Lake Cadagno and recently, CRISPR (clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats), an immunity against viruses, was identified in anoxygenic PSB *C. okenii* genome¹¹³ hinting at ongoing viral predation. Contrastingly, no data was available on the abundance of viruses in Lake Cadagno and how viruses modulate the phototrophic sulphur bacterial community. Until now, no genome of virus infecting purple or green sulfur bacteria is available.

To overall address the highlighted gap of knowledge of microbial food webs, eukaryotes, and viruses in Lake Cadagno, this thesis addresses these aims with the following three chapters and further explores their significance in context to Proterozoic Ocean microbial communities.

Chapter I: Bacterial, phytoplankton and viral distributions and their biogeochemical contexts in meromictic Lake Cadagno offer insights into the Proterozoic Ocean microbial loop.

Chapter II: A near-complete genome of microbial eukaryote *Chlorella* from high alpine lake reveals an enhanced CO₂ concentrating mechanism along with sulfur and nitrogen metabolism.

Chapter III: Potential of viruses modulating oxygenic and anoxygenic photosynthesis in chemocline of Lake Cadagno.

3. Chapters

Chapter I: *Bacterial, phytoplankton and viral distributions and their biogeochemical contexts in meromictic Lake Cadagno offer insights into the Proterozoic ocean microbial loop*

Jaspreet S Saini^{1,2}, Christel Hassler¹, Rachel Cable³, Marion Fourquez⁶, Francesco Danza^{4,5}, Samuele Roman⁴, Mauro Tonolla^{4,5}, Nicola Storelli^{4,5}, Stéphan Jacquet⁷, Evgeny M. Zdobnov², Melissa B. Duhaime^{3#}

Submission status: **Published¹³⁰ in ASM mBio.**

Contribution statement

I contributed to conceptualization, investigation, data curation, methodology, formal analysis, visualisation, writing original draft and review and editing.

Partial funding acquisition

I secured the first three of my salary for this project by obtaining a Swiss Government Excellence Scholarship. Prof. Hassler supported my application for this scholarship. I reached Ernst et Lucie Schmidheiny Foundation, which provided an additional 18 months of my scholarship with the support letters from Prof. Zdobnov and Prof. Duhaime.

3.1. Bacterial, phytoplankton and viral distributions and their biogeochemical contexts in meromictic Lake Cadagno offer insights into the Proterozoic Ocean microbial loop

Jaspreet S Saini^{1,2}, Christel Hassler¹, Rachel Cable³, Marion Fourquez⁶, Francesco Danza^{4,5}, Samuele Roman⁴, Mauro Tonolla^{4,5}, Nicola Storelli^{4,5}, Stéphan Jacquet⁷, Evgeny M. Zdobnov², Melissa B. Duhaime^{3#}

¹Department F.-A Forel for Environmental and Aquatic Sciences, Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of Geneva, Switzerland

²Department of Genetic Medicine and Development, University of Geneva, and Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, Geneva, Switzerland

³Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI, United States

⁴Institute of Microbiology (IM), Department for environmental constructions and design (DACD), University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland (SUPSI), Switzerland

⁵Department of Botany and Plant Biology, University of Geneva, Switzerland

⁶Aix Marseille Univ., Université de Toulon, CNRS, IRD, MIO UM 110, 13288, Marseille, France

⁷Université Savoie Mont-Blanc, INRAE, UMR CARTELE, Thonon-les-Bains, France

Correspondent footnote

duhaimem@umich.edu

telephone 734-764-6219; fax 734-763-0544

Abstract

Lake Cadagno, a permanently stratified high-alpine lake with a persistent microbial bloom in its chemocline, has long been considered a model for the low-oxygen, high-sulfide Proterozoic Ocean. Although the lake has been studied for at least 25 years, the absence of concerted study of the bacteria, phytoplankton, and viruses, together with primary and secondary production, has hindered a comprehensive understanding of its microbial food web. Here, the identities, abundances, and productivity of microbes were evaluated in the context of Lake Cadagno biogeochemistry. Photosynthetic pigments together with 16S rRNA gene phylogenies suggest the prominence of eukaryotic phytoplankton chloroplasts, primarily Chlorophytes. Chloroplasts closely related to those of high-alpine adapted *Ankyra judayi* persisted with oxygen in the mixolimnion where photosynthetic efficiency was high, while chloroplasts of *Closteriopsis*-related chlorophytes peaked in the chemocline and monimolimnion. Anoxygenic phototrophic sulfur bacteria, *Chromatium*, dominated the chemocline along with *Lentimicrobium*, a genus of known fermenters. Highest secondary production in chemocline suggests anoxygenic primary producers depended on heterotrophic nutrient remineralization. Virus-to-microbe ratio peaked with phytoplankton abundances in the mixolimnion and were at a minimum where *Chromatium* was highest, trends that suggest viruses may play a role in the modulation of primary production. Through the combined analysis of bacterial, eukaryotic, viral, and biogeochemical spatial dynamics, this study provides a comprehensive synthesis of the Lake Cadagno microbial loop. This study offers a new ecological perspective on how biological and geochemical connections may have occurred in the chemocline of the Proterozoic Ocean where eukaryotic microbial life is thought to have evolved.

Importance

As a window to the past, the study offers insights into the role of microbial guilds of Proterozoic Ocean chemoclines in the production and recycling of organic matter of these high sulfur, low oxygen ancient oceans. The new observations described here suggest that chloroplasts of eukaryotic algae were persistent in the low oxygen upper-chemocline along with the purple and green sulfur bacteria known to dominate the lower half of the chemocline. Further, this study provides the first insights into Lake Cadagno viral ecology. High viral abundances suggested

viruses may be essential components of the chemocline where their activity may result in the release and recycling of organic matter. The framework developed in this study through the integration of diverse geochemical and biological data types lays the foundation for future studies to quantitatively resolve the processes performed by discrete populations comprising the microbial loop in this early anoxic ocean analogue.

Introduction

Roughly 2.3 billion years (Gyr) ago the oceans were sulfide-rich¹³¹ and anoxygenic photosynthesis was a dominant mode of microbial primary production¹⁴. Following the great oxidation event 2.4-2.1 Gyr¹³², anoxygenic photosynthesis continued to sustain microbial life in the euxinic environments below oxygenated surface waters^{14,131,133}. Habitats in which anoxygenic photosynthesis significantly contributes to primary production continue to persist, such as in sulfur-rich meromictic lakes¹³⁴ like Lake Cadagno³. These permanently stratified lakes are resistant to seasonal mixing events that would otherwise redistribute oxygen throughout the water column¹³⁵. In these systems, biogeochemical processes provide a link between the contrasting dominant modes of primary production, thereby directly connecting the food webs of the oxygenated and anoxic habitats. By resolving these biogeochemical connections, we may obtain insights on how oxygenic and anoxygenic photosynthesis may have evolved in the Proterozoic Ocean's chemocline.

Meromictic Lake Cadagno is a well-established ancient ocean model²⁰⁻²⁴ owing to its permanently stratified oxygenated surface and euxinic bottom waters, its shallow chemocline within the photic zone, and sulfate and molybdenum concentrations lower than those of modern oceans. The microbial community composition of meromictic Lake Cadagno typifies the reconstructed signatures of life in the Proterozoic Ocean^{20,22,24}. Purple and green sulfur bacteria (PSB and GSB, respectively) are amongst the hallmark bloom-forming microbes that are frequently observed in the chemocline of Lake Cadagno^{104,122}. Within the chemocline, carbon, nitrogen, sulfur, and iron cycling are integrated through metabolic activities of the anoxygenic photosynthetic purple sulfur and green sulfur bacteria^{120,121,136,137}. Two PSB, *Thiodictyon syntrophicum* and *Chromatium okenii*, have been identified as the greatest contributors to primary production in Lake Cadagno^{104,107,120}. However, recent measurements of primary production have been limited to the chemocline^{104,138} and measurements of secondary production

do not exist. Phytoplankton (including modern eukaryotes and cyanobacteria) likely coexisted with anoxygenic phototrophic sulfur bacteria in the Proterozoic Ocean ^{18,139}. High phytoplankton abundances and productivity were expected in the oxic zone because phytoplankton produces organic matter via oxygenic photosynthesis. In order to better understand microbial loop linkages across the stratified mixolimnion-chemocline transition in Lake Cadagno, paired measurements of productivity, microbial community composition, and diversity are essential next steps.

Lake Cadagno studies to date have focused on the phytoplankton and prokaryotic members of the microbial community and have yet to include viruses. Viruses are known to impact both phytoplankton and heterotrophic microbial populations through lysis and lysogeny and may hold a central position in the marine food webs and biogeochemical cycling ^{50,54}. Through the lysis of their microbial hosts, viruses play a role in the conversion of particulate organic carbon to dissolved organic carbon, which is predicted to be capable of sustaining the microbial loop ^{140,141}. Viruses have been identified in meromictic lakes ^{5,142,143}, but their abundances across the vertical water column of Lake Cadagno are unknown.

To better understand the role the microbial loop plays in sustaining the food web across the stratified layers of Lake Cadagno, microbial community members (phytoplankton, prokaryotes, and viruses) were studied in the context of biogeochemical and primary and secondary production measurements. We hypothesized the mixolimnion to have low primary production relative to the chemocline because the chemocline is known to be inhabited by a persistent microbial bloom of primary producing phototrophic sulfur bacteria ¹⁰⁴. We also expected high secondary production and viral abundance to be an indicator of effective organic matter recycling within the Lake Cadagno water column, because photoautotrophs, both phototrophic sulfur bacteria and phytoplankton, rely on heterotrophs and viruses for the remineralization of organic matter and nutrient cycling ^{144,145}. Through a combination of physical, chemical and biological analyses, this work provides new evidence on how transitions between permanently stratified lake habitats and assemblages may sustain microbial food webs, informing our understanding of the aquatic ecosystems of early Earth.

Results

Position of Mixolimnion, Chemocline, and Monimolimnion

Transitions between the major stratified layers sampled from Lake Cadagno were visually apparent by the colour of pigmented biomass captured on the 0.22 μm filters (Fig. 1A). From the surface to 12.5 m depth, the oxygen levels fell from a maximum of 9.24 mg/L to 2.79 mg/L (light green, day 2; Fig. 1B). As hypoxia is defined as 2.00 mg $\text{O}_2/\text{L}^{146}$, 12.5 m marks the boundary of the oxic mixolimnion zone and the upper chemocline (top light purple; Fig. 1). The chemocline was at a depth of 13.0-15.5 m, as determined based on near-zero oxygen and light levels (day 2), peaked turbidity, a slight decrease in temperature, and a simultaneous rise in conductivity (dark purple; Fig. 1, B-D). At 14.5 m, oxygen levels were near-zero and <1% of surface light penetrated (day 2; Fig. 1B, D). Within the chemocline, the deep chlorophyll maximum (DCM) and peak turbidity shifted overnight between days 1 and 2, but in both cases, the peak turbidity was observed 0.5-1.5 m below the DCM (day 2; Fig. 1B, D). Peak phycocyanin concentrations (26.53 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$) and basal fluorescence ($F_b = 66.0$) were observed at the DCM (day 2, 13.5-14 m) and above a secondary chlorophyll peak at 15 m (Fig. 1D, Fig. S2). The monimolimnion was defined as the zone between 15.5 m and the benthos. The gradual increase in particulate sulfur (0.74 ppm), H_2S (2.84 mg/L) and ammonia (262.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$) concentrations were observed in the monimolimnion, as well as a decline in turbidity and photosynthetic pigments (Fig. 1B, E, H).

Figure 1. Depth profiles of biogeochemical parameters of Lake Cadagno. Dashed and solid lines represent 28 and 29 August 2017, respectively. Standard deviations for each sample are indicated by horizontal bars. (A) Photographs of biomass collected on 0.22 μm (142 mm diameter) filters from Lake Cadagno mixolimnion, chemocline, and monimolimnion strata. The depth profiles of (B) oxygen and turbidity, (C) conductivity and temperature, (D) Chl *a*, phycocyanin, and photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) (E) hydrogen sulfide and ammonium concentrations, (F) net primary production (NPP) and secondary production (SP) rates, (G) particulate organic carbon (POC) and dissolved organic carbon (DOC) concentrations, (F) particulate sulfur (PS) and particulate organic nitrogen (PON) concentrations. In B-H, the high O₂ mixolimnion, mid O₂ mixolimnion, low O₂ mixolimnion-chemocline transition zone, chemocline, lower-chemocline, and anoxic monimolimnion layers are indicated by light green, dark green, light-lilac, lilac, dark lilac and light brown backgrounds, respectively.

Microbial production at the oxic/anoxic interface

Between 7.0-11.0 m in the lower mixolimnion, there was a slight rise (up to 13.12 $\mu\text{g/L}$ on day 1 and 11.80 $\mu\text{g/L}$ on day 2) in Chl *a* (Fig. 1D). The Chl *a* peak in the mixolimnion at 9.0 m corresponded with a peak in net primary production (NPP; 3210 $\text{ng C L}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$; Fig. 1D, F). The NPP peak declined in the lower mixolimnion (11.0 m) and upper chemocline (13.0 m). Though NPP was not measured below 13.0 m, basal and maximum fluorescence measured through the chemocline gave an indication of phytoplankton photosynthetic activity and efficiency (Fig. S2). In the oxic-anoxic boundary, a maximum Fv/Fm (an indicator of photosynthetic efficiency) of 0.49 was observed between 13.0-13.5 m and declined to 0.36 at 15.0 m (Fig. 1F) where the light was absent. Overlapping with this oxygenic photosynthesis, the highest rates of secondary productivity (SP) were observed through the chemocline (Fig.1F). SP was significantly positively associated with some indicators of both photosynthetic microbes (Pearson: Chl *a*: $R=0.96$, $p\text{-value}=1.7\text{e-}05$; phycocyanin: $R=0.80$, $p\text{-value}=0.005$) and total biomass (Pearson: turbidity: $R=0.78$, $p\text{-value}=0.007$; total cell counts: $R=0.65$, $p\text{-value}=0.04$) (Fig. S3). The peak of DOC (14.0 m) followed the peaks of POC, PON (15.0 m; Fig. 1G-H). Below the chemocline,

some organic and inorganic compounds continued to rise (particulate sulfur, H_2S , NH_4^+), while PON and POC dropped (Fig. 1).

Figure 2. Dashed and solid lines represent 28 and 29 August 2017, respectively. Standard deviations for each sample are indicated by horizontal bars. The abundances of (A) prokaryote-like particles (PLP) and (B) Free virus-like particles (VLP) from flow cytometry analyses and (C) virus-to-microbe ratio, as VLP/PLP.

Prokaryote- and Virus-like particle abundances and trends

The concentration of prokaryotic-like particles (PLPs; prokaryotic cell counts inferred from flow cytometry data) was highest in the chemocline at 15.0 m, roughly half that in the monimolimnion, and was lowest in the mixolimnion (Fig. 2A). The flow-cytometry PLP counts were in line with the fluorescent in situ hybridization (FISH) counts of the previous year (July

2016), which reported up to 10^6 cells/ml in chemocline¹⁰⁹ and also concurred with the turbidity (Fig. 1D), which is used as a proxy for cell density in Lake Cadagno^{24,147}. In contrast, free virus-like particles (VLPs; viral counts inferred from flow cytometry data) were highest at the bottom of the mixolimnion, lowest in the upper mixolimnion, and relatively invariable through the rest of the water column (Fig. 2B). As a result, the virus to microbe ratio (VMR) peaked at the bottom of the mixolimnion (1642 at 11 m), but decreased drastically (158 at 15 m) when prokaryotic-like particles rose in the chemocline (Fig. 2C).

Bacterial community composition through the mixolimnion, chemocline, and monimolimnion

Both relative (OTU count scaled by total OTUs) and inferred absolute abundances (OTU count scaled by total FCM PLP counts¹⁴⁸) were considered to assess abundances of microbial taxa through Lake Cadagno (Fig. 3A-B). Inferred absolute abundances of prokaryotic-classified cells ('Bacteria' & 'Archaea' OTU count scaled by total FCM PLP counts¹⁴⁸) were at a minimum in the oxic mixolimnion (day 1; 0-12.5 m; Fig. 3B, Table S1). On average, the mixolimnion community primarily consisted of Actinobacteria (35.37% of total OTUs; 33,841 cells/ml), Bacteroidetes (21.49% of total OTUs; 20,557 cells/ml), Proteobacteria (20.46% of total OTUs; 19,579 cells/ml), and Cyanobacteria (5.46% of total OTUs; 5,229 cells/ml) phyla (Fig. 3A-B, Table S1).

Figure 3: (A) Relative (OTU count scaled by total OTUs) and (B) Inferred (OTU count scaled by total FCM PLP counts¹⁴⁸) abundances of prokaryotic phyla at the sampled depths in Lake Cadagno, (C) genera in the Proteobacteria phylum, (D) genera in the Bacteroidetes phylum. To the right of each panel, the high O₂ mixolimnion, mid O₂ mixolimnion, low O₂ mixolimnion-chemocline transition zone, chemocline, lower-chemocline, and anoxic monimolimnion layers are indicated by light green, dark green, light-lilac, lilac, dark lilac and light brown backgrounds, respectively and correspond with the depths reported on the left-most y-axis.

In the chemocline, the inferred absolute abundance of prokaryotic-classified cells peaked at 15 m (day 2; Fig. 3A), which corresponded with peak turbidity, POC and PON (Fig. 1). The major phyla represented at this depth were Proteobacteria (48.52%; 439,195 cells/ml) and Bacteroidetes (25.40%; 229,927 cells/ml). The genera that dominated these phyla at 15 m were purple sulfur bacteria (PSB) *Chromatium* (35.25%; 319,051 cells/ml). *Chromatium* (Proteobacteria) was significantly positively correlated with turbidity ($R=0.93$; $p\text{-value}=7.25e-05$) and total cell counts ($R=0.99$; $p\text{-value}=8.66e-09$) suggesting its significant contribution to chemocline biomass (Fig. S3). The inferred absolute abundances of an unclassified *Lentimicrobiaceae* OTU, the second most abundant OTU in the chemocline at 15 m, was significantly positively correlated with secondary production ($R=0.8$; $p\text{-value}=5.09e-03$), turbidity ($R=0.91$, $p\text{-value}=2.28e-04$, PLPs ($R=0.85$, $p\text{-value}=1.82e-03$), yet negatively correlated with light ($R=-0.78$, $p\text{-value}=7.33e-03$) and oxygen concentration ($R=-0.87$; $p\text{-value}=1.10e-03$; Fig. S3). Considering that *Lentimicrobium* species are known anaerobic fermenters¹⁴⁹, their strong correlation with secondary production and microbial biomass suggests their unknown contribution towards recycling of chemocline biomass. Furthermore, though Firmicutes was not a dominant phylum itself, an unclassified genus of the phylum, *Erysipelotrichaceae* (3.91%; 35,435 cells/ml), was among the abundant genera at 15 m (Fig. S4, Table S1). Green sulfur bacteria (GSB), *Chlorobium* (2.52% 20,849 cells/ml), was the fifth most abundant genera of chemocline. Phototrophic sulfur bacteria, *Thiocystis*, *Thiodictyon* and *Lamprocystis*, and sulfate-reducing *Desulfocapsa* and *Desulfobulbus*, previously observed in Lake Cadagno^{104,116,121}, were present at less than 0.01% of total OTUs in the chemocline (Table S1).

On average, the total PLP counts in the monimolimnion (17.0-19.0 m) were less than half that of the peak chemocline counts and more than twice the average mixolimnion counts (Fig. 2A). The average relative and inferred (Fig. 3A-B) abundances of the dominant populations reflected those of the chemocline at 15 m, which included Proteobacteria (34.05% of total OTUs; 148,019 cells/ml), Bacteroidetes (24.65%; 107,165 cells/ml), Cyanobacteria (13.51% of total OTUs; 58,726 cells/ml), and Actinobacteria (5.84%; 25,425 cells/ml). In addition to bacteria, archaeal OTUs of the *Methanoregula* and *Woesearchaeia* genera were identified in the monimolimnion, but in low abundances (<1000 cells/ml, Table S1), which may be partially attributed to primer bias against archaea in the 16S rRNA gene V4 amplification performed^{150,151}.

Phytoplankton in the mixolimnion, chemocline, and monimolimnion

Cyanobacteria were consistently among the abundant phyla at each depth, but at no depth did they dominate (Fig. 3A). Within this phylum, *Oxyphotobacteria* and chloroplast-classified OTUs dominated the Cyanobacteria, representing 94-100% of the total Cyanobacteria-classified OTUs (Fig. 4A). Of the low abundance cyanobacterial genera, *Cyanobium* was found throughout the water column, while *Pseudanabaena* and *Gastranaerophilales* were predominantly found at 15 m and deeper (Fig. 4A-B). To better understand the relationship between the microbial guilds of Lake Cadagno, we sought phylogenetic evidence to support the origin of these putative chloroplast OTUs, as per previous literature^{152,153}. The phylogeny of all Cyanobacteria-classified OTUs and their two nearest neighbours in SILVA¹⁵⁴ indicated that the chloroplast and *Oxyphotobacteria* OTUs clustered in clades with chloroplast 16S rRNA genes of cultured eukaryotic algae (Fig. 4B): Chlorophyta (Otu00008, Otu000342, Otu00006, Otu00323), Ochrophyta (Otu00033), Streptophyta (Otu00208), Haptophyta (Otu00143), and uncultured-chloroplasts (Otu00042, Otu00051, Otu00052, Otu00055).

In the lower mixolimnion between 7.0-11.0 m, where high oxygen, Chl *a*, and NPP persisted and peak Fv/Fm was observed (Fig. 1D, F), Otu00008, which is most closely related to the chloroplast of cultured Chlorophyta, *Ankyra judayi*, dominated the subset of Cyanobacteria-classified OTUs where they represented up to 89.97% of the total cyanobacterial OTUs of mixolimnion (Fig. 4B,D). At 11.0 m, the next most abundant OTUs were Otu00042 and

Otu00055, which belonged to a clade of chloroplasts from uncultured organisms, representing 21.53% and 31.63% of the total cyanobacterial OTUs, respectively.

A primary chlorophyll peak was identified in the chemocline between 13.0-14.0 m, where FCM-based counts of phycobilin-containing cells (309,333 cells/ml; Fig. 4C), phycocyanin pigments (26 µg/L day 2, Fig. 1D), and Chl *a* pigments (45 µg/L day 2) rose sharply (day 2; Fig. 1D). While Cyanobacteria-classified OTUs represented nearly a quarter of all OTUs at the primary chemocline chlorophyll peak, they represented only 7.30% of the total OTUs at the secondary chemocline chlorophyll peak (15 m; Table S1). The most abundant chloroplast OTU throughout the chemocline, Otu00006, was most closely related to the chloroplasts of cultured Chlorophyta, *Parachlorella kessleri* and *Closteriopsis acicularis*, the latter a genus¹⁵⁵ observed in meromictic Lake Tanganyika (Fig. 5). The next most dominant chloroplast-like OTUs, Otu00033 and Otu00052, clustered with cultured Ochrophyta chloroplasts and uncultured chloroplasts, respectively (Fig. 5). In the monimolimnion, Otu00006 and Otu00033 dominated the Cyanobacteria-classified OTUs (Fig. 5), which were most closely related to Chlorophyta and Ochrophyta chloroplasts, respectively.

Figure. 4: Abundances and phylogenies of Lake Cadagno phytoplankton based on 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing and flow-cytometry. Mixolimnion samples (0-11.0 m) were collected on day 1, chemocline and monimolimnion (12.0-19.0 m) samples were collected on day 2. Abundances in panels B-C are acquired by scaling 16S rRNA gene read counts by FCM cell counts. (A) Inferred concentrations (cells/ml) of OTUs assigned to the phylum Cyanobacteria, and of those, the (B) Inferred concentrations (cells/ml) of OTUs classified as putative chloroplasts and non-chloroplast at the genus level. (C) Depth profile of phycobilins-containing cell counts based on flow cytometry with a 640 nm laser. The high O₂ mixolimnion, mid O₂ mixolimnion, low O₂ mixolimnion-chemocline transition zone, chemocline, lower-chemocline, and anoxic monimolimnion layers are indicated by light green, dark green, light-lilac, lilac, dark lilac and light brown backgrounds, respectively.

Phylogram with manual bootstrapping (Only values >80)

Figure 5: Phylogenetic tree of the representative 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequences of putative chloroplast and non-chloroplast OTUs in panel B assigned as Cyanobacteria, along with their two nearest neighbour sequences from the SILVA database. Clades are colour-coded consistent with the colouring of bar plots in Fig. 4B panel.

Prokaryotic genotypic and phenotypic diversity trends

Bacterial genotypic diversity (16S rRNA gene) and PLP phenotypic diversity (based on individual cell features distinguished by FCM⁹⁸) both dropped at 7.0 m and rose in the lower mixolimnion where oxygenic primary production peaked (Fig. 6A-B, Fig. 1F). Overall, genotypic alpha diversity (Shannon) trends were near-uniform, except at the peak of turbidity

(15.0 m) where PLP phenotypic alpha diversity peaked and moderate genotypic alpha diversity was observed (Fig. 6A-B). Below the chemocline, consistently high genotypic and phenotypic alpha diversity was observed in the anoxic monimolimnion (Fig. 6). The increases in genotypic and phenotypic alpha diversity in the lower chemocline and monimolimnion were consistent with previous 16S rRNA gene-based studies on Lake Cadagno ¹⁰⁹, and other permanently stratified systems, including Powell Lake ¹⁵⁶, Ursu Lake ¹⁵⁷, and Fara Fund Lake ¹⁵⁷. Given the evidence that in microbial ecology “*diversity begets diversity*” ¹⁵⁸, the observed increase in substrate diversity in the lower chemocline and monimolimnion (Fig. 1) likely facilitated greater microbial functional diversity, such as the reported anaerobic methane oxidation and phosphorus recycling ^{20,128}. In addition, the increased particulate matter (Fig. 1) may have created greater habitat heterogeneity, which in turn would also presumably lead to greater community diversity. Finally, it is also possible that the high diversity in the monimolimnion may have been partially attributed to the accumulation of sinking cells from the mixolimnion and chemocline, which may or may not still be living, but contribute to community diversity measures.

In the Principal Coordinate Analysis (PCoA) ordinations of bacterial community dissimilarity (Bray Curtis), the first two components combined accounted for 76.9% and 46.2% of all observed variation in genotypic and phenotypic beta diversity, respectively (Fig. 6C-D). When both genotypic and phenotypic diversity was considered, the oxic mixolimnion and the co-clustering anoxic chemocline and monimolimnion samples separated along the first axis (Fig. 6C-D). In the phenotypic diversity ordination (Fig. 6D), the mixolimnion samples separated along the second axis by whether they originated from the high-oxygen (1.0-7.0 m, light green) or the mid-oxygen (8.0-11.0 m, dark green) zones (Fig. 6C-D). As with phenotypic alpha diversity, oxygen and light were negatively correlated with phenotypic and genotypic beta diversity (Fig. S3).

Figure. 6: Trends in microbial community genotypic (16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing, including prokaryotic and chloroplast-related OTUs) and phenotypic (PLP features based on flow-cytometry⁹⁸) alpha and beta diversity in Lake Cadagno. (A) Variation in genotypic alpha diversity (Shannon) with depth. (B) Variation in PLP phenotypic alpha diversity (Shannon). Mixolimnion samples (0-11.0 m) were collected on day 1, chemocline and monimolimnion (12.0-19.0 m) samples were collected on day 2. Colours of data points represent depth strata sampled. (C) PCoA represents the genotypic beta diversity dissimilarity (Bray Curtis) of microbial communities. (D) PCoA represents phenotypic beta diversity dissimilarity (Bray Curtis distance) of microbial communities.

Discussion

In this study, the investigation of viral, microbial and biogeochemical spatial dynamics through Lake Cadagno's water column improves our understanding of how biological and geochemical connections between the spatially segregated food webs in the Proterozoic Ocean model may have manifested^{14,20,22,24}.

Eukaryotic algae associated with oxygenic phototrophy in the mixolimnion

With the major transition to an oxygenated ocean 800-700 Ma, the ever-reducing levels of toxic sulfide and relief of nitrogen limitations likely facilitated the evolution of modern eukaryote precursors, as proposed in the Proterozoic Ocean model^{14,15}. In the oxic mixolimnion of Lake Cadagno, we observed low levels of sulfur and ammonia in combination with high abundances of eukaryotic algal chloroplast OTUs and photosynthetic activity, simultaneously with the low abundances of small (<40 µm) prokaryotic-like particles. These patterns reflected the conditions predicted during the early period of eukaryotic evolution in the Proterozoic Ocean (Fig. 7A). The chloroplast sequences identified in the mixolimnion were dominated by close relatives of the freshwater chlorophyte, *Ankyra judayi* (OTU00008; Fig. 7B), which has not yet been described in Lake Cadagno. This first report of *Ankyra judayi* in Lake Cadagno may reflect the dearth of studies focussing on eukaryotic phytoplankton composition of Lake Cadagno mixolimnion, especially those using modern molecular techniques. Likely due to its ability to endure high UV radiation, *Ankyra judayi* has been observed to outcompete other phytoplankton

and grow to high densities in a high-alpine Andean lake ¹⁵⁹, which may explain the evidence for its presence in the sun-lit mixolimnion in the month of August (peak seasonal temperature ¹¹⁵) of high-alpine Lake Cadagno and may reflect traits of early photosynthesizing eukaryotes. Our findings are consistent with prior microscopy-based studies reporting that the majority of the algal biomass was attributed to eukaryotic algae in the Lake Cadagno mixolimnion ¹³⁸. Moreover, eukaryotes also persisted in anoxic zone (15-19 m), however, Fv/Fm data suggested that they were not photosynthetically active and their presence may be explained by settling from photic zones. These observations of the Lake Cadagno mixolimnion provides one possible model for the period of early evolution of eukaryotes in the oxic strata of the Proterozoic Ocean, where, though spatially segregated, they may have co-occurred with abundant and productive chemocline and monimolimnion bacteria.

Revisiting the microbial linkages between *in situ* oxygen production and anoxygenic processes in the chemocline

The processes of the major microbial oxygenic and anoxygenic guilds have been reported to contribute almost equally to organic matter production in the Lake Cadagno chemocline ¹³⁸, as they may have in ancient ocean chemoclines. We observed the coexistence of oxygenic (chlorophytes, diatoms, cyanobacteria) and anoxygenic phototrophs (PSB and GSB) in the Lake Cadagno chemocline (Fig. 7C-E); however, unlike previously concluded ^{109,115}, cyanobacterial 16S amplicon reads were rare, while those of chloroplasts of chlorophytes and stramenopiles were abundant in this study. The presence of chlorophytes and stramenopiles in the Lake Cadagno chemocline were consistent with previous studies that indicated *in-situ* oxygen production by photosynthetic algae and diatoms ^{114,160}. Given that eukaryotes also contain phycobilisomes ¹⁶¹ and the abundance of chloroplast 16S rRNA reads of eukaryotic algae observed here, we propose that previous conclusions that attributed phycobilin-based cell counts to cyanobacterial blooms ^{109,115} be revisited. Future studies should investigate the relative contribution of cyanobacteria and eukaryotic phytoplankton to oxygenic photosynthesis in the chemocline.

Besides oxygenic and anoxygenic primary production, aerobic respiration has also been proposed to be coupled with biogeochemical processes of the ancient ocean chemocline ¹⁴. However, evidence for which microbes are associated with such activity in Proterozoic analogs

is sparse. Though typically thought for its role in photoautotrophy, *Chromatium*, the dominant chemocline microbe in this study, is also known to perform light-independent chemolithoautotrophy and has been reported to contribute up to 40% of total dark carbon fixation through aerobic sulfide oxidation¹¹⁴ (Fig. 7L). In that study, aerobic respiration by *Chromatium okenii* co-occurred with *in-situ* production of oxygen by photosynthetic algae¹¹⁴, methane oxidation by methanotrophs and iron oxidation likely by *Chlorobium* and *Rhodobacter*, where iron oxidation accounted for 10% of total primary production in the chemocline^{127,160} (Fig. 7H). Through their oxygen production, the oxygenic phototrophs (chlorophytes, diatoms, cyanobacteria) observed in the chemocline may play a critical role by enabling these oxidative metabolic processes central to Lake Cadagno's biogeochemical cycling. These observations indicate that the ancient purple sulfur bacteria may have likely adapted the aerobic metabolism with the rise in oxygenic phototrophs following great oxygenation event, and support the proposal of a mixed community of oxygenic and anoxygenic primary producers in the chemocline of Proterozoic Ocean model¹⁴. Future work targeting the ecological and metabolic interactions between chlorophytes, diatoms, cyanobacteria and chemocline bacteria at the oxic-anoxic interface of Lake Cadagno will improve our understanding of the evolution of life in ancient oceans.

Potential for nitrogen metabolism by phototrophic sulfur bacteria and photosynthetic microbial eukaryotes in Proterozoic Oceans

The nitrogen cycle likely mediated by N₂ fixing cyanobacteria and purple and green sulfur bacteria has been proposed to provide inorganic nitrogen essential for ancient ocean photoautotrophy^{14,24}. The shift of oxygenic to anoxygenic photosynthesis observed in this study was coincident with a decreasing efficiency of oxygenic photosynthetic microbes (Fv/Fm), increasing concentrations of hydrogen sulfide, and a shift in bacterial abundance and beta diversity (Fig. 7F). Amongst the anoxygenic phototrophic sulfur bacteria, *Chromatium okenii* has been found to perform >80% of average bulk N₂ fixation²⁴ and 40% of ammonia uptake¹⁰⁷ in the chemocline of Lake Cadagno. The highest abundance of *Chromatium* at the peak of PON and turbidity observed here, suggested the potential for on-going N-fixation and nitrogen assimilation in the Lake Cadagno chemocline. In addition to *Chromatium*, other phototrophic purple sulfur bacteria (*Lamprocystis*, and *Thiodictyon*) and green sulfur bacteria (*Chlorobium*) are also capable

of nitrogen fixation and assimilation ^{24,107,136}. These genera are also observed in this study but in low abundances as compared to *Chromatium*. While N₂ fixation is important, ammonia assimilation has been considered to be the major N source, capable of sustaining ~80% of autotrophic carbon fixation in the Lake Cadagno chemocline ²⁴. The eukaryotic phytoplankton observed in this study may also be capable of nitrogen assimilation ¹⁶², however, direct evidence for this in Lake Cadagno is lacking. Overall, the diazotrophic purple (*Chromatium*, *Lamprocystis*, and *Thiodictyon*) and green (*Chlorobium*) sulfur bacteria, along with the microbial eukaryotes (Chlorophytes), may have assimilated the upwardly diffusing ammonia and facilitated the nitrogen needed for organic matter production (POC, PON, PS) in the Lake Cadagno chemocline (Fig. 7G). Such relief from nitrogen limitation may have supported the persistence of PSB, GSB, and Chlorophytes in the permanently stratified Proterozoic Ocean ^{30,163}.

Figure. 7: Microbial loop of meromictic Lake Cadagno. Microbiology icons created with BioRender.com.

Nutrient remineralization through secondary production contributes to chemocline biomass

While broadly recognized that the PSB and GSB that dominated the Lake Cadagno chemocline in this study are known to be largely responsible for anoxygenic primary production in this stratum (Fig. 7E) ^{104,112}, we found that, as with primary production, secondary production rates, reported here for the first time, were the highest in the chemocline, exceeding secondary production in the mixolimnion and monimolimnion by 42.4- and 1.9-fold, respectively (Fig. 7I). Here we estimated that the N generated by secondary production can contribute on average $8.05\% \pm 1.06$ of the autotrophic N demand in the chemocline, while N₂ fixation has been reported to support up to 7.3% (Phillipi et al 2021). In summary, the observations of peak secondary production in the zone of greatest biomass suggested that remineralization is important for supplying nutrients to the active chemocline microbial assemblage.

By pairing these secondary production rates with a description of heterotrophic populations present, we shed light on the clades that may be involved in nutrient remineralization in the chemocline. *Lentimicrobium*, was the second most abundant genus in this study and has been previously implicated in fermentation under a limited light and oxygen ¹⁴⁹. Sulfate-reducing bacteria (SRBs, Fig. 7J), such as the observed *Desulfocapsa* and *Desulfobulbus*, are known to form aggregates with phototrophic PSB (e.g., *Thiodictyon syntrophicum*, *Lamprocystis purpurea*) and both co-occurred in the chemocline ^{116,164,165}. Through secondary production, heterotrophic microbes are likely involved in the decomposition of particulate organic matter (POC, PON) and particulate sulfur (PS) and the supply of inorganic nutrients necessary to carry out primary production by and sustaining populations of oxygenic and anoxygenic photoautotrophs in the chemocline (Fig. 7K). Trends in putative autotrophic and heterotrophic population abundances combined with the secondary productivity rates provide evidence for microbial potential towards recycling of organic matter proposed in the Proterozoic Ocean model ^{14,20,22,24}.

Potential for the role of viruses in modulating microbial activity and nutrient cycling

Viruses serve as top-down controls on host populations and reprogram host metabolism during infection ^{50,54,166}. Evidence for viral activity has been observed in ancient cyanobacterial

mat analogues, including their potential for resource scavenging through the degradation of host phycobilisomes, a pigment central to photosynthesis ¹⁶⁷. The observed colocalization of high VMR and photosynthetically active phytoplankton in the lower mixolimnion and mixolimnion-chemocline transition may be explained by ongoing lytic viral infections of phytoplankton. Viral lysis products may contribute to the DOC peak and support the high secondary production near the DCM (Fig. 7L). Such a scenario was observed in the phytoplankton *Ostreococcus* virus-host system, where host densities were maintained concurrently with continual lysis due to phase switching between resistant and susceptible hosts ¹⁶⁸. If this scenario is occurring, the sustained lysis of phytoplankton has the potential to release DOC in a viral shunt near the mixolimnion-chemocline transition. A DOC peak was indeed observed slightly below this depth in Lake Cadagno. However, given that VMR is a feature that emerges from a number of underlying virus-microbe interactions, viral life-history traits, and environmental co-factors ¹⁶⁹, the prediction of sustained phytoplankton viral predation at the mixolimnion-chemocline transition requires empirical confirmation.

Previous studies have identified genomic evidence for viral infection of the presumed major carbon assimilators in the chemocline, *Thiodictyon syntrophicum*, and *Chromatium okenii* ¹⁰⁴. Genomes of these organisms sequenced from Lake Cadagno contain CRISPR elements ^{113,119}, which derive from a type of acquired immunity against invading viral and plasmid DNA. This suggests viruses may play a role in the modulation of carbon and sulfur cycles, as has been proposed in the hydrothermal vent ¹⁷⁰ and wetland ¹⁷¹ microbial communities, where viruses have been found to carry genes central to methanogenesis (*mcrA*) and sulfur reduction (*dsrA*, *dsrD*). Active viral lysis also provides a new possible mechanism to explain the observed low abundances of *Chromatium okenii*, which has previously been attributed to microbial predation ¹⁰⁷. Despite genomic evidence suggesting active infection of these populations ^{113,119}, VLP counts did not rise with PLP counts in the chemocline. Yet, our observation of minimum VMR (Fig. 7M) and peak microbial abundances in the Lake Cadagno chemocline supported an emerging trend in stratified meromictic lakes, as the same observation was made in meromictic Ace Lake (Vestfold Hills of East Antarctica) ⁵. Such coincident low VMR and high microbial abundances have been recognized as a hallmark of the power-law relationship proposed to describe the VMR dynamics in aquatic systems ¹⁶⁹. We propose viruses as an important component of the Proterozoic Ocean microbial community. Population-specific studies of viral infection are

needed in Lake Cadagno to understand the impact of viruses on the evolution and function of microbes that underlie its biogeochemistry and to shed light on the roles viruses may have played in the ancient ocean.

Conclusion

This work highlights how biogeochemical exchange within microbial guilds may be driving biomass accumulation to support the food web of the permanently stratified Lake Cadagno. Ultimately, the organic matter generated through eukaryotic and bacterial activity and viral remineralization in the chemocline can be made available to zooplankton and fish. The collective microbial biomass including viruses will eventually sink to the sediments contributing to the organic matter burial (Fig. 7N)^{121,172}. The observed trends suggest a high degree of interconnectedness and ecological importance of microbial guilds in stratified ancient oceans.

This study inspires future research directions towards a better ecological and biogeochemical understanding of Lake Cadagno and similar meromictic ancient ocean analogues. Our community composition and secondary production data suggested that the ecological role and metabolic potential of heterotrophic bacteria that recycle chemocline biomass in the presence of sulfur and ammonia, such as second most abundant *Lentimicrobium* and their potential towards recycling chemocline biomass, were intriguing unknowns. Furthermore, eukaryotic phytoplankton has been known to contribute to the deep chlorophyll maximum of Lake Cadagno's chemocline for two decades¹³⁸, yet insights into the cellular machinery that allows them to photosynthesize under limited light remain unknown. Further, while primary producers (phytoplankton, phototrophic sulfur bacteria) and heterotrophic bacteria are central to the realized function of the lake biogeochemistry and ecology, viruses may shuffle the repertoire of genes controlling both microbial guilds, hence modulating biogeochemical (carbon, nitrogen and sulfur) cycles of the lake. Future work will build on from our empirical observations to better understand the role that microbes of the chemocline (oxic-anoxic boundary) may have played in the Proterozoic transition from primarily anoxygenic to oxygenic metabolisms that dominate nutrient biogeochemical cycling in modern oceans^{14,173,174}.

Methodology

Water-sample collection and physicochemical profiling

This study was conducted in Lake Cadagno (21 m deep), a high alpine meromictic lake situated at 1921 m above sea level in the Southern Alps of Switzerland¹⁷⁵. Due to the extensive number of samples collected and experiments performed for process measurements, sampling was collected over two subsequent days. The oxic mixolimnion (0-10 m) was sampled on 28 August (day 1), and the chemocline (11-16 m) and monimolimnion (17-19 m) were sampled on 29 August 2017 (day 2). Internal waves are known to affect the position of Lake Cadagno's stratified water masses, though their frequency is unknown¹⁴⁷. To control for this anticipated variability, a number of parameters are collected on both days to identify the depths of the zones, guiding the sampling of mixolimnion on day 1 and chemocline and monimolimnion on day 2. Water sampling and characterization of physical (turbidity, temperature, oxygen, conductivity), biological (Chl *a*, phycocyanin) and chemical (H₂S, NH₄⁺) parameters of the water column were performed as previously described¹³⁷. Water was sampled using a double diaphragm teflon pump (Almatech PSG Germany GmbH) connected to acid-washed low-density polyethylene (LDPE) line deployed from a platform that was anchored above the deepest part of the Lake Cadagno (46.55087° N, 8.71152° E).

Vertical lake profiles were determined using an autonomous conductivity temperature depth sensor (CTD; Ocean Seven 316 Plus CTD; IDRONAUT, S.R.L.). The CTD recorded pressure (dbar), temperature (°C), and conductivity (mS/cm); dissolved oxygen (mg/L) was measured with a pressure-compensated polarographic sensor. The error in oxygen profiles for day two was manually adjusted by referring to day 1 measurements which indicated approximately zero oxygen within and below chemocline. CTD profiles from the whole water column (0-20 m, day 1 and 2) were used to identify the distribution of the mixolimnion, chemocline and monimolimnion and guided water sampling strategy. The CTD was equipped with an LI-192 Underwater Quantum Sensor (Li-Cor Biosciences; NE, USA) that continuously recorded photosynthetically active radiation (PAR-W/m²) and a TriLux multi-parameter algae sensor (Chelsea Technologies Ltd; Surrey, UK) that measured in-vivo Chl *a* (µg/L), an indicator of phytoplankton (including eukaryotic autotrophs and cyanobacteria) biomass¹⁷⁶, and

phycocyanin ($\mu\text{g/L}$), a pigment characteristic of cyanobacteria¹⁷⁷.

Chemical parameters

Dissolved compounds

Samples for the analysis of dissolved compounds (DOC) were filtered through an Acropak filter cartridge (PALL) with a $0.8\ \mu\text{m}$ pre-filter and $0.2\ \mu\text{m}$ final filter. Filters were collected in 30 mL acid-washed and pyrolyzed pyrex tubes filled to the top and supplemented with $100\ \mu\text{L}$ HCl 2M. Tubes were stored in the dark at $4^\circ\ \text{C}$ until processed (November 2017; University of the Geneva) using a Shimadzu TOC-LCPH analysis system. Blanks consisting of Milli-Q water were made and calibration was done using the standard from 0.2 to 5 ppm. Analyses of dissolved ammonium (NH_4^+) and hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) were done on-site at the Alpine Biology Centre (CBA; Piora, Switzerland) with freshly collected water samples using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (DR 3800, HACH)¹⁷⁸.

Particulate compounds

Particulate organic carbon (POC), nitrogen (PON) and particulate organic sulfur (POS) were collected by filtering 150 to 500 mL of lake water (volume necessary to begin to clog the filter) on pre-combusted 47 mm GF/F filters (5h at $550^\circ\ \text{C}$, cat. #WH1825-047, Whatman, Wisconsin, USA), which were then acidified ($500\ \mu\text{L}$ HCL 1 M, added twice at 1 h interval) and dried in an oven ($65^\circ\ \text{C}$) overnight in acid-washed pyrex petri dishes. Samples were sealed using parafilm and aluminium foil until analysis (November 2017, University of Geneva) using an Elemental Analyzer (2400 series II CHNS/O Elemental Analysis, PerkinElmer). Procedural blanks using MilliQ water were performed (24-25 November 2017) in duplicate to measure the background signal, which was used to correct the concentrations of samples. POC, PON, POS were expressed in mg/L (ppm). Because purple sulfur bacteria also contain inorganic sulfur globules inside their cell^{113,165}, particulate organic sulfur (POS) is referred to as particulate sulfur (PS).

Biological parameters

Primary production

Primary productivity was determined using incubation with NaH_4CO_3 (Perkin Elmer cat.

#NEC086H005MC; Waltham, MA, USA; 5 mCi, 1 mL in glass ampoule) that was freshly diluted into 4 mL MilliQ water at pH 9.6 (adjusted using NaOH, Sigma) and added at a dose of 1 mCi/L of lake water, as described¹⁷⁹. Incubation was carried out along an incubation chain deployed at six depths for 23 h on 28-29 August 2017. Each depth consisted of a metallic ring fixed to a rope at the desired depth (3, 5, 7, 9, 11 and 13 m). The ring was surrounded by six arms on a horizontal plane, each of which ended with a bottle holder. 75 mL acid-washed glass bottles were filled to the top with lake water (ca. 100 mL) at the corresponding depth and spiked with ¹⁴C prior to being deployed on each level of the incubation chain. At each depth, three transparent bottles were incubated for activity measurements at *in situ* natural light intensities, and three amber bottles were incubated for dark community respiration measurements. At the end of the incubation, each bottle was filtered onto 47 mm GF/F filters (cat. #WH1825-047, Whatman, Wisconsin, USA) which were then stored in a plastic petri dish. Petri dishes were placed in a sealed box containing calcium hydroxide (slaked lime) powder and after adding HCl (1M, 500 µL) onto filters, inorganic carbon was degassed overnight. The calcium hydroxide captures the degassed ¹⁴C, which is further treated as solid radioactive waste. Filters were then collected into 20 ml scintillation vials, supplemented with 10 mL of Ultima Gold AB cocktail, and shaken manually. Primary productivity was expressed in µmol of net carbon fixation per h either per L of lake water or per Chl *a*, considering a dissolved inorganic carbon concentration of 1.8 mM C¹²⁰.

Maximum quantum yield

The maximum quantum yield (F_v/F_m) informs the photosynthetic health and biological activity of algae-based on photo-physiological characteristics of the chlorophyll photosystem II. Maximum quantum yield was determined using a Fast Repetition Rate Fluorometer (FRRF, FastOcean PTX coupled to a FastAct base unit; Chelsea Technologies). Water for maximum quantum yield measurements was pre-concentrated 10-fold by gently resuspending the cells as the sample passed through a 0.22 µm 47 mm polycarbonate filter (cat. #GVWP04700, Millipore; Darmstadt, Germany) using a hand pump (pressure below 15 mbar) and a 47 mm filtration unit (cat. #300-4000; Nalgene). This step was done to ensure high enough method sensitivity and has been shown to alter neither Chl *a* nor cell integrity of samples from Lake Geneva¹⁸⁰. The FRRF was used in single turnover mode to record, in a 45 min dark-adapted natural sample, the basal (F_b)

and the maximal (F_m) fluorescence following exposure to intense light. The sample was then gently filtered on a 0.22 μm 47 mm filter (cat. #GVWP04700, Millipore; Darmstadt, Germany) to record the residual fluorescence (F_r). For each sample, the $F_b - F_r$ represented the initial dark-adapted fluorescence F_0 associated with intact cells. The F_0/F_m was then calculated using the ratio: $(F_m - F_0)/F_m$.

Flow-cytometry (FCM)

Total cell counts from fresh unpreserved samples collected on-site, as well as 0.22 μm -filtered cell-free MilliQ water controls, were generated in triplicate on a BD Accuri C6 cytometer (Becton Dickinson, San José CA, USA) using two lasers (blue: 488 nm, red: 640 nm) and four fluorescence detectors (lasers 488 nm: FL1 = 533/30, FL2 = 585/40, FL3 = 670; laser 640 nm: FL4 = 675/25). Standard deviations of the triplicates were calculated to assess variations and to evaluate the potential for counting biases obtained from the flow-cytometry cell counts. FL4 detectors were specifically used to detect emission from phycobilin, a pigment proxy for cyanobacteria. Cells were stained with SYBR green I (cat. #S7563, Molecular Probes; Eugene, OR) with a ratio of 1:10,000 (vol/vol), following incubation for 13 minutes at 37°C in the dark¹²². Histogram of event counts versus green fluorescence (FL1 > 1,100) allowed quantification of total cells.

VLPs were counted using flow-cytometry¹⁸¹ after pre-filtration of lake water through 55 μm mesh to remove higher organisms such as zooplankton¹³⁸ and the lake water was subsequently passed through 0.22 μm filters to remove large particles and cells. To discern viral particles from cell-sized particles or instrument background, 0.22 μm - and 0.02 μm -filtered MilliQ water was used as cell- and virus-free controls, respectively. In triplicate, 1 ml sample from the filtrate was fixed by adding 10 μL of glutaraldehyde (25% stock solution) in sample cryovials. The samples were fixed for 15 minutes at room temperature and subsequently stored in liquid nitrogen for shipping, then stored at -80°C until they were processed in February 2018. Free virus-like particle counts were obtained using a FACSCalibur flow cytometer with 15mW 488 nm laser (Becton Dickinson Biosciences; Grenoble, France). Samples were thawed at 37 °C then diluted in autoclaved and 0.02 μm filter-sterilized Tris-EDTA (0.1 mM Tris-HCL and 1 mM EDTA, pH 8). Samples were then stained for 10 minutes at 75°C using SYBR Green I (Molecular Probes) at a 1:10,000 final concentration¹⁸². Standard deviations were calculated to

assess the potential bias resulting during VLP counting.

Phenotypic alpha diversity of PLP (Prokaryotic-like-particles)

FCM based phenotypic fingerprints have been proven to be a rapid, inexpensive, and robust method to spatially and temporally assess microbial community dynamics⁹⁸ and has been considered effective in assessing microbial diversity in aquatic systems^{95,183}. Raw flow-cytometry files were used to estimate phenotypic traits (morphology and nucleic acid content) and transformed and normalized using transform and flowBasis functions in the Phenoflow package⁹⁸ (https://github.com/rprops/Phenoflow_package) in R (v4.1.0)¹⁸⁴ and R-Studio (v1.4.1106)¹⁸⁵. Briefly, the height values of the two fluorescent parameters (FL1, FL3) and two scatter parameters (SSC, FSC) recorded for each cell were treated with a hyperbolic arcsin transformation. These phenotypic intensity values were then scaled to a 0-1 range. Each parameter was then normalized based on the average maximum FL1-H intensity value over the data set. The cytometry fingerprint represents community structure in terms of the phenotypic attributes of the cells that comprise the community—essentially, any feature that influences the way the laser interacts with passing particles, such as morphology, size, and nucleic acid content, is captured in the phenotypic fingerprint. Using this approach, prokaryotic phenotypic diversity metrics have been shown to be highly correlated with community taxonomic diversity⁹⁸. To calculate phenotypic alpha diversity, phenoflow calculates Hill number diversity indices (D_q) from order 0-2, where 0 represents the richness and $q > 1$ represents richness and evenness, also referred to as D_0 (richness), D_1 (Shannon), and D_2 (inverse Simpson)¹⁸⁶. Phenotypic beta diversity was estimated from the phenotypic feature vectors using the Bray-Curtis distance metric and the beta diversity ordination was then calculated using non-metric multidimensional scaling. Fluorescence detectors (lasers 488 nm: FL1-H = 533/30, FL3-H = 670) were used to target PLP diversity. Polygon gating was applied to filter out the noise observed in control samples (Fig. S1). Clockwise, the polygon gate coordinates (x,y) were: (7, 6), (15, 6), (15, 17), and (7,10). Kernel density estimates were calculated by applying a binning grid (128 x 128) to FSC-H (Forward scatter height), SSC-H (Side scatter height), FL1-H and FL3-H. The obtained kernel densities values were assigned into one-dimensional vectors, termed *phenotypic fingerprints*.

Secondary production

Heterotrophic bacterial production, also termed secondary production, was estimated by the micro-centrifuge ^3H -Leucine bacterial production method ¹⁸⁷. A working solution of $5 \mu\text{Ci mL}^{-1}$ leucine was made from a manufacturer stock solution of radioactive leucine, L-[3,4,5- ^3H (N)] (cat. #NET460A005MC, PerkinElmer, MA, USA). To reduce the potential for autodegradation of the leucine radiolabel, stock ^3H -Leucine material was stored in the dark at 2 to 4 °C (never frozen) and used for the incorporation experiment within 5 days. Two replicates and one trichloroacetic acid (TCA)-killed control (5% [vol/vol] final concentration; cat. 91228, Sigma) were used for each depth. Briefly, 1.5-mL of lake water samples were incubated with a mixture of radioactive and nonradioactive leucine at final concentrations of 20 nM. Using the [^3H]-Leucine working solution, enough “hot” leucine was added to each tube to create a sufficient signal (50% or 85% of hot leucine were used in the mixture for samples collected above and below 13m depths, respectively). Incubations were conducted for 2 hr in a dark incubator at *in situ* temperatures that corresponded to their sample depths. Saturation of leucine incorporation over this period was tested with 20, 30 and 40 nM of total leucine. At the end of the incubation, 200 μL of 50% TCA is added to all but the control tubes to terminate leucine incorporation. To facilitate the precipitation of proteins, bovine serum albumin (BSA; Sigma, 100 mgL^{-1} final concentration) was added, then samples were centrifuged at 16,000 g for 10 min ¹⁸⁸. The supernatant was discarded and the resultant precipitated proteins were washed with 1.5 mL of 5% TCA by vigorous vortexing and again centrifuged (16,000 g for 10 min). The supernatant was discarded. Subsequently, 1.5 mL of UltimaGold™ uLLt (Part number: 6013681, PerkinElmer, MA, USA) was added to each vial, mixed, and allowed to sit for >24 h at room temperature before the radioactivity was determined using a liquid scintillation counter (Beckman LS6500). To calculate biomass production, the following conversion factors were applied: molecular weight of leucine of 131.2 g/mol, the fraction of leucine per protein of 0.073, the ratio of cellular carbon to the protein of 0.86, and 2.22×10^6 DPM/ μCi to convert disintegrations per minute (DPMs; the measure of radioactivity) to μCi . A factor of $1.55 \text{ kg C mol leucine}^{-1}$ was used to convert the incorporation of leucine to carbon equivalents, assuming no isotope dilution ¹⁸⁹.

The contribution of remineralization towards autotrophic N demand was further

calculated using the following equations;

$$(1) \text{ Bacterial respiration (BR)} = (\text{BP} / \text{BGE}) - \text{BP}^{190} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

BR → Bacterial respiration proxy for remineralization

BP → Bacterial production

BGE → Bacterial Growth Efficiency (=0.26)¹⁹⁰

Bacterial respiration is expressed in $\text{mol C L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$

$$(2) \text{ N generated by heterotrophic bacteria} = \text{BR} / \text{C:N ratio} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

BR → Bacterial respiration proxy for remineralization

C:N ratio = Particulate organic carbon (POC) / Particulate organic nitrogen (PON)

N generated by heterotrophic bacteria is expressed in $\mu\text{mol N L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$

$$(3) \text{ Autotrophic N demand} = (\text{C fixation rate} / (\text{C:N ratio})) \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

Average C fixation rate between 13.7 to 15.5 m = $31.1 \mu\text{mol C L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$ ²⁴

C:N ratio = Particulate organic carbon (POC) / Particulate organic nitrogen (PON)

Autotrophic N demand is expressed in $\mu\text{mol N L}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$

$$(4) \text{ Contribution of N remineralization towards autotrophic growth (\%)} = \text{N generated by heterotrophic bacteria (Eq. 2)} / \text{Autotrophic N demand (Eq. 3)} = \text{N generated by heterotrophic bacteria (Eq. 2)} / \text{Autotrophic N demand (Eq. 3)}$$

Statistical Analyses

The magnitude and significance of relationships between physical and biological parameters were determined with linear regressions and visualized with scatter plots using R (v4.1.0)¹⁸⁴ in R-Studio (1.4.1106)¹⁸⁵ using ggplot2 (3.3.3)¹⁹¹ and ggpubr (0.4.0)¹⁹² packages¹⁹³. $R > 0.70$ was considered a strong positive correlation, and a p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Illumina MiSeq 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequence analyses

16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing

Water was collected from 3.0, 5.0, 7.0, 9.0, 11.0, 13.0, 15.0, 15.5, 17.0 and 19.0 m (20 L per depth). One sample from each depth was collected for 16S sequencing, representing five from

the mixolimnion, three from the chemocline, and two from the monimolimnion. As per prior studies of Lake Cadagno¹³⁸, samples were 55 µm pre-filtered to remove large particles and organisms, such as zooplankton. Using a peristaltic pump, the subsequent biomass was captured on 0.22 µm filters (cat. #GPWP14250 142 mm Express Plus Filter, Millipore; Darmstadt, Germany) as previously performed for bacterial studies in Lake Cadagno^{109,111,116,194}. Filters were flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C until extraction of DNA using the DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (cat. #69504 QIAGEN, Germantown, MD, USA) combined with QIAshredder (cat. #79654, QIAGEN, CA, USA), as described¹⁹⁵. The first elutions of DNA (50 µl each) were stored (4 °C) until sequencing. Dual indexed primers were used and the V4 region of the 16S rRNA gene amplicon was targeted and amplified, as described¹⁹⁶. Sequencing libraries were prepared using the Illumina Nextera Flex kit (Illumina; CA, USA) and sequenced using the MiSeq platform (500 cycles, Illumina) at the University of Michigan Microbiome Core facility.

The sequenced reads were quality controlled (mothur: minlength=240, maxhomop=8, maxlength=275), assembled, trimmed, aligned using SILVA v132 16S rRNA reference sequences (mothur: reference position start=1968, end=11550). Following the removal of chimeras, sequences were clustered at 97% identity into representative operational taxonomic units (OTU) using mothur¹⁹⁷. Samples that resulted in fewer than 5000 reads were re-sequenced to ensure the full profile was captured with at least two replicates per stratified zone (i.e., mixolimnion, chemocline, and monimolimnion). The OTUs were taxonomically classified using SILVA 132¹⁹⁸ and TaxAss freshwater (version 1)¹⁹⁹ 16S rRNA gene databases.

Microbial community analysis

Downstream community analysis was carried out by the phyloseq package⁹⁹ using R (4.1.0)¹⁸⁴ in R-studio (1.4.1106)¹⁸⁵ to analyze the alpha and beta genotypic diversity of prokaryotic communities. Bacterial and archaeal taxa were merged using *merge_phyloseq*. To minimize the impact of rare taxa, taxa not observed at least three times in 20% of the samples were removed using the *filter_taxa* function in phyloseq. OTU counts were transformed to relative abundance (0-1 range) by *transform_sample_counts*. OTUs were not rarefied to preserve rare OTUs for diversity analyses²⁰⁰. For genotypic beta diversity PCoA (16S amplicon data), OTU counts were

Hellinger transformed with R microbiome package (1.15.3) ²⁰¹.

To resolve the challenges associated with compositional relative abundance data ^{202,203}, “inferred absolute abundances” were calculated by multiplying relative abundances by flow-cytometry (FCM)-generated cell counts ¹⁴⁸ for each sample. Briefly, the relative abundances of prokaryotic OTUs of a given taxon (taxon read count/total read count in sample) was multiplied by the PLP concentrations (cells/ml) for that sample, as determined by flow cytometry. Scaling the 16S amplicon read counts by flow-cytometry cell counts provided a more accurate assessment of changes in microbial populations through the water column. This is most strongly demonstrated in the differences observed between Figure 3 panels A and B. When the total cell counts increase in the chemocline, the magnitude of changes in populations can be represented only when reads are scaled by cell counts (Fig. 3B).

Chloroplast 16S rRNA gene phylogeny

The Alignment, Classification, and Tree (ACT) functions of SILVA were used to generate the phylogenetic tree of the representative 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequences of putative chloroplast and non-chloroplast OTUs that had been assigned as Cyanobacteria ²⁰⁴. Representative sequences of chloroplast OTUs were aligned to the SILVA 132 sequences (SINA 1.2.11). Two neighbours per query sequence (95% minimum sequence identity) were added to the tree with the chloroplast OTU sequences. The *Advanced variability profile* was selected as ‘auto’ and sequences above 90% identity were kept in order to consider only the highest confidence, most homologous sequence. The phylogenetic tree of the OTUs was bootstrapped with RAxML (version 8) ²⁰⁵ with 20 maximum likelihood (ML) and 100 bootstrapped searches. The tree was annotated using the R package ggtree (2.2.4) ²⁰⁶ and Adobe Illustrator (25.2.1).

Data Availability

Raw sequences are deposited in the NCBI Short Read Archive (SRA) and available through the BioProject PRJNA717659. The code used for running the mothur analysis, statistical analyses, and figure generation is available at the project GitHub repository: https://github.com/DuhaimeLab/Lake_Cadagno_microbial_loop_Saini_et_al_2021.

Acknowledgements

The project was funded by Swiss National Science Foundation grant no. PP00P2-138955 and through financial support to J.S.S. from the Swiss Confederation and Ernst and Lucy Schmidheiny Foundation that graciously enabled the development of this manuscript. We thank the Duhaime Lab at the University of Michigan for supporting a learning environment to carry out the sequencing, flow cytometry, and ecological analysis and for productive feedback during the manuscript development. Many thanks to Dr Sandro Peduzzi and the Alpine Biology Center Foundation (Switzerland) for providing accommodations during Lake Cadagno sampling and for offering comments on the manuscript. The University of Michigan Microbiome Core facility aided in the generation of Lake Cadagno 16S rRNA gene data.

Supplementary Materials

Table S1. The relative abundances (OTU read count/total sample read count) and inferred abundances (relative abundances x FCM cell counts) of prokaryotic OTUs and chloroplasts.

A. Automatic Gating for PLPs counts (1m)

Figure S1. Scatterplot of flow-cytometry events visualized with BD6 flow-cytometer interface (A-B) and R-studio Phenoflow package (A-D) for one replicate of the 1 m sample. FCM events representing prokaryotic-like particles (PLPs) using (A) automatic gating via a four-quadrant layout and (B, C) manual gating. (D) FCM events in a 0.2 μm filtered, cell-free MilliQ water (control). The red outline represents the gating strategy for cell counts and phenotypic diversity analysis. This gate was applied to all samples.

Figure S2. Line plot depicting the results of the experiment to monitor the health of photosynthetic cells. Fast Repetition Rate Fluorometer was used to measure basal fluorescence (Fb; blue line) and maximum fluorescence (Fm; black line), which were then used to calculate maximum photosynthetic quantum yield (F_v/F_m ; red line), a proxy for the health of photosynthetic cells.

Figure S3. Grid and heatmap depicting the Pearson correlation R-coefficients and p-values performed between data types; strong positive correlations indicated by blue hues, strong negative correlations indicated by red, no correlation by yellow. Prefix of parameter name indicates parameter type category, (A) abundance: 16S rRNA amplicon-based relative abundances, flow-cytometry generated PLP and VLP counts, and phycobilisome-containing cell counts; (D) diversity: alpha and beta diversity calculated from 16S-based genotypic and flow

cytometry-based phenotypic Bray Curtis distance measures; (FCS) flow cytometry-derived data; (N) nutrients, including DOC, POC, PON, PS, ammonium, and sulfate; (P) physicochemical parameters from CTD, including light, conductivity, temperature, oxygen, chl a, phycocyanin, turbidity. Secondary production is included with no prefix.

Figure S4. Inferred absolute abundances of bacterial genera through the water column of meromictic Lake Cadagno. Absolute abundances are inferred by multiplying the relative abundances (OTU read count/total sample read count) by FCM cell counts.

Chapter II

Chapter II: A near-complete genome of microbial eukaryote *Chlorella* from a high alpine meromictic lake reveals its potential towards carbon, sulphur and nitrogen metabolism and its implications for Proterozoic oceans

Jaspreet S Saini, Mosè Manni, Christel Hassler, Rachel Cable, Melissa B. Duhaime, Evgeny M. Zdobnov

Submission status: **In prep.**

Contribution statement

I contributed to conceptualization, investigation, data curation, methodology, formal analysis, visualization, writing original draft and review and editing.

Partial funding acquisition

I secured the first three of my salary for this project by obtaining a Swiss Government Excellence Scholarship. Prof. Hassler supported my application for this scholarship. I reached Ernst et Lucie Schmidheiny Foundation which provided an additional 18 months of my scholarship with the support letters from Prof. Zdobnov and Prof. Duhaime.

3.2. Chapter II: A near-complete genome of microbial eukaryote *Chlorella* from a high alpine meromictic lake reveals its potential towards carbon, sulphur and nitrogen metabolism and its implications for Proterozoic oceans

Jaspreet S Saini, Mosè Manni, Christel Hassler, Rachel Cable, Melissa B. Duhaime, Evgeny M. Zdobnov

Abstract

Meromictic Lake Cadagno is a permanently stratified system that resembles the condition of a Proterozoic Ocean with the persistent microbial bloom within the chemocline. Oxygenic and anoxygenic photosynthesis have been associated for almost two decades with the chemocline. While anoxygenic purple and green sulphur bacteria have been well studied in Lake Cadagno, the reports on oxygenic phytoplankton have remained sparse since their initial discoveries in the 1920s. After 100 years of phytoplankton investigation, this study presents the first near-complete nuclear and chloroplast genomes of a photosynthetic microbial eukaryote, named *Chlorella cadagno* MAG, from the chemocline of Lake Cadagno. We also recovered an additional chloroplast genome from *Cryptomonas* species containing phycobilisomes. The small 19.25 MB *Chlorella* nuclear genome displays high GC content (71.5%). Phylogenetic placement of this microbial eukaryote suggests it is a novel species of *Chlorella* related to species *Nannochloris* and *Chlorella desiccata*. Functional annotations of the Lake Cadagno *Chlorella* genome predicted 10,888 protein-coding genes and revealed their potential for carbon, sulphur and nitrogen metabolism. This genomic evidence unravels the mystery of how a microbial eukaryote can persist in low light and oxygen with persistent exposure to hydrogen sulphide and ammonium at the lower edge of the chemocline of Lake Cadagno.

Keywords: Microbial Eukaryote, Protist, Ancient ocean, Oxic-anoxic boundary, Metagenomics, Meromictic Lake, Phytoplankton.

Introduction

Meromictic Lake Cadagno, situated at an altitude of 1921m within the Swiss Alps, resembles the conditions of the Proterozoic Ocean ²⁴. The lake is permanently stratified into three zones called mixolimnion (upper-oxic), chemocline (oxic-anoxic boundary), and monimolimnion (lower-anoxic). The chemocline harbours the persistent microbial bloom that coincides with decreased oxygen and light concentrations but increased ammonium, iron, and sulphide ^{109,110,113,116,118,126,137}. Within these physicochemical variations, the biomass of phytoplankton and phototrophic sulphur bacteria and their contrasting metabolism of oxygenic photosynthesis and anoxygenic photo-and-chemosynthesis have been associated for at least two decades ^{104,114,124,127,138,160,207}. Moreover, oxygenic photosynthesis specifically facilitates the dark aerobic sulphide oxidation ¹¹⁴ by *Chromatium okenii*—a purple sulphur bacteria also known to contribute most to the biomass of the Lake Cadagno chemocline ^{24,208}. Oxygenic photosynthesis is also coupled with methane and iron oxidation carried out by putative methane and iron-oxidising bacteria in Lake Cadagno ^{114,127,160}. Since these studies emphasised the coupling of oxygenic photosynthesis with anoxygenic photo-and-chemosynthesis, the identification of oxygenic phototrophs, including photosynthetic algae and diatoms, remains limited to microscopy ^{114,160}.

The microoxic conditions within the chemocline ¹¹⁵ have also been recently proposed to be contributed by phycobilins cells which are a proxy often used to report cyanobacteria in Lake Cadagno ^{109,115,121}. In contrast, the follow-up 16S phylogeny revealed that cyanobacteria were rare and that the chloroplasts of *Chlorophyta* and *Ochromytha* species (stramenopiles; diatoms) were abundant in the chemocline ²⁰⁷. Because both prokaryotic cyanobacteria and chloroplasts can perform oxygenic photosynthesis, this warranted genomic characterization of prokaryotic and eukaryotic phytoplankton present in the oxic-anoxic boundary.

Phytoplankton peaks (Chl *a*, Phycocyanin) are persistently reported at the upper edge of the chemocline ^{104,110,138}, the position where particulate sulphur, H₂S, particulate organic nitrogen, NH₄⁺ concentrations started rising ²⁰⁷. Sulphide is considered toxic to most eukaryotes ¹⁴ and

photosynthetic eukaryotes rely on cyanobacteria for nitrogen fixation through symbiosis²⁰⁹. Some reports have highlighted that microbial eukaryotes^{210,211} and cyanobacteria^{212,213} can use nitrogen and sulphur in their metabolism in other systems but their prospective role in sulphur and nitrogen cycling was yet to be explored for Lake Cadagno. Because of the persistence of phytoplankton in chemocline, the genomes of these photosynthetic microbes might contain genes (for example; Ammonium transporters and nitrate transporters, sulfite and sulphate reductase) that are central to sulphur and nitrogen metabolism^{214,215}.

The prokaryotic population has been rigorously studied, and genomes of anoxygenic purple sulphur bacteria (e.g. *Chromatium okenii*, *Thiodictyon syntrophicum*) capable of modulating sulphur and nitrogen metabolism are available^{113,119}. In contrast, no eukaryotic genome was previously sequenced from Lake Cadagno. This study is the first to present a near-complete genome of a photosynthetic microbial eukaryote belonging to a novel *Chlorella* species from the chemocline of Lake Cadagno. Functional annotation of the newly-discovered *Lake Cadagno Chlorella* genome provides new insights into the ability of microbial eukaryotes to thrive under almost no light and oxygen, and persistent exposures to hydrogen sulphide and ammonium in chemocline.

Results and Discuss

The Lake Cadagno chemocline was situated between 13-15.5 m, where oxygen and light reached close to zero, where peaks of phytoplankton and phototrophic sulphur bacteria were observed using photosynthetic pigments (Chl *a*, Phycocyanin) and turbidity²⁰⁷. In this report, we investigated the microbial communities of chemocline using shotgun DNA sequencing because of the prior hypotheses of *in-situ* oxygen production^{114,160} by photosynthetic algae, diatoms,^{114,160} and cyanobacteria¹¹⁵.

Figure S1 (optional): Physicochemical depth profiles on August 28-29, 2017 taken from Saini et al. 2022. The position of the chemocline was between 13.0 to 15.5 m indicated by the grey zone as described ²⁰⁷. In panel (A) Chl *a* and Phycocyanin was used as a proxy for phytoplankton, and turbidity is associated with purple and green sulphur bacteria in the chemocline of Lake Cadagno. In panel (B) Chemical profiles including H₂S, Oxygen, and Ammonium are indicated.

Mixotrophic protists modulating microbial food webs of Lake Cadagno

Within the chemocline, the contigs from metagenome assemblies ranged between 345-853 megabytes (MB) with the N50 values between 7,659-28,898 bp (Fig. S2 A-D). At 13 m where phytoplankton (Chl *a*, Phycocyanin) started to rise, only 3,469 contigs (L50) contributed

to 50% of the assembly with a minimum length of 28,898 bp (N50), indicating the presence of long contigs. Exceptional attempts were made to study the microbial eukaryotes in other systems^{216,217}, however, we had no prior reports on eukaryotic genomics of Lake Cadagno. After clustering contigs using CONCOCT⁶⁶, most of the resulting metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) belonged to the bacterial lineage with only a few microbial eukaryotic genomes (3.61 to 8.41% of total MAGs; Fig. 1A-B). This low occurrence may reflect the challenges associated with eukaryotic genome binning owing to their larger size and complexity than most prokaryotes²¹⁸. MAGs of phytoplankton, including cyanobacteria and photosynthetic microbial eukaryotes, were further scrutinised for their involvement in *in-situ* oxygen production via oxygenic photosynthesis^{114,115,160}. Typical cyanobacteria specific phycocyanin, and phycobilin signals are persistently observed (year 2013¹²¹, 2017^{109,115,207}, and 2019¹⁰⁴) in the chemocline of Lake Cadagno, however, we did not recover an assembled cyanobacterial genome (29 August 2017; Table1).

BUSCO²¹⁹ identified genomes in a wide range of completion (12.20-93.80%) for eukaryotic phytoplankton, including Chlorophyta (group Chloroplastida) and Stramenopile (Fig. 1G; [Table 1](#)). Both these photosynthetic microbial genomes were expected to be found because the chloroplast amplicons of Chlorophyta and Ochrophyta (Stramenopile) were also observed in a parallel study²⁰⁷. The 18S SSU rRNA sequences reported the dominance (>70% sequences) of Cryptophyta with around 5-10% of Perkinsozoa (Alveolata) and Stramenopiles³. However, in this study, a mixed population of microbial eukaryotes was observed which included Alveolata (4.32-13.78%), Cryptomonadales (6.05-16.16%), Obozoa (12.70-27.84%), Rhizaria (8.27-12.13%), Chloroplastida (10.72-19.48%) and Stramenopiles (5.31-26.24%) in the chemocline (Fig. 1D). Cryptophytes (Cryptomonadales), Chlorophytes (Chloroplastida), Diatoms (Stramenopiles) are Chl *a* containing phytoplankton³³ ie. potentially performing oxygenic photosynthesis in the chemocline. In addition to these phytoplankton, Cryptomonas (Cryptomonadales), Dinoflagellates and Ciliophora (Alveolata) are also known as consecutive mixoplankton (CM), which might be preying on purple sulphur and green sulphur bacteria while simultaneously also capable of autotrophy in chemocline²²⁰⁻²²². Overall, these results present a diverse population of mixotrophic protists in the chemocline capable of oxygenic photosynthesis and phagotrophy, processes which potentially contribute to both primary and secondary production of the Lake Cadagno chemocline.

Figure 1: Bacterial and eukaryotic metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) from the chemocline (13-15.5 m depth) of Lake Cadagno. 15-w represents a whole water sample (without 55 μm mesh). Panel (A, B) depicts the number and size of bacterial and eukaryotic MAGs classified using CONCOCT and CAT-BAT taxonomy (hits >0.5 bit-scores). Panel (C) highlights

BUSCO assessment of microbial eukaryotes showing only MAGs with >10% completion. Panel (D) Eukaryotic community classification using SSU rRNA sequences by Phyloflash.

Figure S2: Overview of four metagenomics samples collected between 13-15.5 m depth of Lake Cadagno's chemocline, where 15-w represents a whole water sample (without 55 μ m mesh). Panel A-D summarises stats from SPAdes assemblies, including size (A), average GC content (B), number of contigs (C), and respective N50/L50 values.

A newly-discovered photosynthetic eukaryotic genome belongs to a novel species of *Chlorella*

Due to the large size and complexity of eukaryotes, obtaining their well-curated genome from metagenomes remains a challenging task²²³ and warrants the publication like “*More protist genome needed*”²²⁴. In this study, after the manual curation of Chlorophyta MAG, the final

genome of 19.25 Mb containing a total of 701 contigs (minimum length: 2'500 bp) was recovered, which had an average GC content of 71.5%. The refining process resulted in a decrease in the total number of contigs and an increase in the contribution of long contigs (total contigs= 701, 17>100KB, 116>50KB, and 275>25KB) when compared to the best quality MAG before refinement (13m_164, total contigs= 1232, 3>100KB, 48>50KB, and 212>25KB) (Fig. 2A). Interestingly, Chlorophyta MAG had higher coverage (48.53x) and relative abundance (4.62%) than *Chromatium* MAG at the beginning of the chemocline (12.63x, 1.29% at 13 m). *Chromatium okenii* dominates the chemocline in biomass ^{24,113,208}, and its relative abundance peaked in the anaerobic whole water sample (6.84% at 15-w). The increase in coverage of Chlorophyta MAG followed by dominance of *C. okenii* was expected as phytoplankton tends to stay above the phototrophic sulphur bacteria, observed by the peak of Phycocyanin, Chl *a* and turbidity ²⁰⁷. Comparatively, maximum mean coverage and relative abundance (27.82x, 0.85% at 15.5 m) of green sulphur bacteria *Chlorobium* MAG was still lower than refined *Chlorophyta* MAG and *Chromatium* MAG (Fig. 2B-C), consistent with the 16S sequencing indicating low *Chlorobium* amplicons (2-6%) of the total fraction ^{24,207}, even though GSBs are the dominant population in terms of cell number ^{104,109}.

Figure 2: Statistics on Chlorophyta MAG from Lake Cadagno water column, i.e. mixolimnion (5, 9, 11 m), chemocline (13, 15, 15-w, 15.5 m) and monimolimnion (17 m). Visualisation of refined Chlorophyta MAG using Blobtools and R-studio ggplots. (A) Snail plot divided into 1,000 size-ordered bins around the circumference, with each bin representing 0.1% of the 19,253,842 bp assembly (220,241 bp, shown in red). Orange and pale-orange arcs indicate N50 and N90 values where the longest scaffold is displayed in red, respectively. (B-C) Bowtie 2 and Samtools based respective number of reads (log) and mean depth coverage of MAGs including purple (*Chromatium*, 13m_206) and green (*Chlorobium*, 15m_20) sulphur bacteria along with refined *Chlorella*. (D) Relative abundance of MAGs obtained using CoverM. (E) A hexagon-binned plot of GC content and coverage based on mapping with refined *Chlorella* specific raw reads obtained from samples with high N50 values (13 and 15.5 m). (F) Taxonomic classification of Chlorophyta MAG calculated via Diamond Blastx nr database (updated 24 July 2021).

At least 95% of the contigs of Chlorophyta MAG belonged to the *Chlorellaceae* according to Diamond blastx against the nr database (Fig. 2F). The phylogenomics tree indicated that *Chlorella* MAG represents a novel genome (referred to as *Chlorella cadagno* MAG; Fig. 3A) illustrating close to the small genomes of *nannochloris* and *chlorella dessicata* species (Fig. 3A). *Chlorella cadagno* MAG is likely to be the ancestral lineage of *nannochloris* and *chlorella dessicata* and had contrastingly higher GC content when compared to the nearest neighbours (Fig. 3C; 71.50 vs 40-45). The microscopic pictures of closest relatives (species from Chlorellaceae) indicated that *Chlorella cadagno* MAG belonged to the nanophytoplankton community²²⁵ (2–20 μm) (Fig. 3B). *Chlorella cadagno* MAG exhibited high quality when its genome completion of 95.5% [95.2% single-copy, 0.35% duplicated, 0.9% missing, and 3.6% fragmented] was compared with the mean genome completion of the family (91.24 %, Fig. 3D). These findings recover the first extensively curated high-quality eukaryotic genome from the chemocline of meromictic Lake Cadagno.

Figure 3: Comparative analyses of *Chlorella cadagno* MAG with relatives from the Chlorrellaceae family (NCBI ID 35461). (A) Phylogenomic tree of *Chlorella cadagno* MAG with other species from the Chlorrellaceae family (NCBI ID 35461). The maximum likelihood phylogeny of a super-alignment (40'847 aa) of 90 single-copy orthologs. *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* is an outgroup species. Branch lengths represent substitutions per site. Values on nodes indicate bootstrap support. (B) Pictures of chlorella species taken from the culture collection of algae and protozoa ²²⁶ (C) Size and GC content comparison (D) BUSCO quality assessment using chlorophyta_odb10 dataset (number of markers=1519).

Genomic evidence of *Chlorella* and *Cryptomonas* chloroplasts contributing to oxygenic photosynthesis in the chemocline

Previous studies reported the possibilities of cyanobacteria in the chemocline of Lake Cadagno based on a phycocyanin, and phycobilins signals^{109,115,121} but 16S gene phylogeny identified chloroplasts²⁰⁷. Nevertheless, the study was limited to amplicon data. This metagenomics dataset also didn't recover an assembled cyanobacteria genome, and further provided evidence for *Cryptomonas* using 18S sequences and MAGs (Table 1, Table 2) which are known for phycobilisomes^{161,227} and also previously identified in Lake Cadagno¹³⁸. Therefore, while identifying the respective chloroplast genome of new identified *Chlorella*, we also targeted *Cryptomonas* chloroplasts. Using preexisting Chloroplast genomes of *Chlorella* (*Parachlorella kessleri*) and *Cryptomonas* (*Guillard theta*) from NCBI, Blastn identified two prospective chloroplast contigs with at least 100KB size termed as Chloroplast A (cpA) and Chloroplast B (cpB). Followed by circularization of cpA and cpB using NOVOPlasty, phylogenetics analysis confirmed that these prospective chloroplasts belonged to *Chlorella* and *Cryptomonas* species (Fig. 4A).

Chlorella chloroplast (cpA) coverage and the number of reads (log) peaked in the chemocline, and persisted in the monimolimnion, a pattern also matching the nuclear genome (Fig. 2D-F, Fig. 4B). Comparing the mean coverage depth of nuclear and chloroplast genome (vs 35.92 vs 55.93x, Fig. 2C, Fig. 4B) in chemocline, each *Chlorella* cell is likely to have one chloroplast—a typical case for eukaryotic algae²²⁸. Simultaneously, *Cryptomonas* chloroplast (cpB) coverage and read patterns coincided with the phycobilisomes containing cells that also peaked in the chemocline (Fig. 4C)²⁰⁷. The genes coding for these photosynthetic reaction centres (PSI *psa* and PSII *psb*) were present in both chloroplasts of *Chlorella* (cpA) and *Cryptomonas* (cpB). However, phycobilisome-specific phycoerythrin protein (*cpeB*) was only found in *Cryptomonas* chloroplast and phycoerythrin has also been previously identified for *Cryptomonas* of Lake Cadagno¹³⁸ (Fig. 4 D,E). Cyanobacteria was reported in Lake Cadagno by targeting phycocyanins^{109,115,121}. Contrastingly, we didn't recover phycocyanin genes in chloroplasts of *Cryptomonas*, although phycoerythrin is attached to the phycocyanins and are part of the overall structure of phycobilisome structure²²⁹⁻²³². Briefly, the phylogenetic tree, coverage, and read pattern provide a piece of robust evidence that cpA and cpB are representative chloroplast genomes of *Chlorella* and *Cryptomonas*. Overall, genomics evidence suggests that these chloroplasts contributed to the persistent *Chl-a* peak while *Cryptomonas*

potentially possessed phycobilisomes, which were presumed to have cyanobacterial origin in Lake Cadagno chemocline ^{109,115}.

Figure 4: Phylogenomic of representative chloroplast genomes of *Chlorella* and *Cryptomonas* assembled using NOVOPlasty ²³³. (A) Phylogenomics tree based on 18 marker genes including ATP synthase (atpA, atpB, atpC), large and small ribosomal proteins (rpl2, rpl5, rpl12, rpl14, rpl19, rpl23, rps3, rps8, rps9, rps19), photosystem I and II (psa C, psb A, psbB, psbE, psbH). The tree was generated using MEGA with maximum likelihood calculated by jones-taylor-thornston (JTT) model along bootstrapping (n=100). (C, D) Circularised chloroplasts (cpA, cpB) genomes were annotated using GeSeq ²³⁴ (B, E) Chloroplast (cpA, cpB) coverage, and the number of reads

(log) was calculated throughout the water column of Lake Cadagno using Bowtie 2 and SAMtools.

Integrated carbon, sulphur and nitrogen metabolism in Lake Cadagno Chlorophyte and its implication for Proterozoic Oceans

Chlorophytes are one of the oldest eukaryotic microbial lineages, and their origin can be traced back to sulphide-rich Proterozoic Oceans^{30,131}. The contribution of PSB and GSB towards carbon, sulphur and nitrogen metabolism has been rigorously studied^{24,104,113–115,119–121,136,138}. On the contrary, metabolism of Chlorophyte or a microbial eukaryote is yet to be demonstrated for Lake Cadagno. In this study, EukMetaSanity²³⁵ based on AUGUSTUS²³⁶ and Metaeuk²³⁷ predicted a total of 10,888 protein-coding genes for *Chlorella cadagno* MAG (Fig. S2A). Functional annotations of this genome indicated KEGG pathways involved in carbon [M00165, M00166, M00167, M00168, M00169, M00170, M00171, M00172, M00579], nitrogen [M00615, M00531], and sulphur [M00176] metabolism (Table 3). The coverage of these pathways is almost zero in the mixolimnion and maximum in the chemocline, which further persisted in the monimolimnion (Fig. 5). Amongst these C,N,S pathways, C3 photosynthesis [M00165, M00166, M00167, M00579], Crassulacean acid metabolism [M00168, dark], and assimilatory sulphate reduction [M00179] had the highest completion, whereas, C4 photosynthesis [M00170, M00171, M00172], nitrate assimilation [M00615] had the low pathway completion. The low pathway completion is likely because of the gene loss which may have evolutionary basis, and can also be because of technological reasons such as failure of capturing genes using sequencing.

The C3 and C4 pathways are hallmarks of photosynthesis^{238,239} while crassulacean acid metabolism (CAM) is specialised to uptake CO₂ in dark and increases the CO₂ availability for photosynthesis²⁴⁰. Thus hinting at an enhanced carbon fixation mechanism in *Chlorella cadagno*. These findings suggest its potential towards *in-situ* oxygen production, a process coupled with dark aerobic sulphide oxidation by *C. okenii* in the chemocline of Lake Cadagno. The detection of sulphate assimilatory pathway [M00179] in the nuclear genome of *Chlorella cadagno* MAG further suggests that the sulphate resulting from the sulphide oxidation by *C.*

okenii might in return be consumed by algae. Therefore, suggesting the metabolic tradeoff between photosynthetic algae and purple sulphur bacteria of Lake Cadagno chemocline. Although such sulphur dependent eukaryotic metabolism was unknown for Lake Cadagno, a closely related species *Chlorella pyrenoidosa* has shown to utilise sulphate in laboratory conditions ^{241,242}.

Nitrogen, a key element of life, is modulated by microbial networks ²⁴³ and nitrate assimilation serves as an important source of nitrogen for microalgae ²⁴⁴. In Lake Cadagno, particulate organic nitrogen (PON) peaked in the chemocline ²⁰⁷, in which co-occurrence of nitrogen fixation, ammonia assimilation, and denitrification by purple and green sulphur bacteria is well known ^{24,107,136}. However, the contribution of eukaryotic microbes towards nitrogen cycling is yet to be demonstrated. The pathway for nitrate assimilation [M00615] were identified in Lake Cadagno *Chlorella*, which can be used for nitrate assimilation as shown for *Chlorella pyrenoidosa* and *Chlorella vulgaris* ^{245–248}. Microalgae like *Chlorella* and *Chlamydomonas* utilise nitrate for biomass synthesis ^{244,249}, and pathway of assimilatory nitrate reduction [M00531] was also newly discovered in Lake Cadagno *Chlorella*. The stored nitrate in eukaryotic cells might be used for “breathing” of eukaryotic microbes in anoxic conditions ²⁵⁰, and this also explains persistence of *Chlorella* in anoxic zones of Lake Cadagno. These findings overall demonstrate the potential of Lake Cadagno *Chlorella* to thrive anoxia using carbon, sulphur and nitrogen metabolism as they may have in ancient anoxic oceans. These findings suggest that early photosynthetic microbial eukaryotes may have driven the aerobic conditions via oxygenic photosynthesis which was proposed to be necessary for the evolution of complex life on Earth ²⁹.

Evidence for C,N,S Metabolism in Lake Cadagno *Chlorella*

Figure 5: Functional annotations of *Lake Cadagno Chlorella*'s metabolism. Predicted protein coding genes were mapped to KEGG modules (pathways) using GhostKoala, KEGG mapper, and Anvio (*anvi-estimate-metabolism*).

Figure S2: Functional analysis of Chlorophyta MAG using MetaeukSanity and KEGG. (A) EukMetaSanity predicted protein-coding genes using Metaeuk and Augustus.

Conclusion

This research boosts our understanding of microbial eukaryotes of Lake Cadagno by presenting the first near-complete (including nuclear and chloroplast) genome of novel species of *Chlorella* and one additional chloroplast genome of *Cryptomonas* species both capable of oxygenic photosynthesis in the chemocline. Whether these *Chlorella* in the monimolimnion are alive and active should be verified using metatranscriptomics. Future work is suggested for *Chlorella cadagno* MAG laboratory cultivation to explore their potential for biotechnological applications. For example, *Chlorella vulgaris* is used as biofuels and dietary supplements^{251,252}. In the end, the integrated carbon, sulphur, and nitrogen metabolism in Lake Cadagno *Chlorella* implies how early photosynthetic eukaryotes may have thrived in ancient oceans while facilitating aerobic conditions necessary for the evolution of complex eukaryotic life on Earth.

Materials and Methods

Sample collection and DNA extraction for metagenomics

20L water was collected between two subsequent days 28-29 August 2017 from the stratified zones of Lake Cadagno i.e. mixolimnion (5, 9, and 11 m), chemocline (13, 15, and 15.5 m), and monimolimnion (17 m). Mixolimnion was sampled on day 1 and chemocline and monimolimnion was sampled on day 2. Additionally, one whole water sample without the use of mesh (15—W) was also collected from the peak of turbidity²⁰⁷. The collected water samples were prefiltered using a 55µm mesh to remove zooplankton¹³⁸, and was subsequently passed through a filtration setup equipped with 0.22 µm-filters (cat. #GPWP14250 142 mm Express Plus Filter, Millipore; Darmstadt, Germany) to capture the microbial biomass²⁰⁷. After filtration, the 0.22 µm-filters were flash-frozen at -196° C and later stored at -80° C until DNA extraction which was performed in October 2018 as explained²⁰⁷.

PCR-free libraries were prepared with read length and insert size of 250 bp and sequenced using Illumina HiSeq 4000; CA, USA at the University of Michigan Advanced

Genomics sequencing core facility. Raw reads from the sequencer were trimmed, quality checked and normalised using BBDuk and BBNorm from the BBTools package ²⁵³.

Assembly, Mapping, and Binning

Raw reads were assembled using SPAdes (version 3.15.0) at a kmer length of 21,33,55 by assigning 16 threads (--t) with a memory of 250GB ⁶⁵. Metagenomics mode (--meta) was used for all samples except 15—W for which assembly was only successful without the --meta flag. The contigs names of each assembly were simplified using Anvio (*anvi-script-reformat-fasta*, version 7) and contigs less than 1000 nucleotides (-l 1000) were removed ⁷⁵. Assembly statistics, including size, GC content, number of contigs, N/L50 calculated using *stats.sh* in BBMap ²⁵⁴.

The metagenome assemblies (including nuclear and chloroplasts) were mapped to raw reads using Bowtie 2 (version 2.4.2)²⁵⁵, SAMtools (v.1.12) ²⁵⁶, yielding binary alignment map (BAM). The BAM was sorted and indexed using Anvio (*anvi-init-bam*, version 7) ⁷⁵. Contigs were binned into metagenomic assembled genomes (MAGs) via CONCOCT ⁶⁶ (Clustering contigs with coverage and composition) (version 1.1.0) with default parameters by providing coverage information from individual samples. Cryptomonas MAGs were also binned using competitive binning which leveraged coverage information from all the samples.

Taxonomic classification, quality assessment and visualisation of eukaryotic MAG

Taxonomic classification: Eukaryotic community was initially classified using SSU rRNA sequences by phyloFlash ²⁵⁷ and metagenomic assembled genomes (MAGs) were taxonomically classified using the contig and bin annotation tool (version 5.2.3) also known as CAT BAT ⁷³. Briefly, CAT BAT used prodigal ²⁵⁸ for gene calling and predicted open reading frames (ORFs) which are mapped to NCBI non-redundant protein database (updated 24 July 2021) using DIAMOND (version 0.9.14.115) BLAST (p) (version 2.5.0+), ^{259–262}.

Quality assessment: These MAGs were quality assessed using BUSCO auto lineage (Benchmarking Universal Single-Copy Orthologs, version 5.2.0) ^{219,263,264} which relies on OrthoDB v10 ²⁶⁵ for assessing completion, duplication, and fragmentation of MAGs.

Bin-refinement: Bin refinement was performed by concatenating Chlorophyta MAGs and extracting raw reads from the libraries with high N50 values (Fig 1D; 13 m and 15.5 m). These

raw reads were re-assembled and re-binned to obtain a final representative Chlorophyta MAG. The eukaryotic MAG was further manually refined by referring GC content and coverage in Anvio⁷⁵ while removing coexisting bacterial, archaeal, viral and unknown contigs identified using contig annotation tool (CAT)⁷³.

Visualisation: Stats on eukaryotic MAG (size, contig length, GC content, coverage) were visualised using BlobToolKit (version 2)²⁶⁶ which uses Diamond (version 0.9.14.115) BLAST (p) (version 2.5.0+) (nr database, updated 24 July 2021)^{259–262} for taxonomic classification.

Organelle hunting and chloroplast phylogenomics

Chloroplasts are essential components of autotrophic phytoplankton, and have potential towards contributing to the peaks of photosynthetic pigments like Chlorophyll *a* and phycobilisomes²⁰⁷. Therefore, while hunting the respective chloroplast genome of *Lake Cadagno Chlorella*, we also targeted cryptomonas chloroplasts^{161,227}. Prospective chloroplasts contigs were identified using Blastn by obtaining best hits (*-max_target_seqs 1*) for each query sequence. *Parachlorella kessleri* (NC_012978.1; Chlorella) and *Guillard theta* (NC_000926_1; Cryptomonas) chloroplast genomes were used as query and contigs (hits) with at least 100KB were identified for each query genome (c_000000000152-15-w; c_000000000257-15.5 m). These prospective chloroplast genomes were termed as Chloroplast A (cpA), and chloroplast B (cpB) which were used as template for circularization via NOVOPlasty²³³. The chloroplast genome size range of 80000-200000 was set with the default kmer length of 33 in NOVOPlasty.

Chloroplast phylogenomics was performed with prospective chloroplast genomes from prospective chloroplast genomes of Lake Cadagno (cpA, and cpB) with an additional list of chloroplast genomes from the following three families; (1) *Chlorellaceae* [Taxonomy ID: 35461], (2) *Cryptophyceae* [Taxonomy ID: 3027], and (3) *C. Stramenopiles* [Taxonomy ID: 33634]. *Stramenopiles* were used as outgroups.

The accession numbers of chloroplast genomes used in phylogenomics analysis are as follows; *Micractinium conductrix* [KY629620_1], *Chlorella sorokiniana* [NC_023835.1], *Chlorella heliozoae* [KY629616_1], *Chlorella vulgaris* [AB001684_1], *Dicloster acuatius* [KM462885.1], *Marvania geminata* [KM462888_1], *Pseudochloris wilhelmii* [KM462886.1], *Auxenochlorella proto-theoides* [KC631634.1], *Pabia signiensis* [KM462866.1], *Geminella minor* [KM462883.1], *Rhodomonas salina* [EF508371_1], *Guillardia theta* [NC_000926_1],

Chroomonas placoidea [KY856941_1], *Cryptomonas curvata* [KY856939_1], *Entomoneis sp.* [MG755800.1], *Pseudo-nitzschia delicatissima* [MW715816.1], *Nitzschia inconspicua* [MW971520.1], *Nitzschia supralitorea* [MT383638_1]. A total of 18 marker genes were used for the construction of the chloroplast phylogenomics tree which included ATP synthase (atpA, atpB, atpC), large ribosomal subunits (rpl2, rpl5, rpl12, rpl14, rpl19, rpl23) and small ribosomal subunits (rps3, rps8, rps9, rps19), photosystem I (psaC) and photosystem II (psbA, psbB, psbE, psbH). These markers were individually aligned using MAFFT²⁶⁷ following a quality assessment and removal of ambiguous sequences using Gblocks²⁶⁸. Phylogenetic tree inferences were made using MEGA²⁶⁹ by selecting maximum likelihood calculated by jones-taylor-thornston (JTT) method and by bootstrapping (n=100). The tree was visualised using Dendroscope²⁷⁰ and annotated using ggtree (3.0.1)²⁰⁶ in R-studio¹⁸⁵ (1.4.1106) and Adobe Illustrator (25.2.1).

Functional annotations of nuclear and chloroplast genomes

The metabolic potential of eukaryotic genomes was predicted using EukMetaSanity²³⁵. These protein sequences were annotated by GhostKOALA by assigning K-numbers using KO (KEGG orthology) database^{271,272} mapped to pathways using KEGG mapper²⁷³. The predicted genes were verified using Diamond (version 0.9.14.115) BLAST (p) (version 2.5.0+) (nr database, updated 24 July 2021)²⁵⁹⁻²⁶². These KEGG pathways were independently confirmed using *ab initio* functional annotations by Anvio (*anvi-estimate-metabolism*, version 7.1) which also calculated coverage and completeness of metabolic pathways.

Comparative phylogenomics and quality assessment of *Chlorellaceae* genomes

Phylogenomics of *Chlorellaceae* (NCBI Taxonomy: 35461) was performed using the super-alignment of (40'847 aa) using 90 single-copy orthologs. *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* (GCA_000002595.3) was used as the outgroup species. Following are the accession numbers of the genomes; GCA_006782965.1 (*Chlorella sorokiniana*), GCA_003130725.1 (*Chlorella sorokiniana*), GCA_003116155.1 (*Chlorella sorokiniana*), GCA_002245835.2 (*Chlorella sorokiniana*), GCA_009928355.1 (*Chlorella sp. CH2018*), GCA_006782985.1 (*Chlorella sorokiniana*), GCA_006782975.1 (*Chlorella sp. Dachan*), GCA_002939045.1 (*Chlorella sorokiniana*), GCA_013372505.1 (*Chlorella sp. BAC 9706*), GCA_001021125.1 (*Chlorella*

vulgaris), GCA_009720215.1 (*Chlorella vulgaris*), GCA_009720205.1 (*Chlorella vulgaris*), GCA_000147415.1 (*Chlorella variabilis*), GCA_001430745.1 (*Auxenochlorella pyrenoidosa*), GCA_002896455.3 (*Chlorella sp. ArM0029B*), GCA_002245815.2 (*Micractinium conductrix*), GCA_003063905.1 (*Chlorella sp. A99*), GCA_001598975.1 (*Parachlorella kessleri*), GCA_008119945.1 (*Chlorella vulgaris*), GCA_015712045.1 (*Parachlorella kessleri*), GCA_019202925.1 (*Chlorella desiccata*), GCA_019044685.1 (*Chlorella desiccata*), GCA_004335565.1 (*Nannochloris sp.*), GCA_004335555.1 (*Nannochloris sp.*), GCA_003709365.1 (*Auxenochlorella protothecoides*), GCA_000733215.1 (*Auxenochlorella protothecoides*), GCA_002897115.2 (*Prototheca cutis*), GCA_003255715.1 (*Prototheca wickerhamii*), GCA_016906385.1 (*Prototheca wickerhamii*), GCA_002794665.1 (*Prototheca stagnorum*), GCA_004335735.1 (*Chlorella sp. KRBP*).

Chapter III

3.3. Potential of viruses modulating oxygenic and anoxygenic photosynthesis in chemocline of Lake Cadagno

JS Saini et al.

Contribution statement

I contributed to conceptualization, investigation, data curation, methodology, formal analysis, visualization, writing original draft and review and editing.

Partial funding acquisition

I secured the first three of my salary for this project by obtaining a Swiss Government Excellence Scholarship. Prof. Hassler supported my application for this scholarship. I reached Ernst et Lucie Schmidheiny Foundation which provided an additional 18 months of my scholarship with the support letters from Prof. Zdobnov and Prof. Duhaime.

Introduction

Viruses are astronomically abundant on this planet (10^{31}) compared to the two trillion galaxies (10^{12}) observed in the entire universe ^{51,274}. These biological entities control the microbial realm through lysis, lysogeny and chronic infections and impact biogeochemical cycles globally ^{52,275}. Viruses are ubiquitous in terrestrial and aquatic systems, including soil ²⁷⁶, oceans ²⁷⁷, lakes ^{55,278}, and wastewater ²⁷⁹. The majority of these viruses infect the bacterial realm and are tiny bacteriophages (54 ± 12 nm non-tailed phages; ²⁸⁰ until the recent discoveries of giant viruses of eukaryotic algae indicated to be globally distributed which are also known as nucleocytoplasmic large DNA viruses (NCLDV) ^{57,281}. Following the giant viruses, the detection of jumbo bacteriophages ^{61,282} keeps on challenging the paradigms about the diversity of viruses in our biosphere. Recently, virus-like-particles (VLPs) were measured in meromictic Lake Cadagno, an established Proterozoic Ocean model ^{20–24,207}.

Meromictic Lake Cadagno is a high alpine lake situated at 1921 m altitude in Switzerland. The permanent stratification of this lake separates it into three zones; mixolimnion (upper oxic), monimolimnion (lower anoxic) and an oxic-anoxic boundary called chemocline. In the chemocline, the deep chlorophyll max (*Chl a*) and turbidity indicate phytoplankton and anoxygenic purple and green sulfur bacteria (PSB and GSB). Viruses require a host to replicate, and PSB *Chromatium okenii* is the most active microbe in the chemocline performing major parts of carbon (70%) and nitrogen (>80%) fixation ^{24,104,107}. Evidence indicated CRISPR (Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats) in *C. okenii*, a defence mechanism against viral predations and putative phage sequences, were also detected in *C. okenii* genome ¹¹³. Contrastingly, viruses of *C. okenii* are still missing from Lake Cadagno and any other aquatic systems.

The coupling of the prokaryotic community with the microbial eukaryotes via *in-situ* oxygen production is known ^{114,127,160}. Recently, photosynthetic algae *Chlorella cadagno* has been identified to be abundant at the top of the chemocline. Therefore, to improve our understanding of the viruses of Lake Cadagno, the first step would be to identify and distinguish

the virus community of prokaryotes from microbial eukaryotes ie; the classification of phages and NCLDVs (Nucleocytoplasmic large DNA viruses).

In this section, prospective linkages between microbial eukaryotes, bacteria, and viruses towards nutrient biogeochemical cycling were newly presented, even if the knowledge on viruses of Lake Cadagno was limited to VLPs measurements.

Results and Discussion

In reference to Chapter I & II, photosynthetic algae *Chlorella* and prokaryotic purple sulphur bacteria (PSB) and green sulphur bacteria (GSB) potentially modulate oxygen and anoxygenic photo-chemosynthesis in the chemocline. In Chapter III, efforts were made to detect the viral population capable of infecting microbial eukaryotes (*Chlorella*), PSB (*Chromatium*, *Thiodictyon*), and GSB (*Chlorobium*).

Figure S1. Dashed and solid lines represent 28 and 29 August 2017, respectively. Standard deviations for each sample are indicated by horizontal bars. The abundances of (A) prokaryote-like particles (PLP) and (B) Free virus-like particles (VLP) from flow cytometry analyses and (C) virus-to-microbe ratio, as VLP/PLP.

High abundance of eukaryotic viruses in mixolimnion of Lake Cadagno

VLPs (Virus-like-particles) peaked in the lower mixolimnion around 9-11 m depth of Lake Cadagno where eukaryotic algae was associated with oxygenic photosynthesis (Chapter I)²⁰⁷. Their high abundance of viruses hints at ongoing viral predation of phytoplankton²⁰⁷. Such scenarios of viral infections eventually release DOC²⁸³, which is also observed in lower mixolimnion (Fig.1G). In the zone of mixolimnion of Lake Cadagno where zooplankton predation occurs³, because of the presence of Chlorophytes like *Ankyra judayi*, one would expect dsDNA viruses capable of infecting eukaryotic algae²⁸⁴. By binning viral genomes using metagenomics, this work detected 187 draft NCLDV (viruses infecting eukaryotic algae) genomes in mixolimnion which were higher than the chemocline (n=59), and the monimolimnion (n=11) (Fig. 2). The eukaryotic viruses also had higher coverage and GC content

in the mixolimnion than the chemocline and monimolimnion (Fig. 2 B-C), parallel to the high eukaryotic and viral abundance in the zone of the mixolimnion (Chapter I).

Figure 1. Detection of giant viruses in Lake Cadagno. Putative NCLDV MAGs were binned using MetaBat2²⁸¹ and assessed quality using ViralRecall. (A) MAGs with a positive ViralRecall score (>1) were considered prospective NCLDVs. (B) ViralRecall score vs mean viral hits of prospective NCLDVs. (C, D) Contaminated vs draft NCLDV MAG.

Stats on draft genomes (n=257) of Eukaryotic Giant Viruses (NCLDV)

Figure 2: Stats on draft NCLDV MAGs from the stratified zones of meromictic Lake Cadagno ie. mixolimnion (5, 9, 11 m), chemocline (13, 15, 15-w, 15.5 m) and monimolimnion (17 m).

***Chlorella* viruses may be modulating oxygenic photosynthesis in the chemocline of Lake Cadagno**

Although the coverage of eukaryotic viruses in the chemocline was lower compared to the mixolimnion, the average size of NCLDVs in chemocline was ~300kb, larger than the

average NCLDV genome size of mixolimnion. The NCLDV genome size of ~300kb are categorised as giant viruses ²⁸⁵, which are likely to be present in the chemocline of Lake Cadagno. Coincidentally, eukaryotic algae *Chlorella* is also abundant in the same zone (Chapter II), and the size of *Chlorella* virus (*Paramecium bursaria Chlorella virus*) is also around 330kb ²⁸⁶ similar to the mean NCLDV genome size of ~300kb in the chemocline. *Chlorella* virus-1 has been shown to control photosynthesis via lysis of *Chlorella NC64A* ²⁸⁷. Furthermore, recent study provided insights into its bacteriophage-like replication strategy in which *Paramecium bursaria Chlorella virus-1* perforates chloroplast and nucleus by producing cytoplasmic organelles termed “viral factories” ²⁸⁸. For Lake Cadagno next essential steps would be to blast the *Chlorella* virus genomes available at NCBI against the NCLDV genomes of the Lake Cadagno chemocline. By identifying the *Chlorella* virus genomes, we may be able to assess the impact of viruses on the oxygenic photosynthesis of the chemocline.

First report on detection of phages in Meromictic Lake Cadagno

Figure 3: Stats on viral contigs from MetaSpades assemblies detected using VIBRANT, VirSorter2, DeepVirFinder, and CheckV from each stratified zone of Lake Cadagno ie. mixolimnion (5, 9, 11m), chemocline (13, 15, 15-w, 15.5 m), and monimolimnion (17 m). Each

metagenomic sample was passed through a 50 μm mesh except an additionally collected 15 m whole water sample (15-w).

Phage population was identified using VIBRANT, Virsorter2, DeepVirfinder, and CheckV. These tools are specialised for phages but VIBRANT, and Virsorter2 are also capable of recovering NCLDVs²⁸⁹. The number of viral contigs removed by viral detection tools ranged between 1400-4000 with the water column of Lake Cadagno (Fig. 3). However, the size of the viral assemblies (collection of contigs) was larger in mixolimnion as compared to the chemocline consistent with the highest VLP counts observed in the lower mixolimnion. Both mixolimnion (9m), and chemocline (15.5m) samples have high N50 value which reveals the presence of large size (>400kb) viral genomes. It is possible that these genomes belong to jumbo bacteriophages²⁸², especially in the zone of chemocline where PSB dominates in biomass¹⁰⁷. Future work is suggested to recover *C.okenii* from the pool of viral population detected in this work.

Outlook

In this preliminary report of viruses of Lake Cadagno, eukaryotic virus genomes and bacteriophage contigs were presented. From this pool of viral population, future work might extract viruses of *Chlorella* algae, and phages of purple and green sulphur bacteria. The detection of *Chlorella* virus might be done by taking the previously available *Chlorella* virus genome [NC_000852.5] from NCBI and blasting it against NCLDV genomes presented in this study. Functional annotations of reference genomes can further be compared with proteins predicted from the prospective *Chlorella* virus genomes using tools like DRAM²⁹⁰. By doing this, we may be able to assess the role of viruses towards oxygenic photosynthesis of the chemocline. For detecting the phages of anoxygenic phototrophs like *C.okenii*, and *T.syntrophicum*, CRISPR spacer sequences can be extracted from their MAGs (chapter II). These CRISPR spacer sequences can further be blasted against the phage contigs identified in this study and will potentially lead us to the prospective phage genomes which may be infecting purple sulphur bacteria of chemocline. The prospective phage genomes of purple sulphur bacteria may reveal metabolic potential of viruses towards modulating anoxygenic photo-chemosynthesis of the

chemocline. In a nutshell, the genomic work on viruses of Lake Cadago has potential on answering how viruses may have modulated the primary production of the Proterozoic Oceans.

Methodology

Sample collection and Shot-gun DNA sequencing: Microbial biomass was captured using 0.22 µm filters from mixolimnion (5, 9, 11 m), chemocline (13, 15, 15.5 m) and monimolimnion (17 and 19 m) of Lake Cadagno using 55µm mesh as pre-filter as described in chapter I and II ²⁰⁷. Exceptionally, one additional sample was collected from the peak of turbidity (15 m) without the use of mesh (15-w). DNA was extracted as the protocol described ²⁰⁷ and was sent for illumina high-seq 4000 shotgun DNA sequencing.

Assembly: Raw reads were assembled to contigs using SPAdes ⁶⁵ (v 3.15.0). Contig names were simplified using Anvio's script (anvi-script-reformat-fasta, version 7) and contigs size of fewer than 1000 nucleotides (-l) were removed as per ⁷⁵. Parameters included the selection of kmer length of 21,33,55 and assigning 250 GB memory with 16 threads (--t) in metagenomics mode (--meta) except 15 m whole water (15-w) sample for which assembly was only successful without (--meta) flag.

Mapping: Mapping of MetaSpades assemblies to raw reads was performed by Bowtie 2 (version 2.4.2)²⁵⁵ and Samtools (v.1.12)²⁵⁶, leading to raw binary alignment maps (BAM), which were sorted and indexed using Anvio (anvi-init-bam, version 7) ⁷⁵.

Binning of NCLDV MAGs: Using the information from BAM files, NCLDV MAGs are targeted using MetaBAT2 (v 2.12.1) ⁶⁸ with stringent parameters (-s 100000, -m 10000, -minS 75, -maxEdges 75) as previously described ⁵⁶. These MAGs were quality assessed using the ViralRecall ^{56,291}, and MAGs with net positive scores (>1) were considered as draft NCLDVs ^{56,291} (Chapter III, Fig.1A-D).

Detection of phage contigs: Phage contigs were detected from metagenomic assemblies using VIBRANT ²⁹², VirSorter2 ²⁸⁹, CheckV ²⁹³, and DeepVirFinder ²⁹⁴. These contigs were quality assessed, and viral contigs were finalised based on consensus as described ²⁹⁵.

Statistics

The statistics on viral population (collection of viral contigs) from each sample, including size, GC content, number of contigs, N50, was calculated using *stats.sh* script in BBMap ²⁵⁴ and relative abundances of the viral population are calculated using CoverM (<https://github.com/wwood/CoverM>). N50 is defined as the sequence length of the shortest contigs which covers at least 50% of the genome or assembly whereas L50 is the count of contigs contributing towards the N50 statistics.

Main discussion

In addition to the specific set of discussions for each chapter, this discussion aims to provide a broader aspect of the work. It weighs its strengths and limitations while suggesting directions for future research.

Lake Cadagno provided a better understanding of the Proterozoic Ocean microbial loop

Recently with the help of 16S rRNA gene sequencing and flow-cytometry, immense genotypic and phenotypic diversity has been discovered in the chemocline of Lake Cadagno^{109,207} hinting at microbial life yet to be discovered. Throughout these years, few reports directed attention to microbial eukaryotes^{114,138,160,296}, and reports on viral ecology of Lake Cadagno were non-existent. The first chapter sought our understanding of the functioning of microbial communities (bacteria, viruses, and eukaryotes) as a whole and discussed its relevance to the Proterozoic ocean microbial loop. The better understanding of the Lake Cadagno microbial loop paved the way for the metagenomics of microbial eukaryotes and viruses as a chapter (II) and chapter (III).

A paradox of microbial abundances, activity, and biomass of chemocline

One of the main highlights of the chapter (I) was the methodological aspect related to qualitative and/or quantitative estimation of the abundance of microbes. In previous literature, a mixture of studies used FISH (fluorescent in-situ hybridization), flow-cytometry, and 16S sequencing to estimate the microbes of the chemocline^{109,110,128,136}. While FISH can be handy for targeting a specific set of microbial communities, 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing and flow-cytometry take the edge on the qualitative and quantitative sides. Because of their strengths, the combination of these two techniques has been proven to be helpful in estimating the absolute abundance of microbial communities^{148,297} which has also been applied for Lake Cadagno. However, more abundance does not necessarily mean more biomass. Such scenarios are common in aquatic environments, where the prokaryotic population would likely be more numerous than

eukaryotes, but when accounting for biomass eukaryotes are likely to lead (Main Discussion, Fig. 3). However, with few exceptions for Lake Cadagno, large size prokaryotes like *C. okenii* (8-10 μ m) are known to be present in the chemocline of Lake Cadagno¹¹³, and their size is almost similar to the size of small eukaryotic algae like *Chlorella*. Studies have consistently shown *C. okenii* to be the dominant contributor to chemocline biomass^{24,107}. While *C. okenii* was amongst least abundant (cell counts) microbes in the chemocline in 2008¹⁰⁷, recent evidence suggested its increase in cell numbers approximately to 8e+04 to 3e+05 comparatively in summers (July 2016, and August, 2017)^{109,207}. The increase or decrease in *Chromatium okenii* and other green sulphur bacteria such as *Chlorobium clathratiforme* has also been attributed to seasonal fluctuations¹⁰⁹. Following *Chromatium*, the high number of *Chlorobium clathratiforme* cells has also been noted for Lake Cadagno chemocline but their contribution to Chemocline biomass may further be investigated^{109,110}. The recent studies showed that PSB (*Chromatium okenii*, *T. syntrophicum*, *Lamprocystis* spp., *L. roseopersicina*, *L. purpurea*) contributed between ~30-40% of bulk carbon biomass, and *C. okenii* to majority of the fraction (~30%)²⁴ and rest of the microbial biomass may be attributed to other microbial populations including GSBs, heterotrophic microbes like *Lentimicrobium*, and oxygenic phototrophs like microbial eukaryotes and viruses. The contribution of each microbial domain to chemocline biomass may be presumed to provide insights into their functionality as multiplicity of cells may generate more biomass. Contrastingly, microbial populations with low cell counts may equally be effective in functionality. For example, less abundant *Thiodictyon syntrophicum* contributes around 26% towards inorganic carbon fixation¹¹⁵. One more example from the peatland field site is *Desulfosporosinus* species, which was only 0.006% of the total microbial community but highly active members involved in sulphate reduction²⁹⁸. Because of these reasons, caution should be taken when interpreting biomass, activity, and abundance in aquatic ecosystems.

Discussion, Figure. 1 Hypothetical explanation of abundance vs biomass created with BioRender.com

Chapter II identified the first nuclear and chloroplasts genomes of the chemocline. Assuming eukaryotes tend to be larger than bacterial cells, microbial eukaryotes have the potential to contribute to the biomass of chemocline. However, the contribution of microbial eukaryotes towards chemocline biomass had not been estimated yet.

Cyanobacterial bloom led to the discovery of eukaryotic algal genomes in the chemocline

Discussion, Figure. 2 Basic structure of phycobilisome created with BioRender.com

Based on flow-cytometry cell counts of phycobilisome containing cells, a bloom of cyanobacteria along the 2017 warm season (e.g. 28 August and 12 September)^{109,115}. Approximately 24% of carbon flux in the chemocline was attributed to oxygenic phototrophs including cyanobacteria, chlorophytes and diatoms (Fig. 6^{24 121}). Generally, these oxygenic phototrophs are capable of yielding auto-fluorescences to pyocyanin and phycoerythrin, just above the peak of turbidity. Therefore, it was important to find the source of these photosynthetic signals. In chapter (I), 16S rRNA gene amplicon data indicated the rarity of cyanobacteria and the abundance of chloroplasts in the chemocline. However, chapter (I) was limited to amplicon sequencing. Interestingly, flow-cytometry quantified cyanobacterial cells also contributed most to the carbon fixation during light reactions when compared to purple and green sulfur bacteria (Fig. S5^{24 115}). Therefore, metagenomics was used to identify these photosynthetic cells, which led to the discovery of the first genomes of microbial eukaryotes from Lake Cadagno including *Chlorella* (nuclear and chloroplast) and *Cryptomonas* (chloroplast). *Cryptomonas* chloroplast was equipped with phycoerythrin and photosystem I and II, which are essential top and bottom components of the phycobilisome structure (ref chapter II). These findings suggest that phycocyanin pigments in the chemocline are likely to be originating from *Cryptomonas*, which were attributed to cyanobacteria using flow cytometry. On a positive note, with the help of programs like phenoflow, flow-cytometry generated fingerprints are still a cheap and reliable source to assess bacterial phenotypic diversity and taxa in aquatic systems^{98,299}.

Viruses may facilitate biomass production in the chemocline, but how?

Discussion, Figure. 3 Hypothetical picture of viral modulation of primary production in the chemocline of Lake Cadagno created with BioRender.com.

Twenty years ago, oxygenic and anoxygenic phototrophs contributed equally to the carbon photo assimilation in the chemocline¹³⁸. Viruses infecting cyanobacteria have been shown to contain protein of photosystem (PS) II³⁰⁰ which may be essential for oxygenic photosynthesis occurring in the chemocline of Lake Cadagno. Cyanobacteria were not discovered in the chemocline, but instead green algae *Chlorella* and *Cryptomonas* were present, both containing photosystems (PS I and PS II) in their genome. These findings of *Chlorella* and *Cryptomonas* led to the hunt for NCLDVs (viruses infecting eukaryotic algae). Apart from oxygenic photosynthesis, anoxygenic phototroph *Chromatium okenii* has been a key contributor of primary production in the chemocline, and auxiliary metabolic genes (AMGs) involved in the oxidation of sulfur and thiosulfate (*dsrA*, *dsrC/tusE*, *soxC*, *soxD* and *soxYZ*) has been found in bacteriophages in other systems³⁰¹. On the contrary, viruses manipulating purple sulfur bacteria have been reported to date, neither for Lake Cadagno nor other systems. By providing evidence for viral modulation of oxygenic and anoxygenic phototrophs in Lake Cadagno, we may be able to demonstrate how viruses impacted primary production in the Proterozoic Oceans. This investigation may reveal the role of viruses towards the biogeochemical cycling of the Proterozoic oceans which so far has been missing from the literature.

Conclusion and Future Directions

Microbiology of Lake Cadagno has been studied for at least 25 years, and this work presents the comprehensive synthesis of Lake Cadagno microbial loop in context to proterozoic oceans. Multiple microbial guilds including eukaryotes, bacteria, and viruses were brought forward and were discussed in context to biogeochemical functionality and how their collective contribution is crucial for maintenance of Lake Cadagno microbial bloom.

Flow-cytometry has been extensively used to measure cell counts in Lake Cadagno, however, work was limited to measuring abundance. This work extends flow-cytometry phenotypic fingerprints to assess the alpha beta phenotypic diversity in Lake Cadagno. The phenotypic fingerprints collected throughout these years, may be used in future studies to investigate the seasonal change in diversity throughout the Lake Cadagno water column.

Furthermore, the coupling of oxygenic and anoxygenic photo-chemosynthesis in oxic-anoxic chemocline along with the first genomic insights into microbial eukaryotes were amongst the main focus of this work. Persistence of photosynthetic microbial eukaryotes in anoxic zone was evident, but further studies are needed to verify the integrity of these cells. Are they dead or alive? If alive, how such photosynthetic eukaryotes survive hydrogen sulphide and ammonium rich monimolimnion? Answering such questions may hold greater importance in understanding the origin of eukaryotic life in anoxic oceans. The work also provided the first insights into the viral ecology of Lake Cadagno, but future work is required to provide empirical evidence on viral control on functioning of microbial eukaryotes, and purple and green sulphur bacteria of chemocline.

References

1. Hall, K. J. & Northcote, T. G. Meromictic Lakes. in *Encyclopedia of Lakes and Reservoirs* (eds. Bengtsson, L., Herschy, R. W. & Fairbridge, R. W.) 519–524 (Springer Netherlands, 2012).
2. Balistrieri, L. S., Murray, J. W. & Paul, B. The geochemical cycling of trace elements in a biogenic meromictic lake. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* **58**, 3993–4008 (1994).
3. Tonolla, M. *et al.* Lake Cadagno: Microbial Life in Crenogenic Meromixis. *Ecology of Meromictic Lakes* 155–186 (2017) doi:10.1007/978-3-319-49143-1_7.
4. Block, K. R., O'Brien, J. M., Edwards, W. J. & Marnocha, C. L. Vertical structure of the bacterial diversity in meromictic Fayetteville Green Lake. *Microbiologyopen* **10**, e1228 (2021).
5. Lauro, F. M. *et al.* An integrative study of a meromictic lake ecosystem in Antarctica. *ISME J.* **5**, 879–895 (2011).
6. Rogozin, D. *et al.* Comparative Study of the Stability of Stratification and the Food Web Structure in the Meromictic Lakes Shira and Shunet (South Siberia, Russia). in *Ecology of Meromictic Lakes* (eds. Gulati, R. D., Zadereev, E. S. & Degermendzhi, A. G.) 89–124 (Springer International Publishing, 2017).
7. Hug, L. A. *et al.* A new view of the tree of life. *Nat Microbiol* **1**, 16048 (2016).
8. Legendre, M., Arslan, D., Abergel, C. & Claverie, J.-M. Genomics of Megavirus and the elusive fourth domain of Life. *Commun. Integr. Biol.* **5**, 102–106 (2012).
9. Huber, C. & Wächtershäuser, G. Activated acetic acid by carbon fixation on (Fe,Ni)S under primordial conditions. *Science* **276**, 245–247 (1997).

-
10. Lepot, K. Signatures of early microbial life from the Archean (4 to 2.5 Ga) eon. *Earth-Sci. Rev.* **209**, 103296 (2020).
 11. Olejarz, J., Iwasa, Y., Knoll, A. H. & Nowak, M. A. The Great Oxygenation Event as a consequence of ecological dynamics modulated by planetary change. *Nat. Commun.* **12**, 3985 (2021).
 12. Alcott, L. J., Mills, B. J. W. & Poulton, S. W. Stepwise Earth oxygenation is an inherent property of global biogeochemical cycling. *Science* **366**, 1333–1337 (2019).
 13. Javaux, E. J. & Lepot, K. The Paleoproterozoic fossil record: Implications for the evolution of the biosphere during Earth's middle-age. *Earth-Sci. Rev.* **176**, 68–86 (2018).
 14. Johnston, D. T., Wolfe-Simon, F., Pearson, A. & Knoll, A. H. Anoxygenic photosynthesis modulated Proterozoic oxygen and sustained Earth's middle age. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **106**, 16925–16929 (2009).
 15. Knoll, A. H., Bergmann, K. D. & Strauss, J. V. Life: the first two billion years. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. B Biol. Sci.* **371**, (2016).
 16. Knoll, A. H. Paleobiological Perspectives on Early Microbial Evolution. *Cold Spring Harb. Perspect. Biol.* **7**, a018093 (2015).
 17. Fuchsman, C. A. & Stüeken, E. E. Using modern low-oxygen marine ecosystems to understand the nitrogen cycle of the Paleo- and Mesoproterozoic oceans. *Environ. Microbiol.* **23**, 2801–2822 (2021).
 18. Hamilton, T. L., Bryant, D. A. & Macalady, J. L. The role of biology in planetary evolution: cyanobacterial primary production in low-oxygen Proterozoic oceans. *Environ. Microbiol.* **18**, 325–340 (2016).
 19. Suzuki, N. & Oba, M. Oldest Fossil Records of Marine Protists and the Geologic History

-
- Toward the Establishment of the Modern-Type Marine Protist World. in *Marine Protists: Diversity and Dynamics* (eds. Ohtsuka, S., Suzaki, T., Horiguchi, T., Suzuki, N. & Not, F.) 359–394 (Springer Japan, 2015).
20. Xiong, Y. *et al.* Phosphorus cycling in Lake Cadagno, Switzerland: A low sulfate euxinic ocean analogue. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* **251**, 116–135 (2019).
 21. Canfield, D. E., Farquhar, J. & Zerkle, A. L. High isotope fractionations during sulfate reduction in a low-sulfate euxinic ocean analog. *Geology* **38**, 415–418 (2010).
 22. Dahl, T. W. *et al.* The behavior of molybdenum and its isotopes across the chemocline and in the sediments of sulfidic Lake Cadagno, Switzerland. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* **74**, 144–163 (2010).
 23. Wirth, S. B. *et al.* Combining sedimentological, trace metal (Mn, Mo) and molecular evidence for reconstructing past water-column redox conditions: The example of meromictic Lake Cadagno (Swiss Alps). *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* **120**, 220–238 (2013).
 24. Philippi, M. *et al.* Purple sulfur bacteria fix N₂ via molybdenum-nitrogenase in a low molybdenum Proterozoic ocean analogue. *Nat. Commun.* **12**, 4774 (2021).
 25. Sánchez-Baracaldo, P. & Cardona, T. On the origin of oxygenic photosynthesis and Cyanobacteria. *New Phytol.* **225**, 1440–1446 (2020).
 26. Falcón, L. I., Magallón, S. & Castillo, A. Dating the cyanobacterial ancestor of the chloroplast. *ISME J.* **4**, 777–783 (2010).
 27. Bhattacharya, D. & Price, D. C. The Algal Tree of Life from a Genomics Perspective. in *Photosynthesis in Algae: Biochemical and Physiological Mechanisms* (eds. Larkum, A. W. D., Grossman, A. R. & Raven, J. A.) 11–24 (Springer International Publishing, 2020).
 28. Schirrmeister, B. E., de Vos, J. M., Antonelli, A. & Bagheri, H. C. Evolution of

-
- multicellularity coincided with increased diversification of cyanobacteria and the Great Oxidation Event. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **110**, 1791–1796 (2013).
29. Berg, J. S. *et al.* How low can they go? Aerobic respiration by microorganisms under apparent anoxia. *FEMS Microbiol. Rev.* **46**, (2022).
30. Moczyłowska, M., Landing, E. D., Zang, W. & Palacios, T. Proterozoic phytoplankton and timing of Chlorophyte algae origins. *Palaeontology* **54**, 721–733 (2011).
31. Saunders, G. W. & McDevit, D. C. Methods for DNA barcoding photosynthetic protists emphasizing the macroalgae and diatoms. *Methods Mol. Biol.* **858**, 207–222 (2012).
32. Pernice, M. C. *et al.* Global abundance of planktonic heterotrophic protists in the deep ocean. *ISME J.* **9**, 782–792 (2015).
33. Flynn, K. J. *et al.* Mixotrophic protists and a new paradigm for marine ecology: where does plankton research go now? *J. Plankton Res.* **41**, 375–391 (2019).
34. Worden, A. Z. *et al.* Environmental science. Rethinking the marine carbon cycle: factoring in the multifarious lifestyles of microbes. *Science* **347**, 1257594 (2015).
35. Ohtsuka, S., Suzaki, T., Horiguchi, T., Suzuki, N. & Not, F. *Marine Protists: Diversity and Dynamics*. (Springer Japan, 2015).
36. Caron, D. A., Worden, A. Z., Countway, P. D., Demir, E. & Heidelberg, K. B. Protists are microbes too: a perspective. *ISME J.* **3**, 4–12 (2009).
37. Whitman, W. B., Coleman, D. C. & Wiebe, W. J. Prokaryotes: the unseen majority. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **95**, 6578–6583 (1998).
38. Microbiology by numbers. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **9**, 628 (2011).
39. Flombaum, P. *et al.* Present and future global distributions of the marine Cyanobacteria Prochlorococcus and Synechococcus. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **110**, 9824–9829

-
- (2013).
40. *Oxygenic Photosynthesis: The Light Reactions*. (Springer Netherlands).
 41. Graham, E. D., Heidelberg, J. F. & Tully, B. J. Potential for primary productivity in a globally-distributed bacterial phototroph. *ISME J.* **12**, 1861–1866 (2018).
 42. *Anoxygenic Photosynthetic Bacteria*. (Springer Netherlands).
 43. Kappler, A. *et al.* An evolving view on biogeochemical cycling of iron. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **19**, 360–374 (2021).
 44. Canfield, D. E. & Farquhar, J. The Global Sulfur Cycle. in *Fundamentals of Geobiology* 49–64 (John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2012).
 45. Falkowski, P. G., Fenchel, T. & Delong, E. F. The microbial engines that drive Earth's biogeochemical cycles. *Science* **320**, 1034–1039 (2008).
 46. Schimel, J. Playing scales in the methane cycle: from microbial ecology to the globe. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* vol. 101 12400–12401 (2004).
 47. Bar-On, Y. M., Phillips, R. & Milo, R. The biomass distribution on Earth. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **115**, 6506–6511 (2018).
 48. Bunse, C. & Pinhassi, J. Marine Bacterioplankton Seasonal Succession Dynamics. *Trends Microbiol.* **25**, 494–505 (2017).
 49. Hungate, B. A. *et al.* The Functional Significance of Bacterial Predators. *MBio* **12**, (2021).
 50. Breitbart, M., Bonnain, C., Malki, K. & Sawaya, N. A. Phage puppet masters of the marine microbial realm. *Nat Microbiol* **3**, 754–766 (2018).
 51. Mushegian, A. R. Are There 10³¹ Virus Particles on Earth, or More, or Fewer? *J. Bacteriol.* **202**, (2020).

-
52. Suttle, C. A. Marine viruses--major players in the global ecosystem. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **5**, 801–812 (2007).
 53. Trubl, G. *et al.* Soil Viruses Are Underexplored Players in Ecosystem Carbon Processing. *mSystems* **3**, (2018).
 54. Zimmerman, A. E. *et al.* Metabolic and biogeochemical consequences of viral infection in aquatic ecosystems. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **18**, 21–34 (2020).
 55. Jacquet, S., Miki, T., Noble, R., Peduzzi, P. & Wilhelm, S. Viruses in aquatic ecosystems: important advancements of the last 20 years and prospects for the future in the field of microbial oceanography and limnology. *Advances in Oceanography and Limnology* **1**, 97–141 (2010).
 56. Moniruzzaman, M., Martinez-Gutierrez, C. A., Weinheimer, A. R. & Aylward, F. O. Dynamic genome evolution and complex virocell metabolism of globally-distributed giant viruses. *Nat. Commun.* **11**, 1710 (2020).
 57. Schulz, F. *et al.* Giant virus diversity and host interactions through global metagenomics. *Nature* **578**, 432–436 (2020).
 58. Tran, P. Q. & Anantharaman, K. Biogeochemistry Goes Viral: towards a Multifaceted Approach To Study Viruses and Biogeochemical Cycling. *mSystems* **6**, e0113821 (2021).
 59. Quince, C., Walker, A. W., Simpson, J. T., Loman, N. J. & Segata, N. Shotgun metagenomics, from sampling to analysis. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **35**, 833–844 (2017).
 60. Nayfach, S. *et al.* A genomic catalog of Earth’s microbiomes. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **39**, 499–509 (2021).
 61. Al-Shayeb, B. *et al.* Clades of huge phages from across Earth’s ecosystems. *Nature* **578**, 425–431 (2020).

-
62. Stephens, Z. D. *et al.* Big Data: Astronomical or Genomical? *PLoS Biol.* **13**, e1002195 (2015).
 63. Peng, Y., Leung, H. C. M., Yiu, S. M. & Chin, F. Y. L. Meta-IDBA: a de Novo assembler for metagenomic data. *Bioinformatics* **27**, i94–101 (2011).
 64. Li, D., Liu, C.-M., Luo, R., Sadakane, K. & Lam, T.-W. MEGAHIT: an ultra-fast single-node solution for large and complex metagenomics assembly via succinct de Bruijn graph. *Bioinformatics* **31**, 1674–1676 (2015).
 65. Bankevich, A. *et al.* SPAdes: a new genome assembly algorithm and its applications to single-cell sequencing. *J. Comput. Biol.* **19**, 455–477 (2012).
 66. Alneberg, J. *et al.* Binning metagenomic contigs by coverage and composition. *Nat. Methods* **11**, 1144–1146 (2014).
 67. Wu, Y.-W., Simmons, B. A. & Singer, S. W. MaxBin 2.0: an automated binning algorithm to recover genomes from multiple metagenomic datasets. *Bioinformatics* **32**, 605–607 (2016).
 68. Kang, D. D. *et al.* MetaBAT 2: an adaptive binning algorithm for robust and efficient genome reconstruction from metagenome assemblies. *PeerJ* **7**, e7359 (2019).
 69. Laczny, C. C. *et al.* VizBin - an application for reference-independent visualization and human-augmented binning of metagenomic data. *Microbiome* **3**, 1 (2015).
 70. Manni, M., Berkeley, M. R., Seppey, M., Simão, F. A. & Zdobnov, E. M. BUSCO Update: Novel and Streamlined Workflows along with Broader and Deeper Phylogenetic Coverage for Scoring of Eukaryotic, Prokaryotic, and Viral Genomes. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* **38**, 4647–4654 (2021).
 71. Parks, D. H., Imelfort, M., Skennerton, C. T., Hugenholtz, P. & Tyson, G. W. CheckM: assessing the quality of microbial genomes recovered from isolates, single cells, and

-
- metagenomes. *Genome Res.* **25**, 1043–1055 (2015).
72. Chaumeil, P.-A., Mussig, A. J., Hugenholtz, P. & Parks, D. H. GTDB-Tk: a toolkit to classify genomes with the Genome Taxonomy Database. *Bioinformatics* (2019) doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/btz848.
73. von Meijenfeldt, F. A. B., Arkhipova, K., Cambuy, D. D., Coutinho, F. H. & Dutilh, B. E. Robust taxonomic classification of uncharted microbial sequences and bins with CAT and BAT. *Genome Biol.* **20**, 217 (2019).
74. Kieser, S., Brown, J., Zdobnov, E. M., Trajkovski, M. & McCue, L. A. ATLAS: a Snakemake workflow for assembly, annotation, and genomic binning of metagenome sequence data. *BMC Bioinformatics* **21**, 257 (2020).
75. Eren, A. M. *et al.* Anvi'o: an advanced analysis and visualization platform for 'omics data. *PeerJ* **3**, e1319 (2015).
76. Glendinning, L., Stewart, R. D., Pallen, M. J., Watson, K. A. & Watson, M. Assembly of hundreds of novel bacterial genomes from the chicken caecum. *Genome Biol.* **21**, 34 (2020).
77. Picone, N. *et al.* Metagenome Assembled Genome of a Novel Verrucomicrobial Methanotroph From Pantelleria Island. *Front. Microbiol.* **12**, 666929 (2021).
78. Obiol, A. *et al.* A metagenomic assessment of microbial eukaryotic diversity in the global ocean. *Mol. Ecol. Resour.* **20**, (2020).
79. Silva, R., Padovani, K., Góes, F. & Alves, R. geneRFinder: gene finding in distinct metagenomic data complexities. *BMC Bioinformatics* **22**, 87 (2021).
80. Hoff, K. J. *et al.* Gene prediction in metagenomic fragments: a large scale machine learning approach. *BMC Bioinformatics* **9**, 217 (2008).
81. Dong, X. *et al.* Metabolic potential of uncultured bacteria and archaea associated with

-
- petroleum seepage in deep-sea sediments. *Nat. Commun.* **10**, 1816 (2019).
82. Taş, N. *et al.* Metagenomic tools in microbial ecology research. *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* **67**, 184–191 (2021).
83. Terrón-González, L., Genilloud, O. & Santero, E. Potential and limitations of metagenomic functional analyses. in 1–43 (unknown, 2014).
84. Aguiar-Pulido, V. *et al.* Metagenomics, Metatranscriptomics, and Metabolomics Approaches for Microbiome Analysis. *Evol. Bioinform. Online* **12**, 5–16 (2016).
85. Thissen, J. B., Be, N. A., McLoughlin, K. & Jaing, C. Table 1 . Comparison of Axiom Microbiome Array vs 16S rRNA sequencing. *ResearchGate*
https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Comparison-of-Axiom-Microbiome-Array-vs-16S-rRNA-sequencing-vs-metagenomic-sequencing_tbl1_330975129 (2019).
86. Hugerth, L. W. & Andersson, A. F. Analysing Microbial Community Composition through Amplicon Sequencing: From Sampling to Hypothesis Testing. *Front. Microbiol.* **8**, 1561 (2017).
87. Větrovský, T. & Baldrian, P. The variability of the 16S rRNA gene in bacterial genomes and its consequences for bacterial community analyses. *PLoS One* **8**, e57923 (2013).
88. Lambrecht, J. *et al.* Flow cytometric quantification, sorting and sequencing of methanogenic archaea based on F420 autofluorescence. *Microb. Cell Fact.* **16**, 180 (2017).
89. Marie, D., Shi, X. L., Rigaut-Jalabert, F. & Vaultot, D. Use of flow cytometric sorting to better assess the diversity of small photosynthetic eukaryotes in the English Channel. *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* **72**, 165–178 (2010).
90. Carlson-Jones, J. A. P. *et al.* Enumerating Virus-Like Particles and Bacterial Populations in the Sinuses of Chronic Rhinosinusitis Patients Using Flow Cytometry. *PLoS One* **11**,

-
- e0155003 (2016).
91. Amann, R. & Fuchs, B. M. Single-cell identification in microbial communities by improved fluorescence in situ hybridization techniques. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **6**, 339–348 (2008).
 92. Huber, D., Voith von Voithenberg, L. & Kaigala, G. V. Fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH): History, limitations and what to expect from micro-scale FISH? *Nanoscale Microscale Thermophys. Eng.* **1**, 15–24 (2018).
 93. Bernstein, H. C. *et al.* Trade-offs between microbiome diversity and productivity in a stratified microbial mat. *ISME J.* **11**, 405–414 (2017).
 94. Purvis, A. & Hector, A. Getting the measure of biodiversity. *Nature* **405**, 212–219 (2000).
 95. Wanderley, B. M. S. *et al.* flowDiv: a new pipeline for analyzing flow cytometric diversity. *BMC Bioinformatics* **20**, 274 (2019).
 96. Rubbens, P. & Props, R. Computational Analysis of Microbial Flow Cytometry Data. *mSystems* **6**, (2021).
 97. Props, R. *et al.* Flow cytometric monitoring of bacterioplankton phenotypic diversity predicts high population-specific feeding rates by invasive dreissenid mussels. *Environ. Microbiol.* **20**, 521–534 (2018).
 98. Props, R., Monsieurs, P., Mysara, M., Clement, L. & Boon, N. Measuring the biodiversity of microbial communities by flow cytometry. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* **7**, 1376–1385 (2016).
 99. McMurdie, P. J. & Holmes, S. phyloseq: an R package for reproducible interactive analysis and graphics of microbiome census data. *PLoS One* **8**, e61217 (2013).
 100. Ho, N. T., Li, F., Wang, S. & Kuhn, L. metamicrobiomeR: an R package for analysis of microbiome relative abundance data using zero-inflated beta GAMLSS and meta-analysis across studies using random effects models. *BMC Bioinformatics* **20**, 188 (2019).

-
101. Field, C. B., Behrenfeld, M. J., Randerson, J. T. & Falkowski, P. Primary production of the biosphere: integrating terrestrial and oceanic components. *Science* **281**, 237–240 (1998).
 102. Ozaki, K., Thompson, K. J., Simister, R. L., Crowe, S. A. & Reinhard, C. T. Anoxygenic photosynthesis and the delayed oxygenation of Earth's atmosphere. *Nat. Commun.* **10**, 3026 (2019).
 103. Morana, C. *et al.* Chemoautotrophy and anoxygenic photosynthesis within the water column of a large meromictic tropical lake (Lake Kivu, East Africa). *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **61**, 1424–1437 (2016).
 104. Di Nezio, F. *et al.* Anoxygenic photo- and chemo-synthesis of phototrophic sulfur bacteria from an alpine meromictic lake. *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* **97**, (2021).
 105. Ward, L. M., Cardona, T. & Holland-Moritz, H. Evolutionary Implications of Anoxygenic Phototrophy in the Bacterial Phylum Candidatus Eremiobacterota (WPS-2). *Front. Microbiol.* **10**, 1658 (2019).
 106. Chróst, R. J. & Rai, H. Bacterial Secondary Production. in *Microbial Ecology of Lake Plußsee* (eds. Overbeck, J. & Chróst, R. J.) 92–117 (Springer New York, 1994).
 107. Musat, N. *et al.* A single-cell view on the ecophysiology of anaerobic phototrophic bacteria. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **105**, 17861–17866 (2008).
 108. Rico, K. I. & Sheldon, N. D. Nutrient and iron cycling in a modern analogue for the redoxcline of a Proterozoic ocean shelf. *Chem. Geol.* **511**, 42–50 (2019).
 109. Danza, F. *et al.* Bacterial diversity in the water column of meromictic Lake Cadagno and evidence for seasonal dynamics. *PLoS One* **13**, e0209743 (2018).
 110. Gregersen, L. H. *et al.* Dominance of a clonal green sulfur bacterial population in a stratified lake. *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* **70**, 30–41 (2009).

-
111. Tonolla, M., Peduzzi, R. & Hahn, D. Long-term population dynamics of phototrophic sulfur bacteria in the chemocline of Lake Cadagno, Switzerland. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **71**, 3544–3550 (2005).
112. Peduzzi, S. *et al.* Candidatus ‘Thiodictyon syntrophicum’, sp. nov., a new purple sulfur bacterium isolated from the chemocline of Lake Cadagno forming aggregates and specific associations with *Desulfocapsa* sp. *Systematic and Applied Microbiology* vol. 35 139–144 (2012).
113. Luedin, S. *et al.* Draft Genome Sequence of *Chromatium okenii* Isolated from the Stratified Alpine Lake Cadagno. *Sci. Rep.* **9**, 1936 (2019).
114. Berg, J. S. *et al.* Dark aerobic sulfide oxidation by anoxygenic phototrophs in anoxic waters. *Environ. Microbiol.* **21**, 1611–1626 (2019).
115. Luedin, S. M. *et al.* Mixotrophic Growth Under Micro-Oxic Conditions in the Purple Sulfur Bacterium ‘Thiodictyon syntrophicum’. *Front. Microbiol.* **10**, 384 (2019).
116. Decristophoris, P., Peduzzi, S., Ruggeri-Bernardi, N., Hahn, D. & Tonolla, M. Fine scale analysis of shifts in bacterial community structure in the chemocline of meromictic Lake Cadagno, Switzerland. *J. Limnol.* **68**, 16–24 (2009).
117. Danza, F. Flow cytometry as a tool to investigate the anoxygenic phototrophic sulfur bacteria coexistence in the chemocline of meromictic Lake Cadagno. (University of Geneva, 2018). doi:10.13097/archive-ouverte/unige:103201.
118. Habicht, K. S. *et al.* Comparative proteomics and activity of a green sulfur bacterium through the water column of Lake Cadagno, Switzerland. *Environ. Microbiol.* **13**, 203–215 (2011).
119. Luedin, S. M. *et al.* Complete genome sequence of ‘Thiodictyon syntrophicum’ sp. nov.

-
- strain Cad16T, a photolithoautotrophic purple sulfur bacterium isolated from the alpine meromictic Lake Cadagno. *Stand. Genomic Sci.* **13**, 14 (2018).
120. Storelli, N. *et al.* CO₂ assimilation in the chemocline of Lake Cadagno is dominated by a few types of phototrophic purple sulfur bacteria. *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* **84**, 421–432 (2013).
121. Posth, N. R. *et al.* Carbon isotope fractionation by anoxygenic phototrophic bacteria in euxinic Lake Cadagno. *Geobiology* **15**, 798–816 (2017).
122. Danza, F., Storelli, N., Roman, S., Lüdin, S. & Tonolla, M. Dynamic cellular complexity of anoxygenic phototrophic sulfur bacteria in the chemocline of meromictic Lake Cadagno. *PLoS One* **12**, e0189510 (2017).
123. Storelli, N., Saad, M. M., Frigaard, N.-U., Perret, X. & Tonolla, M. Proteomic analysis of the purple sulfur bacterium Candidatus ‘Thiodictyon syntrophicum’ strain Cad16T isolated from Lake Cadagno. *EuPA Open Proteomics* **2**, 17–30 (2014).
124. Storelli, N. Role of phototrophic sulfur bacteria from the chemocline in the primary production of Lake Cadagno. (University of Geneva, 2014).
doi:10.13097/archive-ouverte/unige:34915.
125. Ludin, S. Functional genomics of purple sulfur bacteria from Lake Cadagno. (University of Geneva, 2018). doi:10.13097/archive-ouverte/unige:108895.
126. Berg, J. The microbial impact on Fe&S cycling at oxic-anoxic interfaces: a single-cell view. (2016).
127. Berg, J. S. *et al.* Intensive cryptic microbial iron cycling in the low iron water column of the meromictic Lake Cadagno. *Environ. Microbiol.* **18**, 5288–5302 (2016).
128. Schubert, C. J. *et al.* Evidence for anaerobic oxidation of methane in sediments of a

-
- freshwater system (Lago di Cadagno). *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* **76**, 26–38 (2011).
129. Kaneko, H. *et al.* Eukaryotic virus composition can predict the efficiency of carbon export in the global ocean. *iScience* **24**, 102002 (2021).
130. Saini, J. S., Hassler, C., Cable, R., Fourquez, M. & Danza, F. Bacterial, Phytoplankton, and Viral Distributions and Their Biogeochemical Contexts in Meromictic Lake Cadagno Offer Insights into the Proterozoic Ocean Microbial *MBio* (2022).
131. Canfield, D. E. A new model for Proterozoic ocean chemistry. *Nature* **396**, 450–453 (1998).
132. Lyons, T. W., Reinhard, C. T. & Planavsky, N. J. The rise of oxygen in Earth's early ocean and atmosphere. *Nature* **506**, 307–315 (2014).
133. Shen, Y., Buick, R. & Canfield, D. E. Isotopic evidence for microbial sulphate reduction in the early Archaean era. *Nature* **410**, 77–81 (2001).
134. *Ecology of meromictic lakes*. (Springer International Publishing, 2018).
135. Stewart, K. M., Walker, K. F. & Likens, G. E. Meromictic Lakes. in *Encyclopedia of Inland Waters* (ed. Likens, G. E.) 589–602 (Academic Press, 2009).
136. Halm, H. *et al.* Co-occurrence of denitrification and nitrogen fixation in a meromictic lake, Lake Cadagno (Switzerland). *Environ. Microbiol.* **11**, 1945–1958 (2009).
137. Ellwood, M. J. *et al.* Iron isotope transformations in the meromictic Lake Cadagno. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* **255**, 205–221 (2019).
138. Camacho, A. *et al.* Microbial microstratification, inorganic carbon photoassimilation and dark carbon fixation at the chemocline of the meromictic Lake Cadagno (Switzerland) and its relevance to the food web. *Aquat. Sci.* **63**, 91–106 (2001).
139. Falkowski, P. G. *et al.* The evolution of modern eukaryotic phytoplankton. *Science* **305**, 354–360 (2004).

-
140. Weinbauer, M. G. *et al.* Viral ecology of organic and inorganic particles in aquatic systems: avenues for further research. *Aquat. Microb. Ecol.* **57**, 321–341 (2009).
141. Zhao, Z. *et al.* Microbial transformation of virus-induced dissolved organic matter from picocyanobacteria: coupling of bacterial diversity and DOM chemodiversity. *ISME J.* **13**, 2551–2565 (2019).
142. Sime-Ngando, T. *et al.* Lake Pavin: A Pioneer Site for Ecological Studies of Freshwater Viruses. in *Lake Pavin: History, geology, biogeochemistry, and sedimentology of a deep meromictic maar lake* (eds. Sime-Ngando, T., Boivin, P., Chapron, E., Jezequel, D. & Meybeck, M.) 229–244 (Springer International Publishing, 2016).
143. Wu, Y.-T. *et al.* Comprehensive Insights Into Composition, Metabolic Potentials, and Interactions Among Archaeal, Bacterial, and Viral Assemblages in Meromictic Lake Shunet in Siberia. *Front. Microbiol.* **9**, 1763 (2018).
144. Christie-Oleza, J. A., Sousoni, D., Lloyd, M., Armengaud, J. & Scanlan, D. J. Nutrient recycling facilitates long-term stability of marine microbial phototroph-heterotroph interactions. *Nat Microbiol* **2**, 17100 (2017).
145. Coutinho, F. H. *et al.* Marine viruses discovered via metagenomics shed light on viral strategies throughout the oceans. *Nature Communications* vol. 8 (2017).
146. Vaquer-Sunyer, R. & Duarte, C. M. Thresholds of hypoxia for marine biodiversity. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **105**, 15452–15457 (2008).
147. Egli, K. *et al.* Spatial and temporal dynamics of a plume of phototrophic microorganisms in a meromictic alpine lake using turbidity as a measure of cell density. *Aquat. Microb. Ecol.* **35**, 105–113 (2004).
148. Props, R. *et al.* Absolute quantification of microbial taxon abundances. *ISME J.* **11**,

-
- 584–587 (2017).
149. Sun, L. *et al.* *Lentimicrobium saccharophilum* gen. nov., sp. nov., a strictly anaerobic bacterium representing a new family in the phylum Bacteroidetes, and proposal of *Lentimicrobiaceae* fam. nov. *Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol.* **66**, 2635–2642 (2016).
150. Fadeev, E. *et al.* Comparison of Two 16S rRNA Primers (V3-V4 and V4-V5) for Studies of Arctic Microbial Communities. *Front. Microbiol.* **12**, 637526 (2021).
151. Willis, C., Desai, D. & LaRoche, J. Influence of 16S rRNA variable region on perceived diversity of marine microbial communities of the Northern North Atlantic. *FEMS Microbiol. Lett.* **366**, (2019).
152. Burja, A. M., Tamagnini, P., Bustard, M. T. & Wright, P. C. Identification of the green alga, *Chlorella vulgaris* (SDC1) using cyanobacteria derived 16S rDNA primers: targeting the chloroplast. *FEMS Microbiol. Lett.* **202**, 195–203 (2001).
153. Hamilton, M. *et al.* Spatiotemporal Variations in Antarctic Protistan Communities Highlight Phytoplankton Diversity and Seasonal Dominance by a Novel Cryptophyte Lineage. *MBio* e0297321 (2021).
154. Pruesse, E. *et al.* SILVA: a comprehensive online resource for quality checked and aligned ribosomal RNA sequence data compatible with ARB. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **35**, 7188–7196 (2007).
155. Stoyneva, M. P., Gartner, G., Cocquyt, C. & Vyverman, W. *Closteriopsis petkovii*-a new green algal species from Lake Tanganyika (Africa). *PHYTON-HORN-* **45**, 237 (2005).
156. Haas, S., Desai, D. K., LaRoche, J., Pawlowicz, R. & Wallace, D. W. R. Geomicrobiology of the carbon, nitrogen and sulphur cycles in Powell Lake: a permanently stratified water column containing ancient seawater. *Environ. Microbiol.* **21**, 3927–3952 (2019).

-
157. Andrei, A.-Ş. *et al.* Contrasting taxonomic stratification of microbial communities in two hypersaline meromictic lakes. *ISME J.* **9**, 2642–2656 (2015).
158. Tanentzap, A. J. *et al.* Chemical and microbial diversity covary in fresh water to influence ecosystem functioning. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **116**, 24689–24695 (2019).
159. Cabrera, S., López, M. & Tartarotti, B. Phytoplankton and zooplankton response to ultraviolet radiation in a high-altitude Andean lake: short- versus long-term effects. *J. Plankton Res.* **19**, 1565–1582 (1997).
160. Milucka, J. *et al.* Methane oxidation coupled to oxygenic photosynthesis in anoxic waters. *ISME J.* **9**, 1991–2002 (2015).
161. Glazer, A. N. & Wedemayer, G. J. Cryptomonad biliproteins - an evolutionary perspective. *Photosynth. Res.* **46**, 93–105 (1995).
162. Glibert, P. M. *et al.* Pluses and minuses of ammonium and nitrate uptake and assimilation by phytoplankton and implications for productivity and community composition, with emphasis on nitrogen-enriched conditions. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **61**, 165–197 (2016).
163. Brocks, J. J. *et al.* Biomarker evidence for green and purple sulphur bacteria in a stratified Palaeoproterozoic sea. *Nature* **437**, 866–870 (2005).
164. Tonolla, M., Demarta, A., Peduzzi, S., Hahn, D. & Peduzzi, R. In situ analysis of sulfate-reducing bacteria related to *Desulfocapsa thiozymogenes* in the chemocline of meromictic Lake Cadagno (Switzerland). *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **66**, 820–824 (2000).
165. Peduzzi, S., Tonolla, M. & Hahn, D. Isolation and characterization of aggregate-forming sulfate-reducing and purple sulfur bacteria from the chemocline of meromictic Lake Cadagno, Switzerland. *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* **45**, 29–37 (2003).
166. Howard-Varona, C. *et al.* Phage-specific metabolic reprogramming of virocells. *The ISME*

-
- Journal* vol. 14 881–895 (2020).
167. Voorhies, A. A. *et al.* Ecological and genetic interactions between cyanobacteria and viruses in a low-oxygen mat community inferred through metagenomics and metatranscriptomics. *Environ. Microbiol.* **18**, 358–371 (2016).
168. Yau, S. *et al.* Virus-host coexistence in phytoplankton through the genomic lens. *Sci Adv* **6**, eaay2587 (2020).
169. Wigington, C. H. *et al.* Re-examination of the relationship between marine virus and microbial cell abundances. *Nat Microbiol* **1**, 15024 (2016).
170. Anantharaman, K. *et al.* Sulfur oxidation genes in diverse deep-sea viruses. *Science* **344**, 757–760 (2014).
171. Dalcin Martins, P. *et al.* Viral and metabolic controls on high rates of microbial sulfur and carbon cycling in wetland ecosystems. *Microbiome* **6**, 138 (2018).
172. Berg, J. S. *et al.* Ancient and modern geochemical signatures in the 13,500-year sedimentary record of Lake Cadagno. *Front. Earth Sci.* **9**, (2022).
173. Azam, F. & Malfatti, F. Microbial structuring of marine ecosystems. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **5**, 782–791 (2007).
174. Zhang, C. *et al.* Evolving paradigms in biological carbon cycling in the ocean. *Natl Sci Rev* **5**, 481–499 (2018).
175. Del Don, C., Hanselmann, K. W., Peduzzi, R. & Bachofen, R. The meromictic alpine Lake Cadagno: Orographical and biogeochemical description. *Aquat. Sci.* **63**, 70–90 (2001).
176. Martinez, E. *et al.* Reconstructing global chlorophyll-a variations using a non-linear statistical approach. *Front. Mar. Sci.* **7**, (2020).
177. Ogashawara, I. Determination of Phycocyanin from Space—A Bibliometric Analysis.

-
- Remote Sensing* **12**, 567 (2020).
178. Bridgewater, L., American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association & Water Environment Federation. *Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater*. (American Public Health Association, 2012).
179. Hassler, C. S. *et al.* Primary productivity induced by iron and nitrogen in the Tasman Sea: an overview of the PINTS expedition. *Mar. Freshwater Res.* **65**, 517–537 (2014).
180. Moisset, S. A. M., Cabanes, D. J. E., Blanco-Ameijeiras, S. & Hassler, C. S. Response of phytoplankton from the metalimnetic chlorophyll maximum to macro- and micro-nutrients amendments in Lake Geneva. *J. Great Lakes Res.* **45**, 290–299 (2019).
181. Marie, D., Brussaard, C. P. D., Thyrraug, R., Bratbak, G. & Vaulot, D. Enumeration of marine viruses in culture and natural samples by flow cytometry. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **65**, 45–52 (1999).
182. Jacquet, S., Dorigo, U. & Personnic, S. A few tests prior to flow cytometry and epifluorescence analyses of freshwater bacterio- and virioplankton communities. *FLOW Cytom* **1**, 1–30 (2013).
183. Buysschaert, B. *et al.* Flow cytometric fingerprinting to assess the microbial community response to changing water quality and additives. *Environ. Sci.: Water Res. Technol.* **5**, 1672–1682 (2019).
184. Team, R. C. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. 2020, R Foundation for Statistical Computing: 2020, Vienna, Austria. URL <https://www.R-project.org>.
185. Team, R. RStudio: Integrated Development for R. RStudio, PBC, Boston, MA, 2020. (2020).

-
186. Rubbens, P., Props, R., Kerckhof, F.-M., Boon, N. & Waegeman, W. PhenoGMM: Gaussian Mixture Modeling of Cytometry Data Quantifies Changes in Microbial Community Structure. *mSphere* **6**, (2021).
187. Fourquez, M. *et al.* Microbial Competition in the Subpolar Southern Ocean: An Fe–C Co-limitation Experiment. (2020) doi:10.3389/fmars.2019.00776.
188. Van Wambeke, F., Heussner, S., Diaz, F., Raimbault, P. & Conan, P. Small-scale variability in the coupling/uncoupling of bacteria, phytoplankton and organic carbon fluxes along the continental margin of the Gulf of Lions, Northwestern Mediterranean Sea. *J. Mar. Syst.* **33-34**, 411–429 (2002).
189. Kirchman, D. L. Leucine incorporation as a measure of biomass production by heterotrophic bacteria. *Handbook of methods in aquatic* (1993).
190. del Giorgio, P. A. & Cole, J. J. Bacterial growth efficiency in natural aquatic systems. *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Syst.* **29**, 503–541 (1998).
191. Wickham, H. Ggplot2. *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev. Comput. Stat.* **3**, 180–185 (2011).
192. Kassambara, A. ggpubr: ‘ggplot2’ based publication ready plots (Version 0.1. 7). *Obtido desde <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=ggpubr>* (2018).
193. Wei, T. & Simko, V. R package ‘corrplot’: Visualization of a Correlation Matrix (Version 0.84). (2017).
194. Bosshard, P. P., Santini, Y., Grüter, D., Stettler, R. & Bachofen, R. Bacterial diversity and community composition in the chemocline of the meromictic alpine Lake Cadagno as revealed by 16S rDNA analysis. *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* **31**, 173–182 (2000).
195. Duhaime, M. & Cable, R. DNA Extraction from Filters using QIAgen DNeasy and QIAshredder v1 (protocols.io.jx5cpq6). *protocols.io* (2017)

- doi:10.17504/protocols.io.jx5cpq6.
196. Kozich, J. J., Westcott, S. L., Baxter, N. T., Highlander, S. K. & Schloss, P. D. Development of a dual-index sequencing strategy and curation pipeline for analyzing amplicon sequence data on the MiSeq Illumina sequencing platform. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **79**, 5112–5120 (2013).
 197. Schloss, P. D. *et al.* Introducing mothur: open-source, platform-independent, community-supported software for describing and comparing microbial communities. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **75**, 7537–7541 (2009).
 198. Quast, C. *et al.* The SILVA ribosomal RNA gene database project: improved data processing and web-based tools. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **41**, D590–6 (2013).
 199. Rohwer, R. R., Hamilton, J. J., Newton, R. J. & McMahon, K. D. TaxAss: Leveraging a Custom Freshwater Database Achieves Fine-Scale Taxonomic Resolution. *mSphere* **3**, (2018).
 200. McMurdie, P. J. & Holmes, S. Waste not, want not: why rarefying microbiome data is inadmissible. *PLoS Comput. Biol.* **10**, e1003531 (2014).
 201. Lahti, L. & Shetty, S. Introduction to the microbiome R package.
<http://bioconductor.statistik.tu-dortmund.de/packages/3.6/bioc/vignettes/microbiome/inst/doc/vignette.html> (2018).
 202. Lin, H. & Peddada, S. D. Analysis of compositions of microbiomes with bias correction. *Nat. Commun.* **11**, 3514 (2020).
 203. Weiss, S. *et al.* Normalization and microbial differential abundance strategies depend upon data characteristics. *Microbiome* **5**, 27 (2017).
 204. Pruesse, E., Peplies, J. & Glöckner, F. O. SINA: accurate high-throughput multiple

-
- sequence alignment of ribosomal RNA genes. *Bioinformatics* **28**, 1823–1829 (2012).
205. Pfeiffer, W. & Stamatakis, A. Hybrid MPI/Pthreads parallelization of the RAxML phylogenetics code. in *2010 IEEE International Symposium on Parallel Distributed Processing, Workshops and Phd Forum (IPDPSW)* 1–8 (2010).
206. Yu, G. Using ggtree to Visualize Data on Tree-Like Structures. *Curr. Protoc. Bioinformatics* **69**, e96 (2020).
207. Saini, J. S., Hassler, C., Cable, R. N., Fourquez, M. & Danza, F. Bacterial, phytoplankton, and viral dynamics of meromictic Lake Cadagno offer insights into the Proterozoic ocean microbial loop. *bioRxiv* (2021).
208. Bosshard, P. P., Stettler, R. & Bachofen, R. Seasonal and spatial community dynamics in the meromictic Lake Cadagno. *Arch. Microbiol.* **174**, 168–174 (2000).
209. Kneip, C., Lockhart, P., Voss, C. & Maier, U.-G. Nitrogen fixation in eukaryotes--new models for symbiosis. *BMC Evol. Biol.* **7**, 55 (2007).
210. Terrado, R., Monier, A., Edgar, R. & Lovejoy, C. Diversity of nitrogen assimilation pathways among microbial photosynthetic eukaryotes. *J. Phycol.* **51**, 490–506 (2015).
211. Curson, A. R. J. *et al.* DSYB catalyses the key step of dimethylsulfoniopropionate biosynthesis in many phytoplankton. *Nat Microbiol* **3**, 430–439 (2018).
212. Schmidt, A. [62] Sulfur metabolism in cyanobacteria. in *Methods in Enzymology* vol. 167 572–583 (Academic Press, 1988).
213. Stal, L. J. Nitrogen Fixation in Cyanobacteria. *eLS* 1–9 (2015)
doi:10.1002/9780470015902.a0021159.pub2.
214. McDonald, S. M., Plant, J. N. & Worden, A. Z. The mixed lineage nature of nitrogen transport and assimilation in marine eukaryotic phytoplankton: a case study of micromonas.

-
- Mol. Biol. Evol.* **27**, 2268–2283 (2010).
215. Giordano, M., Norici, A. & Hell, R. Sulfur and phytoplankton: acquisition, metabolism and impact on the environment. *New Phytol.* **166**, 371–382 (2005).
216. Delmont, T. O. *et al.* Functional repertoire convergence of distantly related eukaryotic plankton lineages revealed by genome-resolved metagenomics. *bioRxiv* 2020.10.15.341214 (2020) doi:10.1101/2020.10.15.341214.
217. Delmont, T. O., Eren, A. M., Vineis, J. H. & Post, A. F. Genome reconstructions indicate the partitioning of ecological functions inside a phytoplankton bloom in the Amundsen Sea, Antarctica. *Front. Microbiol.* **6**, 1090 (2015).
218. Keeling, P. J. Combining morphology, behaviour and genomics to understand the evolution and ecology of microbial eukaryotes. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. B Biol. Sci.* **374**, 20190085 (2019).
219. Manni, M., Berkeley, M. R., Seppey, M., Simao, F. A. & Zdobnov, E. M. BUSCO update: novel and streamlined workflows along with broader and deeper phylogenetic coverage for scoring of eukaryotic, prokaryotic, and viral genomes. *arXiv [q-bio.GN]* (2021).
220. Stoecker, D. K., Taniguchi, A. & Michaels, A. E. Abundance of autotrophic, mixotrophic and heterotrophic planktonic ciliates in shelf and slope waters. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* **50**, 241–254 (1989).
221. Prézelin, B. B. & Alberte, R. S. Photosynthetic characteristics and organization of chlorophyll in marine dinoflagellates. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **75**, 1801–1804 (1978).
222. Tranvik, L. J., Porter, K. G. & Sieburth, J. M. Occurrence of bacterivory in *Cryptomonas*, a common freshwater phytoplankter. *Oecologia* **78**, 473–476 (1989).
223. Chen, L.-X., Anantharaman, K., Shaiber, A., Eren, A. M. & Banfield, J. F. Accurate and

-
- complete genomes from metagenomes. *Genome Res.* **30**, 315–333 (2020).
224. Sibbald, S. J. & Archibald, J. M. More protist genomes needed. *Nat Ecol Evol* **1**, 145 (2017).
225. Leblanc, K. *et al.* Nanoplanktonic diatoms are globally overlooked but play a role in spring blooms and carbon export. *Nat. Commun.* **9**, 953 (2018).
226. Campbell, C. N., Field, J., MacKechnie, K., Saxon, R. J. & Menéndez, C. R. Cryopreservation to sustain long term maintenance of algae and protozoa in the culture collection of algae and protozoa (CCAP). *Cryobiology* vol. 97 279 (2020).
227. Kieselbach, T., Cheregi, O., Green, B. R. & Funk, C. Proteomic analysis of the phycobiliprotein antenna of the cryptophyte alga *Guillardia theta* cultured under different light intensities. *Photosynth. Res.* **135**, 149–163 (2018).
228. Sumiya, N., Fujiwara, T., Era, A. & Miyagishima, S.-Y. Chloroplast division checkpoint in eukaryotic algae. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **113**, E7629–E7638 (2016).
229. Dumay, J., Morançais, M., Munier, M., Le Guillard, C. & Fleurence, J. Chapter Eleven - Phycoerythrins: Valuable Proteinic Pigments in Red Seaweeds. in *Advances in Botanical Research* (ed. Bourgougnon, N.) vol. 71 321–343 (Academic Press, 2014).
230. Beutler, M. *Spectral Fluorescence of Chlorophyll and Phycobilins as an in Situ Tool of Phytoplankton Analysis: Models, Algorithms and Instruments*. (Verlag nicht ermittelbar, 2003).
231. Alam, T., Najam, L., Al-Harrasi, A. & Others. Extraction of natural pigments from marine algae. *Journal of Agricultural and marine sciences* **23**, 81–91 (2018).
232. Haverkamp, T. H. A. & Others. Shades of red and green: the colorful diversity and ecology of picocyanobacteria in the Baltic Sea. (Netherlands Institute of Ecology (NIOO)-Royal

-
- Netherlands Academy of Arts ..., 2008).
233. Dierckxsens, N., Mardulyn, P. & Smits, G. NOVOPlasty: de novo assembly of organelle genomes from whole genome data. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **45**, e18 (2017).
234. Tillich, M. *et al.* GeSeq - versatile and accurate annotation of organelle genomes. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **45**, W6–W11 (2017).
235. Neely, C. J., Hu, S. K., Alexander, H. & Tully, B. J. The high-throughput gene prediction of more than 1,700 eukaryote genomes using the software package EukMetaSanity. *bioRxiv* (2021).
236. Stanke, M., Steinkamp, R., Waack, S. & Morgenstern, B. AUGUSTUS: a web server for gene finding in eukaryotes. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **32**, W309–12 (2004).
237. Levy Karin, E., Mirdita, M. & Söding, J. MetaEuk-sensitive, high-throughput gene discovery, and annotation for large-scale eukaryotic metagenomics. *Microbiome* **8**, 48 (2020).
238. Jones, S. Five ways to cycle carbon. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **6**, 95–95 (2008).
239. Gowik, U. & Westhoff, P. The path from C3 to C4 photosynthesis. *Plant Physiol.* **155**, 56–63 (2011).
240. Hultine, K. R., Cushman, J. C. & Williams, D. G. New perspectives on crassulacean acid metabolism biology. *J. Exp. Bot.* **70**, 6489–6493 (2019).
241. Hodson, R. C., Schiff, J. A. & Scarsella, A. J. Studies of Sulfate Utilization by Algae. 7. In vivo Metabolism of Thiosulfate by *Chlorella*. *Plant Physiol.* **43**, 570–577 (1968).
242. Wedding, R. T. & Black, M. K. Uptake and Metabolism of Sulfate by *Chlorella*. I. Sulfate Accumulation and Active Sulfate. *Plant Physiol.* **35**, 72–80 (1960).
243. Kuypers, M. M. M., Marchant, H. K. & Kartal, B. The microbial nitrogen-cycling network.

-
- Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **16**, 263–276 (2018).
244. Sanz-Luque, E., Chamizo-Ampudia, A., Llamas, A., Galvan, A. & Fernandez, E. Understanding nitrate assimilation and its regulation in microalgae. *Front. Plant Sci.* **6**, 899 (2015).
245. Cramer, M. & Myers, J. Nitrate reduction and assimilation in *Chlorella*. *J. Gen. Physiol.* **32**, 93–102 (1948).
246. Okuda, A. & Ida, S. Assimilation of ammonia, nitrate, and urea by *Chlorella ellipsoidea*. *Soil Sci. Plant Nutr.* **12**, 23–30 (1966).
247. Morris, L. & Ahmed, J. The effect of light on nitrate and nitrite assimilation by *Chlorella* and *Ankistrodesmus*. *Physiol. Plant.* **22**, 1166–1174 (1969).
248. Pozzobon, V., Cui, N., Moreaud, A., Michiels, E. & Levasseur, W. Nitrate and nitrite as mixed source of nitrogen for *Chlorella vulgaris*: Growth, nitrogen uptake and pigment contents. *Bioresour. Technol.* **330**, 124995 (2021).
249. Scherholz, M. L. & Curtis, W. R. Achieving pH control in microalgal cultures through fed-batch addition of stoichiometrically-balanced growth media. *BMC Biotechnol.* **13**, 39 (2013).
250. Kamp, A. & Stief, P. Editorial: Eukaryotic Microbes Store Nitrate for ‘Breathing’ in Anoxia. *Front. Microbiol.* **8**, 2439 (2017).
251. Sakarika, M. & Kornaros, M. *Chlorella vulgaris* as a green biofuel factory: Comparison between biodiesel, biogas and combustible biomass production. *Bioresour. Technol.* **273**, 237–243 (2019).
252. Panahi, Y., Darvishi, B., Jowzi, N., Beiraghdar, F. & Sahebkar, A. *Chlorella vulgaris*: A Multifunctional Dietary Supplement with Diverse Medicinal Properties. *Curr. Pharm. Des.*

-
- 22**, 164–173 (2016).
253. Bushnell, B. BBTools software package. URL <http://sourceforge.net/projects/bbmap> **578**, 579 (2014).
254. Bushnell, B. *BBMap: A fast, accurate, splice-aware aligner*. <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1241166> (2014).
255. Langmead, B. & Salzberg, S. L. Fast gapped-read alignment with Bowtie 2. *Nat. Methods* **9**, 357–359 (2012).
256. Li, H. *et al.* The Sequence Alignment/Map format and SAMtools. *Bioinformatics* **25**, 2078–2079 (2009).
257. Gruber-Vodicka, H. R., Seah, B. K. B. & Pruesse, E. phyloFlash: Rapid Small-Subunit rRNA Profiling and Targeted Assembly from Metagenomes. *mSystems* **5**, (2020).
258. Hyatt, D. *et al.* Prodigal: prokaryotic gene recognition and translation initiation site identification. *BMC Bioinformatics* **11**, 119 (2010).
259. Buchfink, B., Reuter, K. & Drost, H.-G. Sensitive protein alignments at tree-of-life scale using DIAMOND. *Nat. Methods* **18**, 366–368 (2021).
260. Gish, W. & States, D. J. Identification of protein coding regions by database similarity search. *Nat. Genet.* **3**, 266–272 (1993).
261. Database resources of the national center for biotechnology information. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **46**, D8–D13 (2018).
262. Boratyn, G. M. *et al.* Domain enhanced lookup time accelerated BLAST. *Biol. Direct* **7**, 12 (2012).
263. Seppey, M., Manni, M. & Zdobnov, E. M. BUSCO: Assessing Genome Assembly and Annotation Completeness. *Methods in Molecular Biology* 227–245 (2019)

doi:10.1007/978-1-4939-9173-0_14.

264. Waterhouse, R. M. *et al.* BUSCO Applications from Quality Assessments to Gene Prediction and Phylogenomics. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* **35**, 543–548 (2018).
265. Kriventseva, E. V. *et al.* OrthoDB v10: sampling the diversity of animal, plant, fungal, protist, bacterial and viral genomes for evolutionary and functional annotations of orthologs. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **47**, D807–D811 (2019).
266. Challis, R., Richards, E., Rajan, J., Cochrane, G. & Blaxter, M. BlobToolKit - Interactive Quality Assessment of Genome Assemblies. *G3* **10**, 1361–1374 (2020).
267. Rozewicki, J., Li, S., Amada, K. M., Standley, D. M. & Katoh, K. MAFFT-DASH: integrated protein sequence and structural alignment. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **47**, W5–W10 (2019).
268. Talavera, G. & Castresana, J. Improvement of phylogenies after removing divergent and ambiguously aligned blocks from protein sequence alignments. *Syst. Biol.* **56**, 564–577 (2007).
269. Mega, X. Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis across Computing Platforms—PubMed.
270. Huson, D. H. & Scornavacca, C. Dendroscope 3: an interactive tool for rooted phylogenetic trees and networks. *Syst. Biol.* **61**, 1061–1067 (2012).
271. Kanehisa, M., Sato, Y., Kawashima, M., Furumichi, M. & Tanabe, M. KEGG as a reference resource for gene and protein annotation. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **44**, D457–62 (2016).
272. Kanehisa, M., Sato, Y. & Morishima, K. BlastKOALA and GhostKOALA: KEGG Tools for Functional Characterization of Genome and Metagenome Sequences. *J. Mol. Biol.* **428**, 726–731 (2016).

-
273. Kanehisa, M., Sato, Y. & Kawashima, M. KEGG mapping tools for uncovering hidden features in biological data. *Protein Sci.* (2021) doi:10.1002/pro.4172.
274. Castelvechi, D. Universe has ten times more galaxies than researchers thought. *Nature* (2016) doi:10.1038/nature.2016.20809.
275. Fuhrman, J. A. Marine viruses and their biogeochemical and ecological effects. *Nature* **399**, 541–548 (1999).
276. Kuzyakov, Y. & Mason-Jones, K. Viruses in soil: Nano-scale undead drivers of microbial life, biogeochemical turnover and ecosystem functions. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* **127**, 305–317 (2018).
277. Roux, S. *et al.* Ecogenomics and potential biogeochemical impacts of globally abundant ocean viruses. *Nature* **537**, 689–693 (2016).
278. Drewes, F., Peter, H. & Sommaruga, R. Are viruses important in the plankton of highly turbid glacier-fed lakes? *Sci. Rep.* **6**, 24608 (2016).
279. Chen, Y., Wang, Y., Paez-Espino, D., Polz, M. F. & Zhang, T. Prokaryotic viruses impact functional microorganisms in nutrient removal and carbon cycle in wastewater treatment plants. *Nat. Commun.* **12**, 5398 (2021).
280. Brum, J. R., Schenck, R. O. & Sullivan, M. B. Global morphological analysis of marine viruses shows minimal regional variation and dominance of non-tailed viruses. *ISME J.* **7**, 1738–1751 (2013).
281. Moniruzzaman, M., Weinheimer, A. R., Martinez-Gutierrez, C. A. & Aylward, F. O. Widespread endogenization of giant viruses shapes genomes of green algae. *Nature* **588**, 141–145 (2020).
282. Weinheimer, A. R. & Aylward, F. O. Infection strategy and biogeography distinguish

-
- cosmopolitan groups of marine jumbo bacteriophages. *bioRxiv* 2022.01.18.476781 (2022)
doi:10.1101/2022.01.18.476781.
283. Weinbauer, M., Chen, F., Wilhelm, S. & Demetriou, D. Fig. 2. The viral shunt in the context of oceanic carbon cycling. *ResearchGate*
https://www.researchgate.net/figure/The-viral-shunt-in-the-context-of-oceanic-carbon-cycling-Potential-major-influences-of_fig2_261871540 (2011).
284. Charon, J., Marcelino, V. R., Wetherbee, R. & Holmes, E. C. Figure 1. The enormous diversity of algae contrasts with their poorly. *ResearchGate*
https://www.researchgate.net/figure/The-enormous-diversity-of-algae-contrasts-with-their-poorly-characterized-viromes-A_fig1_344877223 (2020).
285. Needham, D. M. *et al.* A distinct lineage of giant viruses brings a rhodopsin photosystem to unicellular marine predators. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **116**, 20574–20583 (2019).
286. Mrázek, J. & Karlin, S. Distinctive features of large complex virus genomes and proteomes. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **104**, 5127–5132 (2007).
287. Seaton, G., Lee, K. & Rohozinski, J. Photosynthetic Shutdown in *Chlorella* NC64A Associated with the Infection Cycle of *Paramecium bursaria* *Chlorella* Virus-1. *Plant Physiol.* **108**, 1431–1438 (1995).
288. Milrot, E. *et al.* Structural studies demonstrating a bacteriophage-like replication cycle of the eukaryote-infecting *Paramecium bursaria* *chlorella* virus-1. *PLoS Pathog.* **13**, e1006562 (2017).
289. Guo, J. *et al.* VirSorter2: a multi-classifier, expert-guided approach to detect diverse DNA and RNA viruses. *Microbiome* **9**, 37 (2021).
290. Shaffer, M. *et al.* DRAM for distilling microbial metabolism to automate the curation of

-
- microbiome function. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **48**, 8883–8900 (2020).
291. Aylward, F. O. & Moniruzzaman, M. ViralRecall-A Flexible Command-Line Tool for the Detection of Giant Virus Signatures in 'Omic Data. *Viruses* **13**, (2021).
292. Kieft, K., Zhou, Z. & Anantharaman, K. VIBRANT: automated recovery, annotation and curation of microbial viruses, and evaluation of viral community function from genomic sequences. *Microbiome* **8**, 90 (2020).
293. Nayfach, S. *et al.* CheckV assesses the quality and completeness of metagenome-assembled viral genomes. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **39**, 578–585 (2021).
294. Ren, J. *et al.* Identifying viruses from metagenomic data using deep learning. *Quant Biol* **8**, 64–77 (2020).
295. Hegarty, B. E. *et al.* A Snapshot of the Global Drinking Water Virome: Diversity and Metabolic Potential Vary with Residual Disinfectant Use. *bioRxiv* 2021.10.07.463401 (2022) doi:10.1101/2021.10.07.463401.
296. Bossard, P. *et al.* Limnological description of the Lakes Zürich, Lucerne, and Cadagno. *Aquat. Sci.* **63**, 225–249 (2001).
297. Rubbens, P. *et al.* Randomized Lasso Links Microbial Taxa with Aquatic Functional Groups Inferred from Flow Cytometry. *mSystems* **4**, (2019).
298. Pester, M., Bittner, N., Deevong, P., Wagner, M. & Loy, A. A 'rare biosphere' microorganism contributes to sulfate reduction in a peatland. *ISME J.* **4**, 1591–1602 (2010).
299. Heyse, J. *et al.* Predicting the Presence and Abundance of Bacterial Taxa in Environmental Communities through Flow Cytometric Fingerprinting. *mSystems* **6**, e0055121 (2021).
300. Mann, N. H., Cook, A., Millard, A., Bailey, S. & Clokie, M. Marine ecosystems: bacterial photosynthesis genes in a virus. *Nature* **424**, 741 (2003).

301. Kieft, K. *et al.* Ecology of inorganic sulfur auxiliary metabolism in widespread bacteriophages. *Nat. Commun.* **12**, 3503 (2021).

